

Deliverable D3.1 – Methodology for Double Loop Action Research

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Executive Summary

Purpose and scope of this report

The more4nature project endeavours to catalyse transformative change in conservation efforts regarding zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention, by strengthening the role of citizens and communities in environmental compliance assurance (ECA) monitoring and enforcement via Citizen Science (CS) and Citizen Generated Data (CGD), and in environmental compliance promotion via citizen & community-led actions. To achieve this, the more4nature project works with a large number of existing CS initiatives which are interested in increasing and institutionalizing contributions to ECA.

To stimulate transformative change in current ECA practice, the project will assist 40 cases with a process of social learning and socio-technical experimentation, combined with provision of algorithms, models, and interoperable systems to public authorities, to encourage the intended validation and uptake of citizen observations for ECA.

This report presents the conceptual framework for transformative change towards collaborative ECA envisioned by the more4nature project, and the project's methodology for Double Loop Action Research that will guide the more4nature case contacts and stakeholders through a staged learning process. It elaborates the methodology used to stimulate transformative change and empower civil society actors in 20 Pioneer and 20 Follower Cases.

This report is intended as a reference document for the partners of the more4nature consortium, capturing:

1. the rationale and theoretical grounding of the more4nature Conceptual Framework guiding the work in the more4nature project at large and in the cases in particular;
2. how the Double Loop Action Research methodology will be applied to the Pioneer Cases and the Follower Cases to ensure effective progress in the cases, facilitate interactions between the cases and WPs, and safeguard the application of guiding principles and ethics requirements; and
3. the initial version of the generic more4nature case compendium, a structured 'Notebook' on the more4nature shared online workspace, that serves as primary tool for implementation of the methodology in the Pioneer Cases.

Conceptual framework

The more4nature conceptual framework provides a coherent frame for guiding and analysing the diverse empirical experience of the cases and enables the development of generalized understanding and recommendations from their activities. It consists of

- i. the more4nature concept of collaborative ECA and
- ii. the conceptual framework of transformative change towards collaborative ECA through social learning and socio-technical experimentation

The more4nature concept of *collaborative* Environmental Compliance Assurance captures the shared understanding of how CS can contribute, in different ways, to the three ECA pillars (compliance promotion, compliance monitoring and compliance enforcement) via

- CGD - data generated by diverse forms of CS initiatives
- CCLA - actions and interventions, taken or initiated by individual citizens, civil society organizations or communities.

Figure 1 more4nature concept of collaborative Environmental Compliance Assurance (source: more4nature consortium)

Both CGD and CCLA provide opportunities for civilian actors to contribute effectively to improving the implementation of environmental rules on the ground, not all of which require participation in formal ECA processes. In collaborative environmental compliance assurance, citizens and communities work in partnership with relevant authorities in promoting, monitoring and acting to protect the environment.

The more4nature conceptual framework of transformative change towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance through social learning and socio-technical experimentation is the result of careful combination of concepts and insights from environmental governance and compliance theory and approaches, behavioural science, the science of citizen science, sustainability science and innovation studies.

Figure 2 more4nature conceptual framework for transformative change towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance (source: the authors)

We use the Institutional Analysis and Development (IAD) as the underlying framework for generalized analysis of the real-life settings of the more4nature cases. This adapted version of the IAD serves to facilitate the analysis of processes that create or change institutional arrangements in ECA (towards collaborative ECA) based on individual and collective choices, including a review of actors, norms, institutional settings, incentive structures, rules, and more. Specifically, the adapted IAD framework for the more4nature project consists of four elements:

Reimagining and deepening the role of citizens and communities in *collaborative* ECA via Citizen Science, Citizen Generated Data and Citizen & Community-Led Actions constitutes a **transformative change**. This requires visioning and experimenting with new roles and interactions to create possibilities for collaboration previously unimagined. Transformative **social learning** as intended by more4nature will not occur by coincidence. Rather, it will be initiated, stimulated and facilitated via **Learning Journeys** to create spaces in which conditions are conducive to social learning, inviting the right configuration of stakeholders into the space, and assist with the co-creation of knowledge socio-technical experimentation.

This comprehensive process seeks to change existing systems and norms, and ultimately will lead to changes in

- i) the *form and level of collaboration and trust* among core actors should change, including use of CS tools to facilitate communication or collaboration between groups;
- ii) the *level of compliance* in the case area,
- iii) which is intended to impact the environmental *state of the resource* in focus of a case over time (e.g. air quality in the zero pollution theme, pollinators in the biodiversity protection theme, or forest health in the deforestation prevention theme). In most cases, the last is likely to happen beyond the timeline of the more4nature project.

Key elements for success of the social learning process are the formation of a group of actors who are in a position to negotiate the relevant outcomes, guided exchanges to arrive at a joint understanding of the challenges to be addressed, and mechanisms to institutionalize agreements of the resulting collaboration. The model of *behavioural dynamics in collaborative ECA* will guide the project work to help analyse **evolving interaction patterns** among these core actors and tackle the step from citizen science and citizen & community-led actions to actually contributing to ECA.

Methodology

The more4nature conceptual frame is operationalized as a methodological approach for double loop action research with two sets of 20 cases each, creating individual Learning Journeys for 40 participating cases.

At project level, the more4nature methodology consists of detailed instructions for consistent and overall coherent elements of the action research activities driven at case level first in the Pioneer Cases and then in the Follower Cases. The cases are supported by social science expertise from WP1 with conceptually grounded guidance for empowering citizens and fostering transformative change; and by data science expertise from WP2 with tools and principles enabling integration of CGD in collaborative ECA. The methodology for stimulating, guiding and tracking social learning towards collaborative ECA in all more4nature case is complemented by an approach for peer learning, co-evaluation and synthesis to ensure that resulting insights can cross-fertilize activities between cases, and feed into the production of generic guidelines and recommendations. At the project level, the methodology provides procedures to ensure effective progress in the cases, coordinates research activities and interactions between the cases and project tasks and work packages, and ensures that all case activities reflect and adhere to the ethical principles of the more4nature project.

At case level, the two sequential “loops” of Action Research in Pioneer and Follower cases aim to

- Explore the applicability and validity of the more4nature socio-technical knowledge, tools and methods in transformative change towards collaborative ECA;
- Foster learning and knowledge co-creation among citizens, communities, regulators and enforcement agencies, as well as among citizen science practitioners on new forms of collaboration for effective environmental compliance assurance;

- Support the co-design of the tools and citizen actions for environmental protection via synergies between CS initiatives and LivingLabs for green and digital transformations;
- Promote recognition by policy makers and authorities of the value of CGD and CCLA in collaborative ECA.

A guided and interactive **Learning Journey** for the participating cases forms the core of the more4nature action research activities. The Learning Journey builds directly on the more4nature conceptual frame, which

- Provides the basis for guidance of cases in stimulating interactive processes of knowledge co-production and learning;
- Supports identification and engagement of relevant stakeholders in their real-life context and with their practice-based knowledge as frame of reference; and
- Proposes scientific concepts and approaches useful to enhance understanding the cases and foster the emergence of solutions outside and beyond the current state of practice.

The Learning Journey is structured into five phases, with each stage designed to prepare and facilitate stakeholder decision-making on all relevant aspects of the evolving local solution. The project team provides socio-technical learning impulses in each phase to stimulate social learning towards cooperative ECA, but stakeholders will remain in charge of all decisions and results.

Figure 3 Stages and expected outputs/outcomes of the more4nature Learning Journey in the cases (source: the authors)

The more4nature methodology comprises **five elements**:

1. Overarching guiding principles.
2. Stipulations for case stakeholders to be engaged
3. Key stages with generic list of activities and envisaged outcomes per stage
4. Compendium as one-stop-shop for instructions, worksheets and guidelines (online workspace)
5. Guidance system: dedicated teams with more4nature partners per thematic area (zero pollution, biodiversity protection, deforestation prevention) and WP1 & WP2 mentors

Implementation and next steps

For the thematic teams in more4nature, the compendium included in this report (Part 2), along with ongoing coaching from experts in WP1 and WP2, serves as a crucial tool for ensuring the successful and consistent implementation of the Learning Journeys in the more4nature Pioneer Cases.

Figure 4 Implementation of the more4nature methodology in the Pioneers & Follower cases

This report introduces the initial prototype version of the more4nature compendium.

Figure 5 Screenshot of the prototype more4nature case compendium

The final version, containing complete instructions for all stages of the methodology, will be developed during the first cycle of the more4nature Double Loop Action Research. After being reviewed and refined, it will be implemented in the second stage of the more4nature Double Loop Action Research with the Follower Cases.

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Glossary of terms

Term	Definition
Acquis	The collection of common rights and obligations that constitute the body of EU law, and is incorporated into the legal systems of EU Member States. The EU acquis evolves continuously over time and includes the content, principles and political objectives of the EU Treaties; any legislation adopted to apply those treaties and the case-law developed by the Court of Justice of the European Union; declarations and resolutions that are adopted by the EU; measures in fields of common policy; international agreements that the EU concludes, and agreements concluded among the Member States themselves with regard to the EU's activities (eur-lex.europa.eu)
Action Research	participatory, democratic process concerned with developing practical knowing grounded in a participatory worldview, and seeking to bring together action and reflection, theory and practice, in participation with others, in the pursuit of practical solutions to issues of pressing concern to people, and more generally the flourishing of individual persons and their communities (Reason and Bradbury, 2001).
Authoritative text	Text that emanates from a legitimate authority (i.e. the state), and that is written (positive law). Broadly used to refer to legislation, case law and doctrinal literature as the main sources of information for understanding positive law (Langbroek <i>et al.</i> , 2017).
Citizen & Community-led Action	Actions and interventions for improving the implementation of environmental rules on the ground, related to the three pillars of ECA, taken or initiated by individual citizens, civil society organizations or communities.
Citizen Generated Data	Data streams generated through Citizen Science
Citizen Science	Citizen science (CS) refers to the involvement of civilian actors in various forms of collaborative data and knowledge generation, including science-driven projects, initiatives to democratize science and policy via science citizenship, civic and community-based (environmental) monitoring, and citizen observatories.
Citizen Observatory	A particular form of CS that provides the means for new forms of interactions between policy-makers, the general public and the scientific community. COs involve ICT-facilitated bi- and multidirectional data and information flows, typically linked to participatory processes in environmental monitoring and governance.
Civic Environmental Monitoring	The use by 'ordinary' people of monitoring devices (e.g., sensors) or their senses e.g., smell; hearing) to detect environmental issues.
Collaborative environmental compliance assurance	Citizens and communities - in partnership with relevant authorities - collaborate in promoting, monitoring and acting to protect the environment.
Compliance	Act of submitting or yielding power to an authority and doing what is expected or required under a rule system enacted by that authority.
Compliance Promotion	range of actions that authorities undertake to help businesses and individuals meet their obligations, and to prevent or reduce infringements and the harm that they cause

Duty-Holders	Natural or legal persons, including public authorities, who must respect obligations derived from EU environment legislation when carrying out activities that involve emissions into or other physical impacts on the environment.
Environmental Compliance Assurance	“all the ways in which public authorities promote, monitor and enforce compliance with the relevant rules” (European Commission).
Environmental Compliance Monitoring	All forms of inspection, surveillance and investigation undertaken by Environmental authorities to verify compliance or discover and characterise infringements
Environmental conflict mediation	Ways to address an environmental conflict outside of court (e.g. through alternative dispute resolution techniques –ADR).
Environmental enforcement	Actions drawing on administrative, criminal and civil law to stop, deter, sanction and obtain redress for non-compliant conduct and encourage compliance.
Environmental litigation	Court cases on environmental issues involving citizens, companies and/or governmental and non-governmental actors.
FabLab	Fabrication Laboratory. A small-scale workshop offering open access to (personal) digital fabrication, which can be used by the public to create transform creative ideas into tangible prototypes.
Fair & Care Principles	Principles in scientific and indigenous data management (Global Indigenous Data Alliance (GIDA))
Learning Journey	Facilitated 5-stage process stimulating social learning among stakeholders of the more4nature Pioneer Cases.
LivingLab	mechanism developed to support innovation by offering a ‘neutral arena’ where different stakeholders would be able to meet and co-develop innovative solutions
Social Learning	Intentional process of collective sense-making and knowledge co-creation with the aims of boosting cooperation and learning among multiple stakeholders. Involves a common vision of the problem and of the desired outcomes to be achieved, as well as a social learning agenda clarifying specific aspects and activities to be undertaken and changes at individual, relational, organizational and institutional levels needed to achieve the desired outcomes.
Subsidiary Principle	Principle of policy making, for example, applied in the European Union, stipulating positively that a higher level policy body must act where the objectives to be pursued can be better attained collectively, and negatively that it must not act where objectives can be satisfactorily attained by subordinate bodies acting individually.
Transposition	Process of adopting binding European regulation into national law.

List of abbreviations

Acronym	Full Name
API	Application programming interface
CARE	Collective benefits, Authority to control, Responsibility & Ethics
CCLA	Citizen & Community-led Action
CGD	Citizen Generated Data
CO	Citizen Observatory
CoP	Community of Practice
CRAVED	Concealable, Removable, Available, Valuable, Enjoyable and Disposable [as characteristics of an environmental product]
CREAF	Centro de Investigación Ecológica y Aplicaciones Forestales
CS	Citizen Science
CSA	Community-Supported Agriculture
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
CW	Irish Coastal Environment Group (Coastwatch)
D	Deliverable
DLR	Doctrinal Legal Research
DoA	Description of the Action (for the more4nature project)
DSSA	Data Space Support Center
EC	European Commission
ECA	Environmental Compliance Assurance
ECSA	Verein der Bürgerwissenschaften - ECSA e.V.
EEA	European Environmental Agency
EIR	Environmental Implementation Review
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
EW	Earthwatch
F2F	Face-to-face
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable & Reusable
FC.ID	Fciencias.id – Association para a investigacao e desenvolvimento de ciencias
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
IAD	Institutional Analysis and Development [Framework]
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IHE	Stichting IHE Delft Institute for Water Education
IMPEL	European Union Network for Implementation and Enforcement of Environmental Law
INECE	International Network for Environmental Compliance and Enforcement
KSA	Stowarzyszenie Krakowski Alarm Smogowy
M	Month
MAR2PROTECT	Preventing groundwater contamination related to global and climate change through a holistic approach based on managed aquifer recharge (Horizon Europe Project)
MICS	Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science [Horizon Europe project]
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NILU	Stiftelsen Nilu
NIOO	Netherlands Institute of Ecology

Acronym	Full Name
NIVA	Norsk Institutt for Vannforskning
NORD	Nordisk Fond for Miljø og Udvikling
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PAR	Participatory Action Research
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Sociological, Technological, Legal and Environmental context
RIVM	Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en milieu
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SI	Social Innovation
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
T	Task
TFEU	Treaty about the Functioning of the European Union
TPB	Theory of Planned Behaviour
UCPH	Københavns Universitet
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
VITO	Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek n.v.
WCMC	World Conservation Monitoring Centre Lbg
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
Z/B/D	Zero pollution, biodiversity protection, deforestation prevention

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Part I

Conceptual basis & methodology

1 Introduction

1.1 More4nature project summary: Vision, objectives and project organization

The more4nature project endeavours to catalyse transformative change in conservation efforts regarding zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention, by strengthening the role of citizens and communities in environmental compliance assurance (ECA) monitoring and enforcement via Citizen Science (CS) and Citizen Generated Data (CGD), and in environmental compliance promotion via citizen & community-led actions (CCLA). The overall vision is supported by five specific objectives. The project will

- 1) Define an **overarching conceptual framework for collaborative environmental compliance assurance**, building on systemic behavioural and relational models that detect obstacles and opportunities for involvement of civil society actors in compliance promotion, monitoring and enforcement. Action research in 20 Pioneer+20 Follower Cases will explore and test a set of behavioural best practices and technical tools derived from the framework, and promote their adoption via the project knowledge platform and other dissemination means;
- 2) Develop Trusted and FAIR principles for data governance, data validation and data management, to **qualify its citizen-generate data for the European Green Deal Data Space (GDDS)**. The project will adopt the necessary building blocks as defined by the Data Space Support Center and the Great project and opt-in as a node in the GDDS, to enable the sharing, community validation and reuse of citizen-generated data and information as complement to official observations.
- 3) Generate indicators using the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), **establishing CS as one methodology for elaborating policy indicators in compliance monitoring**. Including CDG-based indicators in the shared Scientific Data Space creates exposure, enables comparative analysis with legal thresholds, and supports the generation of temporal tendencies and future projections in an integrated way for the benefit of local/regional/nations authorities.
- 4) Empower citizens and communities, creating and exploring spaces in which **civil society actors play an active and accepted role in collaborative Environmental Compliance Assurance (ECA)**. The objective is to move beyond general collection of high quality CGD g, towards targeted contribution of complementary and accepted data to formal compliance monitoring indicators and systems, support for compliance promotion and compliance enforcement through community-led actions co-designed with competent authorities, and contributions to policy design and policy evaluation.
- 5) **Transform current ECA practices of authorities and enforcement agencies**, enabling the combination of official data and citizen science data to improve reporting on implementation and progress within formal monitoring frameworks. CS is increasingly accepted as a source of reliable data, but a deeper transformation is needed to enable meaningful collaboration between authorities and civil society actors in ECA mechanisms, and integrate CGD in the monitoring frameworks for zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention.

To achieve its objectives, the more4nature project works with a large number of existing CS initiatives which are interested in increasing and institutionalizing contributions to ECA. To stimulate transformative change in current ECA practice, the project will assist these cases with a process of social learning and socio-technical experimentation, combined with provision of algorithms, models, and interoperable systems to public authorities, to encourage the intended validation and uptake of citizen observations for ECA.

The more4nature project is organised into 6 Work Packages (WPs):

- WP1 Social dimensions of empowering citizens and CS initiatives in collaborative ECA
- WP2 Technical dimensions: Geospatial modelling with FAIR CGD. From validated CGD to spatialized policy indicators
- WP3 Case studies on collaborative ECA for zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention
- WP4 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
- WP5 Project Management
- WP6 Ethics requirements

1.2 Purpose of the document

This report is produced by T3.1, to summarize the **conceptual framework for the transformative change towards collaborative ECA** envisioned by the more4nature project, and to present the project's **methodology for Double Loop Action Research** that will guide the more4nature case contacts and stakeholders through a staged learning process. In particular, it serves to elaborate the methodology used to stimulate transformative change and empower civil society actors in 20 Pioneer and 20 Follower Cases (WP3). *This report is intended as a reference document for the partners of the more4nature consortium, capturing:*

1. the rationale and theoretical grounding of the more4nature Conceptual Framework guiding the work in the more4nature project at large and in the cases in particular;
2. how the Double Loop Action Research methodology will be applied to the Pioneer Cases (T3.2) and the Follower Cases (T3.4) to ensure effective progress in the cases, facilitate interactions between the cases and WPs, and safeguard the application of guiding principles and ethics requirements; and
3. the initial version of the generic more4nature case compendium, a structured 'Notebook' on the more4nature shared online workspace, that serves as primary tool for implementation of the methodology in the Pioneer Cases.

1.3 Structure of the document

This report is structured into two parts:

Part 1 presents the theoretical and evidence-informed foundations of the more4nature Conceptual Framework (chapter 2); the more4nature methodology for the Double Loop Action Research and details of its implementation (chapter 3); as well as conclusions regarding next steps in the more4nature project (chapter 4).

Part 2 presents the prototype compendium that will be used by the more4nature Pioneer Cases to guide completion of each stage and drive transformative change towards collaborative ECA. The compendium will be embedded in various interactions within the project (e.g. thematic clustering of cases, cross-case Communities of Practice).

2 more4nature conceptual framework

2.1 Approach to framework development

Transformative change towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance (collaborative ECA) requires a holistic and comprehensive process pertinent to the changing of existing systems and norms. The overall research question of the more4nature project is *how the transition towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance as processes of change can be realised for zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention*. The question will be answered by means of Action Research with 20 + 20 case studies. Action Research is “a participatory, democratic process concerned with developing practical knowing in the pursuit of worthwhile human purposes, grounded in a participatory worldview [...]. It seeks to bring together action and reflection, theory and practice, in participation with others, in the pursuit of practical solutions to issues of pressing concern to people, and more generally the flourishing of individual persons and their communities” (Reason and Bradbury, 2001, p. 1).

A conceptual framework for this approach has to deliver on four functions. It has to

- 1) Provide a coherent frame for guiding and analysing the diverse empirical experiences in cases and enable the development of generalized understanding and recommendations;
- 2) Support the engagement of relevant actors (i.e. citizen science initiatives, authorities and experts) and capture their real-life settings and practice-based knowledge as frame of reference;
- 3) Provide a basis for consistent guidance of case activities stimulating interactive processes of knowledge co-production and learning
- 4) Complement empirical insights with sound scientific concepts and approaches foster the emergence of solutions outside and beyond the current state of practice.

The development of the more4nature conceptual framework employed a combination of deductive and inductive approaches to ensure that it is based on available scientific knowledge as well as practice-based knowledge from the more4nature partners (see Figure 1).

Figure 6 Development of the more4nature conceptual framework (source: the authors)

As underlying framework for generalized analysis of the real-life case settings, the Institutional Analysis and Development (IAD) was chosen (Reed *et al.*, 2018). The IAD framework for generalization of the more4nature case experiences is presented in section 2.2, with additional elaboration of the more4nature core actor groups (section 2.3) and the case context aspects (section

2.4). The conceptual framing of European and international environmental policy presents a specific challenge; therefore section 2.5 provides a dedicated overview of the relevant aspects.

To enrich the theoretical foundation with experiential knowledge, a task force of more4nature partners held a series of exploratory sessions (online and hybrid) in spring 2024. This task force elaborated experiences into a shared conceptualization of the potential contributions of CGD as well as Citizen & Community-Led Actions (CCLA) in collaborative ECA. Practice-based components of the framework, drawing both on results from the exploratory workshops, and on empirical work undertaken by task forces and expert groups of the European Commission and the OECD, are elaborated further in section 2.6.

In line with the requirements outlined above, the more4nature conceptual framework was completed with a desk study and literature research, integrating or drawing on the state-of-the art in

- a. Transformative change via social learning and social innovation;
- b. Systemic behavioural models in change processes (incl. relational models of behaviour); and
- c. Compliance theory and approaches.

These additions serve to transform the framework from a tool for the analysis of self-organised processes to a tool for the guidance of a facilitated learning and change process. Theoretical contributions to the conceptual framework are elaborated in sections 2.6.4 and 2.8. Chapter 2 concludes with a summary description of the resulting overarching framework (section 2.9). The operationalisation of this framework in the methodology for the case-level activities is presented in chapter 3.

2.2 Framing the more4nature case situation

The more4nature conceptual framework has to guide Action Research in a variety of different contexts, at different levels, and linked to three separate thematic areas. The Institutional Analysis and Development (IAD) Framework is a widely recognized and used tool suitable to organize such an analysis. It was developed specifically to “...analyze and design policy interventions in a broad variety of political-economic situations” (Polski and Ostrom, 1999, p. 2), especially for problems related to natural resources such as those in focus in the more4nature thematic areas (e.g., water, air, biodiversity, forests) (Ostrom, 2008).

Figure 7 The original Institutional Analysis & Development Framework (source: Polski and Ostrom, 1999)

The IAD serves to facilitate the analysis of processes that create or change institutional arrangements based on individual and collective choices, including a review of actors, norms, institutional settings, incentive structures, rules, and more. It is a tested tool, as social scientists have widely adopted the

IAD framework to study institutional arrangements and the emerge and changes of institutions over time (Ostrom *et al.*, 2002; Cole, Epstein and McGinnis, 2014; Araral and Amri, 2016) and to inform and guide collaborative governance of common pool resources (Brisbois, Morris and de Loë, 2019). Furthermore, an IAD-based concept can be easily tailored to the needs of a specific situation, through adjustment of its main elements.

The first version of the framework involved three main steps: identifying the contextual aspects of management by local communities (the attributes of the physical environment, of the community and the rules-in-use); identifying the actors and their interactions; and evaluating the outcomes of those interactions (Ballet, Koffi and Komena, 2010). This original concept is in line with the requirement of the more4nature project to guide analysis of each case’ context, to frame case activities in terms of actors and their interaction patterns, and to evaluate results not just in environmental terms, but also in terms of collaboration or conflict between actors. With regard to the latter, Rahman, Hickey, and Sarker (2012, p. 33) clarify that outcomes in an IAD framework “can be cooperative (e.g. trust, reciprocity, altruistic behaviour, etc.) and non-cooperative (e.g. free-riding, common property resource degradation, asymmetric power, etc.)”. However, for the analysis of the more4nature cases’ contexts and framing of their case situation in terms of an action arena, the factors analysed as part of the framework need to be carefully adapted to match the specific dynamics of ECA as the policy intervention under investigation.

Figure 8 Adaptation of IAD framework elements for the analysis of more4nature cases (source: the authors)

The IAD framework adaptation for the more4nature project is represented in Figure 8. It consists of four elements.

1. The **core actor groups** are stakeholders directly involved in the institutional arrangement captured by the conceptual frame. In more4nature, these are the institutional stakeholders and civil society stakeholders directly interacting in collaborative ECA. The core actors and the difference between core actors and other groups of project stakeholders are discussed further in section 2.3.
2. The **case situation** is the ‘action arena’ of the original IAD, in which the two core actor groups interact. The case situation is characterised (1) by the ‘action resources’ that give actors their

agency, (2) by the patterns of interaction among the actors, and (3) by the rules-in-use governing their actions and interactions. These elements form the core of the more4nature conceptual framework and are discussed below in dedicated sections on governance arrangements and rules-in-use (section 2.5), Action resources (ECA practice and CS for ECA, section 2.6), and interaction patterns (Behavioural dynamics in ECA, section 2.6.4).

3. The interactions and institutional arrangements of the actors in the action arena lead to different **outcomes or changes**. For the purpose of more4nature cases, changes in three areas are considered relevant as outcomes for a transition towards collaborative ECA. First, the form and level of collaboration and trust among core actors should change, including use of CS tools to facilitate communication or collaboration between groups. Second, changes towards collaborative ECA are meant to affect the level of compliance in the case area, which, thirdly, is meant to impact the environmental state of the resource in focus of a case over time (e.g. air quality in the zero-pollution theme, pollinators in the biodiversity protection theme, or forest health in the deforestation prevention theme). In most cases, the last is likely to happen beyond the timeline of the more4nature project.
4. The **case context** refers to exogenous variables that shape the interaction patterns or action resources of actors in the action arena, such as, the biophysical conditions of the resources, or the attributes of the community (section 2.4).

2.3 more4nature core actor groups

The primary objective of more4nature is to explore the transformative potential of increased citizen involvement in ECA, through CGD on the one hand, and CCLA on the other. This scope means that two specific types of actors are involved in the institutional arrangement under investigation, namely institutional actors and civil society actors.

Institutional core actors are **authorities with a formal role in ECA**. As the foundations of ECA are fundamentally legal in nature (see more4nature deliverable D1.1 and section 2.5), institutional actors form a required group of core stakeholders necessary to make the vision of collaborate ECA a reality.

Institutional core actors include

- **Environmental regulators and other authorities** involved in implementing environmental regulation, in terms of developing strategies and local rules, in terms of monitoring and reporting, and in terms of granting permits and enforcing their conditions;
- **Enforcement agencies** involved in response to non-compliance, including police officers, rangers, or customs agencies; and
- **Actors of the legal system** involved in corrective actions, including prosecutors and judges.

Environmental agencies and authorities are particularly relevant for more4nature cases **at the national level**, and stand out as they are typically both ECA actors and duty holders (e.g. duty to implement international regulation or reporting duties). **Enforcement agencies** are particularly relevant as collaboration ‘targets’ for more4nature cases **at the local level**, e.g. as they are the mandated responders for citizen alerts. The legal system can be relevant for cases at both levels, as civil society actors can exert pressure to advance implementation of regulation at the institutional level (Kameri-Mbote and Odote, 2009; Cann and Yates, 2020), or take legal actions against offenders in support of enforcement.

Civil society core actors of more4nature are

- **CS initiatives** focused on biodiversity, deforestation, or pollution reduction/prevention, that produce Citizen Generated Data (CGD) and have an interest in expanding their activities into compliance assurance;
- **Citizen and community-led initiatives** interested in taking actions to strengthen compliance assurance for biodiversity protection, pollution or deforestation reduction/prevention, for example through outreach and engagement of relevant actors, public education, direct supportive actions such as volunteer habitat clean-ups, or legal cases.

Figure 9 more4nature core actors and their action resources (source: the authors)

Civil society actors and institutional actors are ‘primary’ actors in a conceptual sense, which means they are **actors for whom relationships and interactions patterns are studied and hypothesized at a conceptual level**. That does not mean they are the only people involved in more4nature as a project. The case studies will engage wider range of stakeholders, including policy makers and legislators, legal and scientific experts, and other civil society and private sector stakeholders. Tools for the stakeholder analysis of cases will be further elaborated in section 3.5.

It should be noted that the more4nature case situation involves another group of actors that defines and shapes the action arena, but which are not (necessarily) part of the institutional arrangement captured by the concept, or of the more4nature case Learning Journey guided by the concept. The term ‘compliance’ denotes that a named and defined group of entities (individual or legal persons) is subject to regulation and thus turned into ‘**duty-holders**’ obliged to comply. Duty-holders respond to regulation either with compliance or non-compliance, for a range of different reasons (see section 2.6.2). *All ECA-related actions, both of institutional and civil society actors in each case situation, are ultimately targeted towards duty-holders.* In specific stages of the more4nature case Learning Journey, case stakeholders may have to assess duty-holders in their area, for example to determine local drivers of compliance or non-compliance during the development of a shared vision (see section 2.6.4). Private sector duty holders might also be important stakeholders to engage. However, for the purpose of this research, duty-holders are, first and foremost, considered the subject or target of ECA. Their actions are not an integral part of the institutional arrangement conceptualized in this framework, or in other words, *they are not, per se, collaborating actors in collaborative ECA.*

2.4 more4nature case context

In IAD, the term ‘context’ denotes influential factors external to the action situation, i.e. factors which are not under the control of the actors. As such, the context is the operating space for planning and decision-making in environmental management. In IAD, context factors are selected and tailored depending on the type of resource challenge analysed with the framework. For the purpose of more4nature, the adjusted IAD framework will focus on four context factors: The socio-technical context, attributes of the resource, historic patterns, and governance arrangements. These are briefly elaborated below.

2.4.1 Attributes of the community: Socio-technical context

A context analysis serves to identify the boundaries of interrelated systems in which an emerging institutional arrangement is embedded. Such boundaries are created by different and overlapping rule systems that shape the playing field of the action situation. Typically, the context of a case or initiative is analysed using tools such as PESTEL, to provide a structured, high-level overview over social, economic, political, legal, technological and environmental aspects relevant to the situation (Issa, Chang and Issa, 2010; Yüksel, 2012). In more4nature, this includes the rules and culture related to resource use (of the resource in focus of the case), the socio-economic conditions in the case study area (local or national scale, depending on the more4nature case type), as well as general political arrangements and rules for participation. A further key purpose of a context analysis is to identify influential institutions and stakeholders that play a role in the action situation, either under formal mandates, because of specific interests, or just because of geographical coincidence.

The socio-technical characteristics of the community in the case study area are of special interest, as they are enablers of CS and CCLA in collaborative ECA.

The **sociological** context captures a wide variety of factors and unwritten rules that structure society. It is often difficult to judge which aspects might have an impact on a specific field of action, and the thematic focus of a case can lead to a narrow or one-dimensional perception. Sound sociological background information should include descriptive statistics of the population and demographics at case level (local or national), a summary of the (local) culture related to resource use (i.e. of the resource in focus of the case, e.g. forests), as well as factors that divide society into distinct subgroups, such as stratification by social status, ethnicity, language or religion. Furthermore, the more4nature efforts to trigger transformative change towards collaborative ECA have to fit within wider value systems of society. Therefore, it is important to understand how society perceives authority and law enforcement in general, and how it would come to judge collaborative ECA and related notions, such as (new) forms of public participation in collaborative governance and efforts towards sustainability, as worthy of support. The context analysis will be focused on the general social context, the value systems of the two core actor groups will be discussed as part of the context factor historic patterns (section 2.4.2)

The **technical** attributes of the community within which a more4nature case is placed concern general information regarding ICT infrastructures, Internet access and (smart)phone penetration. A crucial aspect is the current use of technology by authorities and enforcement agencies, affecting the readiness and physical capacity to engage with technology-enabled or technology-driven initiatives.

More4nature will require detailed analysis of legal texts to clarify who controls the processes, priorities and limitations of ECA and natural resource regulation; legal requirements on the data or indicators in terms of spatial resolution and frequency of sampling; and the legal foundation for participation in policy-making processes. In the more4nature conceptual framework, the socio-technical context analysis will be focused on identifying the full set of rules and policies relevant to the case. However, information that requires content analysis of the identified authoritative texts themselves will be discussed as part of the Governance Arrangements (section 2.5)

Figure 10 Role of the socio-technical context analysis in the more4nature conceptual frame (source: the authors)

2.4.2 Historic patterns

While regular context analysis usually points to general social dynamics in the context, including social norms and cultural value systems, it will not normally involve a detailed analysis of belief systems of individual actors. However, as the more4nature core actors embark on a Learning Journey to explore new forms of collaborative action and governance, the space for their current and future interactions is shaped by historic trajectories. Or in other words, the Learning Journey does not start on a blank page. Belief systems are constantly evolving, but they can also form stable patterns that might present as structural or boundary conditions in the cases. At the individual level, these are taken-for-granted notions of the world, which have been turned into “truth” in personal perception (Robbins, 2019). This might include beliefs about other actors (e.g. ‘the police cannot be trusted’), but also narratives about environmental compliance (‘everybody does it’), or about the case-specific natural resource (Bickerstaff and Walker, 2003). At an institutional level, large organizations themselves exhibit behavioural patterns (Simon, 1997), which influence perceptions and behaviours of their members. So-called path dependencies can influence the cases by shaping perceptions or dominant narratives about civil society involvement, influencing openness to learning and change, limiting action options perceived as acceptable, or ‘locking in’ action patterns (Pfeiffer and Leentvaar, 2013).

The analysis of historic patterns in the context analysis will be limited to the two core actor groups (see section 2.3), and initially without a formal historic assessment. Only a review of past attempts at interactions between the actors should be conducted, as well as a scan for critical junctions experienced by the actors. This can provide critical insights necessary to establish successful collaboration. Where relevant, additional analysis might be conducted as part of the Learning Journey, in particular to uncover the origin of attitudes, social pressures or control beliefs affecting interaction patterns (see section 2.6.4). Tools of discourse analysis can be useful to discover narratives used by actors to justify themselves or to position themselves in relation to other actors (Warner, Wester and Bolding, 2008; Clement, 2010; Fischer and Marshall, 2010; Nisar, 2014; Whaley and Weatherhead, 2014). For example, choice of terms used in ECA policy documents can reveal assumptions about duty-holders (see section 2.6.4). In difficult case situations, stakeholders may engage in what Foucault refers to as ‘archaeology’, or the effort of excavating the hidden history of beliefs and “truths” that require reflection and challenge (Foucault, 1970; Jenson, 2008).

Figure 11 Role of the historical pattern analysis in the more4nature conceptual frame (source: the authors)

2.4.3 Attributes of the natural resource

Attributes of the natural resource for which the institution arrangement is being created is another contextual factor to consider. In the case of more4nature, this concerns the natural resource(s) in each case in the thematic areas (e.g. water and air (zero pollution theme); pollinators (biodiversity theme), and forests (deforestation theme). Traditionally, excludability (possibility to control access to the resource) and subtractability (impact of consumption of the natural resource on the consumption potential of other actors) are core aspects of a common-pool resource (Ostrom *et al.*, 2002), the analysis of which is still relevant for the cases. However, designing collaborative ECA within an existing resource management system addresses challenges that differ from those during the design of a resource management regime itself. Accordingly, in the more4nature context, clarification of basic natural resource attributes serves primarily to tailor guidance to the level, resource and ECA pillar targeted by the more4nature cases. For the ECA context, additional characteristics might be considered in different stages of the process. On the one hand, this relates to characteristics that invite or discourage non-compliant behaviour or environmental crime. For example, the CRAVED framework proposes that environmental products become more attractive the more Concealable, Removable, Available, Valuable, Enjoyable and Disposable they are (Petrossian and Clarke, 2014; Moreto and Lemieux, 2015). On the other hand, characteristics of resources influence which methods of monitoring or evidence gathering are appropriate in ECA. For example, cutting a tree produces a physical specimen that can be traced and forensically matched to a location, while air or water pollution is often diffuse (with the exception of big ‘point pollution’ sources such as industrial complexes). This is further discussed in section 2.6.4.

The attributes of the resource shape the action resources available to the core actors of the more4nature cases. For example, in zero pollution cases, regulation of industrial and public duty holders is more extensive than that of agricultural or private ones, and regulations are equipped with more formal instruments for monitoring and enforcement. This reflects that individual companies typically have higher environmental impact, but also that ECA targeting companies has a more favourable cost-benefit balance. The nature of the resource also affects if response to non-compliance is administrative or criminal in nature, which in turns affects the requirements for data that is required or permissible in procedures, with direct implications for the design of ECA-linked CS initiatives.

Policy area	Type	Measurability
Air and noise	<p><i>Air</i>: specific limits for air pollution concentration values and for overall national emission ceilings</p> <p><i>Noise</i>: WHO guidelines may be used as 'policy targets'</p>	<p><i>Air</i>: High – concrete, quantitative target values are specified</p> <p><i>Noise</i>: High – but new WHO guidelines provide target values not yet included in many monitoring activities</p>
Nature and biodiversity	Target to halt the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services, and to ensure that species and habitats recover sufficiently to enable them to flourish over the long term	Low – as the assessment of whether this target has been achieved or not is limited by the fact that there is no clear baseline against which to estimate how the status of flora and fauna might have developed in the absence of EU action
Water	Different target types within different pieces of EU water legislation – e.g. targets for ecological status, bathing water quality, nitrate concentration, and requirements to waste water discharges	High – each target type is measurable in quantitative terms
Waste	Different target types within different pieces of EU waste legislation – e.g. targets for collection, reuse, recovery, recycling, and landfill	High – each target type is measurable in quantitative terms
Chemicals	No specific targets – but requirements to controlling in connection with using and placing chemicals on the market	Low – no quantitative target values
Industrial emissions and major accident hazards	Specific source emission targets – where most are set to contribute to the above air pollution targets, apart from the targets for heavy metals and organic substances	High – concrete, quantitative target values are specified
Horizontal instruments	No targets but requirements to take actions to avoid environmental damage	Low - no specific targets

Figure 12 Comparison of policy targets shaping ECA needs and options in different environmental areas (source: COWI/Eunomia cited in European Commission, 2019)

The nature of the resource also shapes the potential of a case for collaborative ECA. It affects how well formal ECA measures can be targeted, the public or political support for institutional actors, if the regulation of the resource helps to cover the cost of ECA (e.g. through permits), as well as the success potential of enforcement actions (see Figure 12). The more ECA resources of authorities differ from what is realistically needed to achieve intended compliance levels, the more openness might exist for consideration of civil society support.

2.4.4 Governance arrangements

An essential part of the traditional IAD framework is the concept of rules-in-use. The original representation of the framework considered these as part of the exogenous factors. In newer versions of the framework, rules-in-use are part of the action arena. Formal rules such as positive laws and authoritative texts imposed by authorities remain external factors, referred to as governance arrangements in newer adaptations of the IAD (Ratner *et al.*, 2013; Cohen *et al.*, 2019). In contrast, rules-in-use are now understood as the larger set of rules determining human behaviour inside the action arena, which includes the interpretation and (selective) application of formal rules combined with informal rules (Boelens, Zwarteveen and Roth, 2020). The field and practice of ECA derives from existence and interpretation of legal and policy instruments, creating a central role for the analysis of governance arrangements and rules-in-use in the conceptual framework. However, the delineation of the two aspects for the purpose of guiding is not easy.

In the European and international context, the transfer of authority to supranational bodies implies that some national laws and policies are in themselves interpretations. In the EU, the term 'acquis' (eur-lex.europa.eu) is used to describe the totality of all treaties, agreements, regulations, rulings, institutions, and mechanisms established by all members states that EU members are obliged to adopt, reflecting the complexity added. The range of more4nature cases (Figure 13) implies that formal governance arrangements will differ from context to context, even if the multiple cases focus

on compliance with the same European directive. It also highlights that the line between external governance arrangements and action arena-internal rules-in-use is more fluent than in the cases for which the IAD was originally designed.

Figure 13 Context of more4nature Pioneer Cases by governance level (source: the authors)

At the same time, the analysis of rules-in-use in IAD is typically used to consider informal rules and behavioural elements as well, but in the more4nature conceptual frame behavioural dynamics are studied as an integral part of interactions between the actor groups.

For the purpose of the more4nature conceptual framework, governance arrangements and rules-in-use are, therefore, merged into one conceptual element, spanning the context and action arena, with fluid boundaries depending on the case. The element concerns all formal aspects of national and supranational environmental policy and its implementation in countries and subnational governance levels, specifically all aspects that create ECA action resources. The practical delineation between governance arrangements and rules-in-use depends on the legal situation in implementation countries and will differ from case to case. To identify the boundaries, the conceptual frame applies the following conceptual framing (further detail in section 2.5):

1. **Governance arrangements** create the action resource mandates, understood as all rights, roles, responsibilities and powers enumerated in authoritative texts and assigned to specific actors in ways that are subject to interpretation and enforcement by courts.
2. **Rules-in-use** are all formal and operational rules created to implement mandates and creating tangible resources for ECA, including strategies and implementation guidelines, procedures, budgets and materials including monitoring systems or technical tools, operational and technical manuals, and others.

The conceptual element ‘Governance arrangements & Rules-in-use’ will not consider unwritten or informal norms and rules, which are fully conceptualized as part of behavioural dynamics (section 2.6.4).

As the analysis of governance arrangements and rules-in-use will rely on the analysis of legal texts, it should be noted that there is no standardized approach for conducting text analysis with legal texts as data set. Where necessary, the more4nature methodology will draw on Doctrinal Legal Research (DLR) as the proposed method to interpret authoritative texts scientifically (Hutchinson and Duncan, 2012; Langbroek *et al.*, 2017; Kharel, 2018; Cabeza Velandia, 2021).

Figure 14 Governance Arrangements and Rules-in-Use as cross-cutting element with fluid boundaries in the more4nature conceptual framework (source: the authors)

2.5 Governance arrangements & Rules-in use: The Global system of environmental policy

2.5.1 The legal origin of compliance assurance

Compliance is defined as ‘doing what you are expected or required to do’ (Collins Dictionary), but also as ‘submitting’ or ‘yielding power’ to an authority. These definitions intrinsically link compliance to fields of collective action, in which groups form a collective intents and create institutional facts, or “desire-independent reasons for action” (Searle, 2010). This general definition makes compliance and aspect of all environmental regimes, which are institutionalized systems of rules that need to be followed by constituents, whether the regime in question is the informal community-based management of Hardin’s proverbial shared pasture (Ostrom *et al.*, 2002), or a global treaty regulating a toxic substance (Young, 1989; Young, King and Schroeder, 2008).

However, while compliance is a necessary element of all environmental regimes, compliance assurance, which includes the enforcement of rules, differs in nature depending on the rule-setting institution or authority involved. The difference originates from fact that enforcement of rules might involve forms of physical ‘violence’, such as coercing access to private premises for an inspection, restricting access to locations by physical means, or arresting or restraining offenders. For about a century, the question who can legitimately use violence has played a defining role in the sociological understanding of the term ‘state’. Max Weber is credited for formulating the ‘monopoly of violence’ as defining characteristic of a state (Munro, 2013), noting in a 1918 lecture that a state is “human community that (successfully) claims the monopoly of the legitimate use of physical force within a given territory” (Weber, 1946).

Despite the broad and philosophical nature of these definitions, the concept of ‘legitimate’ use of force claimed by a ‘community’ creates specific and tangible implications for more4nature as a project focused on the role of non-state actors in compliance assurance. The terms reveal that state actors are not meant to exercise the monopoly of violence randomly or arbitrarily, but based on rules that reflect collectively intent. For the analysis of governance arrangements and rules-in-use, therefore, four specific implications are

- a) the need to investigate constitutional or ‘rule-setting’ rules establishing state authority;
- b) the difference between state and non-state actions in compliance assurance;
- c) the diversity of sources of mandates, powers and limitations for state actors; and
- d) the influence of interpretation in multiple level implementation

Figure 15 summarizes the systemic links between rule systems, core actors and legitimate ECA measures that will be discussed in more detail in the following sections.

Figure 15 Summary of differences between state and non-state actors in compliance assurance (source: the authors)

2.5.2 Constitutional or ‘rule-setting’ rules in international environmental regulation

The concept of constitutional rules is established in the original IAD analytical framework itself, with Polski & Ostrom (1999) noting that rules for environmental management are frequently nested in other sets of rules. Higher-level rules, or constitutional rules, determine how lower-level rule systems function, and are the basis for the formation of organizations. With more4nature cases operating at different levels, and involving supranational and international policy goals, the interface between governance levels in the creation of legitimacy for state action are of crucial relevance. While international rule systems such as conventions for specific policy areas might be relatively easy to identify, there is no uniform formula to identify if and how they create legitimacy for state action at lower levels (for more detailed discussion of the following aspects, see more4nature deliverable D1.1). This has to be investigated specifically for each case. To establish the influence of international environmental rules in a case area, cases have to

- a) identify which rule systems exist for the environmental thematic area, for compliance assurance, and for the involvement of civil society in either
- b) clarify the “rule-setting rules” or process for transforming supranational and international agreements into a source of state authority and basis for ‘legitimate state action’ in the case country
- c) investigate which of the existing international rule systems have adopted for the case country according to the rule-setting rules.

In most cases, international environmental rule systems are negotiated through diplomatic mechanism, with agreement of negotiators followed by deliberation in legislative bodies of individual countries and adoption into national law. However, there are three ways in which international rules can become sources of authority directly, namely if

1. Negotiation of an international treaty is conducted by a state representative pre-authorized to commit the country to a course of action.
2. International conventions are adopted by a threshold number of states and thus become international law.
3. State actors continually use non-binding international agreements in decision-making, and thus establishing it as customary international law¹.

¹ A prominent example was the governance of transboundary water courses, with the so-called Helsinki principles applied since 1967, and accepted as customary law decades before the agreement of the first binding convention.

The European Union can be interpreted as a special frame for pre-authorized negotiations. In this case, the relevant rule-setting rules are contained in the Treaty about the Function of the European Union (TFEU) (Borchardt, 2023). It does not regulate a specific environmental issue, but transfers rule-setting authority to supra-national bodies. However, it does not grant general powers to any EU institution, i.e. the authority to take all action necessary to achieve certain objectives. Rather, the extent of the transfer of power and the distribution of responsibility between the EU and member states is determined specifically and in detail for different policy areas. According to Article 4 TFEU, environmental policy is an area of ‘**shared competence**’ between the EU and the Member States, which means that the EU is authorized to act where collective action adds value over individual actions taken by Member States, and within specific limits associated with defined policy instruments. Figure 16 provides an overview over the general system of EU instruments and to what degree they are binding for member states.

Figure 16 Sources and Instruments of EU law (source: Borchardt, 2023)

In the analysis of constitutional rules, it is important to consider ‘rule-setting powers’ in a sufficiently broad sense. Rules that are highly relevant for a more4nature case or thematic area might not be environmental in nature, or it might gain influence in indirect ways. This can be illustrated with three examples; more details will be discussed in more4nature deliverable D1.4:

Example 1 - Issue linkage: Global environmental policy goals such as the SDG or the global Aichi biodiversity targets are not legally binding conventions. However, EU bodies expressly link policy instruments of binding regulation such as the Habitats directive to the implementation of global policy objectives contained in both (European Environmental Agency, 2020). In other words, the ECA

mechanisms created for one binding set of supranational rules are effectively creating ECA resources for another, non-binding set of rules through issue linkage.

Example 2 – diversity of constitutional foundations for ECA: Section 2.6.2 will outline a number of mechanisms through which the EU contributes resources to ECA efforts. This support is not provided as part of European environmental policy (Art 4 TFEU), but reflects a general EU competency for carrying out ‘supporting actions’. EU bodies have no authority to harmonize national laws accordingly to Article 2 TFEU, but may complement or coordinate implementation actions taken by individual member states under article 6 TFEU. In this example, the constitutional rule enabling ECA-supporting actions (Art. 6) is different from the constitutional rule authorizing environmental policy-making at EU level (Art. 4), and both are restricted by a third (Art. 2.).

Example 3 – constitutional rules for civilian participation across policy areas: Involvement of citizens in collaborative ECA is not an isolated phenomenon, but forms part of a larger conversation about the role of civil society in public life and policy-making in general, and in environmental rule-making in particular. Individuals and communities, especially in poor and marginalized areas or countries, frequently carry the heaviest burdens imposed by environmental degradation, which attaches specific ethical and justice elements to environmental regimes. This recognition is reflected in Principle 10 of the 1992 Rio Declaration, a formative document for global environmental policy. At the global level, more4nature objectives align with dedicated efforts derived from Rio Principle 10, such as the Environmental Democracy projects run by the UN Institute for Training and Research (UNITAR)². But in the EU, a key source of influence is a broader agenda regarding civilian involvement in policy-making, which forms a foundational element of the “better regulation” agenda established by the Juncker Commission in 2015 (European Commission, 2015), with resulting channels currently in use in EU practice summarized Figure 17. For practical more4nature purposes, such channels will be monitored for case-specific opportunities by task T1.1, T4.5, and T3.5. On a conceptual level, it is relevant to appreciate that the rules and discourses affecting civilian participation in general might form a ‘higher-level’ rule set in which environmental policy is nested, influential for its functioning, but little visible in its specific written rules.

Figure 17 EU conceptualization of civilian involvement in policy-making (source: European Commission, Better Regulation website³)

² <https://www.unitar.org/sustainable-development-goals/planet/our-portfolio/environmental-democracy-projects>
³ https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-making-process/planning-and-proposing-law/better-regulation_en

2.5.3 National legislation, mandates and implementation of environmental regulation

National legislation is the primary source for the identification of governance arrangements in the more4nature cases. Again, applicable rules will typically have multiple sources. To establish the applicable rules in a case, national legislation have to be reviewed for

- International rule systems that have been transposed into national law
- Native national regulation for environmental issues and participation
- National administrative law establishing division of powers and responsibilities between national, regional and local levels of government
- The primary rules and principles of law enforcement and coercive state action (legitimate uses of ‘violence’)

Figure 18 Transposition of EU directives into national law and responsibilities for different actors (source: Falkner et al., 2005)

The analysis of formal mandates in governance arrangements is based on text analysis of the laws identified, establishing from authoritative texts

- Which actors are mentioned in the law and how they are named or defined
- Which roles, rights and/or responsibilities are enumerated for named actors; and
- Which forms of enforcement actions are available to them (active or passive).

Roles are considered descriptions of expected behaviour assigned to a person or associated with a position within an organization, typically (but not exclusively) cited with words as may, can, could, or should. Rights are as claims or entitlements given by the law, and often expressed in terms such as shall have a right of, shall be entitled to, or is entitled to. A responsibility is a duty ascribed to someone or an obligation that is demanded from someone, and it can be identified in the texts with phrases such as its functions are, hereby is required to, must, shall be its duty to, (shall) be responsible for, among others. Responsibilities are easily confused with roles, but they are not the same. While a role is an expected behaviour, it is not a mandatory action (or omission) that an actor must always always. In mentioning a role, an actor is given the possibility to act within that scope, but could decide to do otherwise for multiple reasons, and still act legally (Cabeza Velandia, 2021). Figure 19 provides an example for the results of an analysis of formal mandates in a national environmental policy area (wildlife conservation). As noted above, the selection of authoritative texts is crucial for a successful analysis. In the cited example, relevant formal and enforceable rights and mandates were included not just in environmental legislation, but in legislation including the national gender equality policy, the anti-corruption act, and the witchcraft act.

Figure 19 Example of a mandate analysis. Enumeration of rights, roles, responsibilities or powers found for 35 selected actors mentioned in 14 authoritative texts regulating wildlife conservation in Zambia (source: Cabeza Velandia, 2021)

The final step of the governance analysis concerns how formal mandates are translated into operational rules and rules-in-use. The plurality of actors involved in policy implementation, each level with a certain amount of discretion in decision making, implies that substantive ‘drift’ in focus and meaning may occur, to the degree that the chain of implementation decisions may lead to a lower-level rules that are no longer compliant with higher level rules (Smith, 2018). Figure 20 illustrates the spaces in which such ‘drift’ might occur.

Figure 20 Institutional discretion and scope for "drift" in the implementation of environmental regulation (source: Smith, 2018)

In this sense, the legal analysis already emphasizes that implementation of rule systems by administration is ultimately a problem of social psychology. As noted by Simon (1997) in 1946: “In very small organizations the influence of all supervisory employees upon the operative employees may be direct, but in units of any size there are interposed between top supervisors and the operative employee several levels of intermediate supervisors who are themselves subject to influence from above, and who transmit, elaborate and modify these influences before they reach the operative”.

2.5.4 State actors and non-state actions in compliance assurance

A crucial element of institutional analysis in the context of ECA is to recognize the difference between state and non-state actors, grounded in the principle of the state monopoly of violence outlined above. In very simplified terms

- Citizens (or non-state actors) have rights they are entitled to, facing restrictions that reflect the rights of others, and the submission of authority to the state.
- State actors have the authority to interfere with the rights of non-state actors, but they do not have any natural rights themselves. All powers have to be enumerated in detail, and are subject to restrictions in how powers are exercised, reflecting rights of citizens. Typically, every rule imposed by the state has to be justified (Grechenig and Kolmar, 2011)

The difference between state and non-state actors, or institutional and civil society actors in more4nature has direct and practical implications for the Cases, specifically:

- Citizens can take action on observed environmentally damaging behaviour and environmental infringements based on interest and concern (Berti Suman *et al.*, 2023) as long as they stay within the legal boundaries for private conduct. Even without consideration of specific environmental regulation, enforcement of individual rights can be used a tool by citizens. An examples for such private action was the successful use of national constitutions and the right to life to prosecute environmental pollution in some African countries (Ojwang, 2007; Kameri-Mbote and Odote, 2009)
- However, while citizens enjoy relative freedom to act on environmental concerns, the state monopoly on violence means that there is no such thing as civil ‘enforcement’ if it involves any form of physical force or coercion (see Figure 15). Citizens are not empowered to impose obligation on each other, unless all sides are voluntary participants. This is an important aspect also in the ethical review of Case activities, as there are fine lines between ‘social pressure’ and coercion, or between civil activism and vigilantism. Overstepping civilian rights can make citizen actors themselves subject to enforcement action for infringing a different set of rules (Grechenig and Kolmar, 2011), or creates issues of public ethics with civilians action in quasi-state roles (Bellamy, 2010).
- State institutions have natural rights, including no right to exist. All action has to be authorized by legislation. If there is no mandate, there is no foundation to act, and an institutional actor doing so would commit an act of abuse of power.
- State actors have to observe strict limits and due process rules for all actions involving coercive measures, as these reflect rights of individual citizens. The relevance of this precedence of individual rights is illustrated by the current drive in the United States to eliminate federal environmental regulation based on arguments of government overreach affecting individual or commercial freedoms.

Combining the applicable constitutional rules with the insights about rule implementation, the difference between state and non-state actors, and the difference between coercive and non-coercive actions provides the basis for analysing governance arrangements (mandates) and rules-in-use (implementation & resources) in the more4nature cases in detail. This will be elaborated in more detail in more4nature deliverable D1.4.

2.6 Action Resources: CS and ECA tools and best practices

2.6.1 Action Resources in more4nature

The extended version of the IAD framework by Ratner *et al.* (Ratner *et al.*, 2013) and Clement (2010) brings attention to action resources. These refer to tangible and intangible assets that create capacity and space for agency. In the more4nature context, the powers enumerated in legal mandates, operational guidelines and procedures, budgets, and the tools of the three pillars of ECA all represent action resources. Similarly, CS tools, CGD, as well as media that can generate public pressure and

available options for civilian legal actions are action resources of civil society actors. Ultimately, the more4nature primary objective of “empowering citizens in ECA”, in IAD terms, means increasing the action resources of civil society actors.

2.6.2 Tools for environmental compliance assurance

Legally, ECA is defined as “the range of interventions used by public authorities to ensure compliance by duty-holders with environmental rules that apply to economic and other activities that directly affect the environment through emissions, discharges, or land- and water-related impacts.” (European Commission, 2017). This definition highlights that the ratification of legal rules is not sufficient to ensure that members of the governed population will fulfil obligations concerning their activities imposed by the rules. Empirically, this observation may sound trivial and obvious, especially considering the overwhelming evidence both for rapid environmental degradation, and for gaps in the implementation of environmental regulation (European Commission, 2022). But it is essential to understand ECA as an integral part of the regulatory cycle, meaning ECA does not exist independent of a rule system that requires observation of duties by duty-holders (see Figure 21).

Figure 21 The regulatory cycle (source: OECD, 2004; based on materials of the Finnish Environmental Institute (2004))

All ECA is based on the belief that response of regulated duty-holders to obligations can be influenced (see Figure 22). These factors are discussed in academic research, which will be discussed further below, but ECA is a fundamentally -practice driven field, with toolboxes developed over time. In recent years, efforts to improve practices have been boosted. Driven by the results of the European State of the Environment monitoring programme (see e.g. (EEA, 2023) and Environmental Implementation Reviews (EIR), it has been widely acknowledged that current ECA practice is not sufficient to halt and reverse the trends in environmental degradation. In communicating the results of the EIR 2022, which is entitled “Turning the tide through Environmental Compliance”, The European Commission states that “the significant number of environment-related court cases, infringements, petitions and complaints, handled at both national and EU level, reflects the insufficient level of implementation of the environmental acquis” (European Commission, 2022, p. 22). Efforts to collect and expand good practices led by the European Commission and the OECD, in many cases through communities of

practice of ECA practitioners, in particular the European Union Network for Implementation and Enforcement of Environmental Law (IMPEL), the EnviCrimeNet network of enforcement agents such as police officers specialised in combating environmental crime, the European Network of Prosecutors for the Environment, and the EU Forum of Judges for the Environment, as well as the International Network for Environmental Compliance and Enforcement (INECE). Both these networks and the knowledge resources and support mechanisms they create as a result represent action resources for institutional ECA actors.

Figure 22 Types of responses of duty-holders to regulation and ECA interventions affecting it (source: European Commission, 2017)

Fundamentally, ECA interventions are categorized into the 3 pillars compliance promotion, compliance monitoring and compliance enforcement (see Figure 23):

Compliance promotion encompasses all interventions that aim to prevent non-compliance and environmental offenses before they occur, in particular aiming to change the behaviour of confused, careless, and under-resourced duty-holders. Authorities promote compliance by helping businesses and individuals meet their obligations, for example by

- raising awareness for the regulated issue and its importance
- by providing information and advice on how to comply
- through helpdesks and ‘frequently asked questions’ materials
- by ‘crime-proofing’ legislation with policy designs that deters infringements

Compliance monitoring encompasses all interventions that aim to diagnose the level of compliance by duty-holders, in particular aiming to change the behaviour of opportunistic and contemptuous duty-holders. Compliance monitoring includes all measures undertaken to verify compliance or discover and characterise infringements. Apart from the diagnostic function, compliance monitoring also generates evidence for enforcement. Compliance monitoring includes

- Surveillance (direct, remote and through reporting)
- Inspections and spot-checks
- Complaints mechanisms
- Investigation

Compliance Enforcement refers to all actions by competent authorities that respond to and correct non-compliance detected, primarily aiming to change contemptuous and criminal behaviour, but also to remediate damage caused through non-compliance no matter whether it was caused by carelessness, ignorance or criminal intent. Enforcement actions include administrative, civil and criminal law interventions, such as

- official warnings
- cease-and-desist orders
- administrative or criminal proceedings,
- application of sanctions (penalties, withdrawal of permits)
- demands or orders to take remedial action

Figure 23 Environmental Compliance Assurance concept (source: European Commission, 2017)

With regard to civil society contributions to formal ECA, compliance monitoring channels to discover infringements typically include tip-lines and other channels for complaints from the public. In other words, the knowledge and observations of citizens are, exclusively, an action resource of institutional ECA actors. Empowering citizens and civil society actors means to alter this embedding, envisioning civil society actors as potential ECA practitioners with their own mandates and action resources. In this scenario, autonomous and expanded civil society actions have to be coordinated with the three pillars of formal ECA. Understanding not just the current practice, but the nature of the three ECA pillars as preventative, diagnostic and corrective, and clarifying that each ECA pillar has behavioural targets is an important aspect for the design of effective collaborative ECA mechanisms, in particular to place CGD streams of CS initiatives that go beyond familiar practice. This will be further discussed in section 2.6.4.

In terms of the action arenas for ECA, few dedicated mechanisms exist for supra and international ECA (See more4nature deliverable D1.1). The key exception is the European Union. As member states have transferred rule-setting authority to the supranational body 'compliance' with European environmental regulation has two levels, involving the duties of member states to 'transpose' binding regulation in line obligations under the TFEU, and subsequently the promotion, monitoring and enforcement of the implemented rules at the national level as outlines above. While this two-level structure applies, in principle, to all international environmental regimes, a significant difference in practice results from the fact the European Commission is fully empowered to take both supporting and enforcement action as response to infringements by member states, both equipped with powerful action resources and generating action resources for lower level (both national and subnational) ECA

actors. An overview over ECA actions at the European level are accessible via a dedicated “Implementing EU law” website maintained by the European Commission⁴.

For environmental regulation, supra-national measures under the three ECA pillars include:

1. **Compliance promotion** through facilitation of knowledge production in task forces, communities of practice or platforms such as the environmental governance and compliance forum⁵, resulting in the production of studies (some of which have informed the development of this deliverable), reports and technical guidelines (see Figure 24) such as the Environmental Compliance Assurance ‘Vade Mecum’ (European Commission, 2020b).

Figure 24 EC reporting on compliance promotion activities (source: “Implementing EU Law” website)

2. **Compliance Monitoring** includes two aspects. For one, mandatory European reporting on the environment provides ECA-relevant data for institutional actors at the member state level, especially data collected by the European Environmental Agency⁶ for European “State of the Environment” reports (see e.g. European Environmental Agency, 2020, 2023). Separately, the EU monitors national level compliance directly, with the biannual Environmental Implementation Review (European Commission, 2016; Saint-Genis, 2017), with infringements visualized in a publicly accessible Environmental compliance dashboard (see Figure 25). In line with ECA practice outlines above, compliance monitoring includes a mechanism for complaints by individual citizens to report on state-level infringements.

⁴ https://commission.europa.eu/law/application-eu-law/implementing-eu-law_en

⁵ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/law-and-governance/environmental-compliance-assurance/commission-support_en#environmental-compliance-and-governance-forum

⁶ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/>

Figure 25 European Environmental Compliance Dashboard (source: EEA⁷)

3. **Compliance Enforcement** at the European level involves actions taken by the European Commission against member states as duty-holders. Formal infringement procedures include a range of measures ranging from letters demanding information or action to formal prosecution in courts (European Parliament, 2018). Infringement procedures can be tracked on the Commission website. Notably, a large share of infringement procedures relates to environmental regulation (Viitanen, 2019; Fazi and Góra, 2021)

Figure 26 EC infringement procedures tracking (source: "Implementing EU law" website)

⁷ https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/explore-interactive-maps#co=5&c5=&b_start=0

2.6.3 Citizen Science and citizen & community-led actions for ECA

Action resources in IAD terms refer to tangible and intangible assets that create or strengthen capacity and space for agency of the core actors. The action resources of institutional actors in ECA, discussed in the previous section, are legal mandates, operational guidelines and procedures, budgets, and the tools of the three pillars of ECA. The citizen science tools, the data generated by CS initiatives (citizen generated data – CGD) as well as citizen & community-led actions (CCLA) are action resources that are available (although not exclusively) to civil society actors but which may require strengthening.

Citizen science (CS) refers to the involvement of civilian actors in various forms of collaborative data and knowledge generation (Fritz *et al.*, 2019; Haklay *et al.*, 2021), ranging from science-driven projects (with different degrees of participation, (Shirk *et al.*, 2012), initiatives to democratize science and policy via science citizenship (Irwin, 1995), community-based environmental monitoring schemes (Whitelaw *et al.*, 2003) and civic monitoring (Haklay and Francis, 2017), as well as citizen observatories (Hager *et al.*, 2021). CS is a multi-stakeholder as well as a multi-dimensional phenomenon (Hager *et al.*, 2021; Wehn, 2022) but there is no single agreed definition; distinct preferences and epistemic communities re. CS appear to prevail among natural scientists (top-down CS) and social scientists (bottom up CS) (Hacking, Lewis and Evans, 2024) with data collection considered a core activity of any form of CS (Haklay *et al.*, 2021). CS initiatives span from those primarily focused on CGD and knowledge co-creation, to those directed towards (local) action, e.g. interventions in socio-ecological systems and supporting stewardship via conservation projects (e.g. Wiggins and Crowston, 2011; Schäfer and Kieslinger, 2016). Both CS results - CGD as well as actions related to environmental stewardship and protection – are highly relevant for ECA. In view of the plurality of approaches to and views of CS, it has been argued that CS is best defined in context according to five distinct areas of characteristics (Haklay *et al.*, 2020, 2021): core concepts, disciplinary aspects, leadership and participation, financial aspects, and data and knowledge.

The multi-stakeholder processes that CS entails have the potential to contribute to public engagement, transparency, equity, inclusiveness and justice in science and policy (Irwin, 1995; Cooper *et al.*, 2021; Wehn, Ajates, *et al.*, 2021); and may empower citizens in sustainable natural resource management - cognitively, politically, socially and economically (Danielsen *et al.* 2021), contributing to conflict resolution and strengthening self-determination (Johnson *et al.*, 2021). Frameworks for assessing the impacts of citizen science have rapidly evolved (Phillips, Bonney and Shirk, 2012; Kieslinger *et al.*, 2017; Reed *et al.*, 2018), and newer approaches specifically discuss impacts on existing environmental governance and decision making systems (Leach and Fairhead, 2002; e.g. Nascimento *et al.*, 2018; Berti Suman, Schade and Abe, 2020; Wehn, Ajates, *et al.*, 2021).

Depending on the purpose of a CS initiative, CGD and knowledge co-creation interacts with different ‘institutionalized knowledge systems’ (Leach and Fairhead, 2002) such as academic research, policy making and implementation, or combinations of both (see Figure 27). Conceptualizing the potential role of CS in ECA focuses the analysis on interactions with policy processes and governance outcomes (right-hand side in Figure 27). In general, such CS initiatives include private advocacy or watchdog platforms created without the explicit collaboration of policy makers, but also CS initiatives that involve formalized participatory mechanisms offered by authorities or collaborative action between citizens and authorities.

Figure 27 Key forms of citizen science defined by collaborating actors, purpose and sphere of engagement (source: the authors)

This also includes citizen observatories (COs), first initiated in Europe more than a decade ago, as particular forms of CS that provide the means for new forms of interactions between policy-makers, the general public and the scientific community. COs involve ICT-facilitated bi- and multidirectional data and information flows, typically linked to participatory processes in environmental monitoring and governance (Hager *et al.*, 2021) (centre of Figure 27). This is in line with the more general notion of collaborative governance as being “... characterized by the pooling of knowledge and resources amongst a broadly inclusive set of actors with an interest in the problem at hand (e.g., citizen groups, policy makers, natural resource or other industries, Indigenous groups) (Ansell and Gash, 2008). While COs ‘by nature’ may be inherently closer to ECA than other forms of CS, it is important to note that, in the context of more4nature, the project’s efforts to trigger transformative change towards collaborative ECA and empowering citizens in ECA is not limited to COs. Rather, the >160 existing CS initiatives to be engaged in the 40 more4nature case studies will be supported, along with the institutional actors, in the process of fostering collaborative ECA.

While the CGD generated by different CS initiatives may not be explicitly or inherently linked to ECA, the value of CGD for the implementation of policy has already been demonstrated in the past. A decade ago, Danielson *et al.* (2014) found that for measuring progress towards achieving global environmental indicators of 12 major international environmental agreements, CGD could serve for 63% of the indicators. Fritz *et al.* (2019) explored the 5 dimensions of CGD (spatial, temporal, thematic, process, and data management) and their features, to illustrate the value of CGD for monitoring and reporting on progress with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (see Figure 28). According to Fraisl *et al.* (2020), CGD has the potential to contribute to all 17 SDGs, to at least one indicator per goal; moreover, CGD is already contributing or could contribute to 40% of the environmental indicators (68% of which lack data) and, overall, CGD could contribute to 76 SDG indicators (33%).

Figure 28 The five dimensions of citizen-science data, their features and their value for the SDGs (source: Fritz et al., 2019)

An exploration of CGD data shared on the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (<https://www.gbif.org/>) during the two decades from 2000-2020 by Mandeville et al. (2023) shows that a large and growing majority of biodiversity data in protected areas now stems from CGD (see Figure 29), on different continents as well as for different species. This is exceeding both, previous estimates of CGD contributions and exceeding other data sources, including official data (Maitland et al., 2023). Such global biodiversity evidence is key for monitoring progress towards the target to protect 30% of the earth’s habitats by 2030, agreed in the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework.

Figure 29 Changes in the contribution of participatory monitoring from 2000-2020 (GBIF) (source: Mandeville et al., 2023)

a) The amount of data contributed to GBIF annually from participatory monitoring (yellow) and non-participatory monitoring approaches (blue) for global protected areas; b) the annual percentage of data derived from participatory monitoring across global regions; c) the annual percentage of data derived from participatory monitoring across broad taxonomic groups.

Despite this growing potential, institutional actors may be lagging behind in their knowledge and perceptions of citizen science. The European Commission is driving efforts to make the potential of CS more visible (European Commission, 2020a), yet these efforts start from a low level. In 2019, a draft assessment of environmental governance in Europe included encouragement of citizen science in its proposed indicators for public participation, but in its feasibility test could not find information about related activities (Nesbit et al., 2019), illustrative result in Figure 30.

Figure 30 Illustrative presentation of public participation assessment for conducted for the development of an EU assessment framework for environmental governance. Indicative results for CS activities in proposed indicator 3.4.2 Q6. (source: Nesbit et al., 2019)

Aside from CGD, another dimension of CS that is highly relevant for more4nature is that, as discussed above, depending on the purpose of a CS initiative, they entail actions and interventions to protect the environment. CS initiatives of this type are often bottom-up, grassroots initiatives and/or with close links to civil society organisations or environmental NGOs. Moreover, many CS initiatives are not static; their purpose and range of activities can evolve over time, whereby increased knowledge, understanding and awareness of environmental challenges by civilian actors results in an urgency to act and to protect the (local) environment (Wehn, Gharesifard, *et al.*, 2021; Somerwill and Wehn, 2022). For example, the CS initiative [Plastic Spotter](#) in Leiden, The Netherlands, was defined by citizens to study litter floating in the city canals which then triggered plastic litter clean up actions in Leiden (and other cities). Such activities intersect and partially overlap with the longstanding theory and practice of community-led development (Chambers, 1997) and community-based initiatives in environmental conservation and protection (Berkes, 2004), outside the CS field. Indeed, Ostrom’s work on collective action, culminating in the IAD, centres on the notion of how communities organise themselves to manage common pool resources sustainably (Polski and Ostrom, 1999; Ostrom *et al.*, 2002).

more4nature aims to explore the potential of leveraging not only CGD but also existing and new distinct actions and interventions for improving the implementation of environmental rules on the ground, related to the three pillars of ECA (see section 2.6.1). Since such actions in principle may be taken not only by communities but also by individual citizens (e.g. initiating litigation actions against a duty holder or an authority in charge of ECA), in more4nature, these are framed as **citizen & community-led actions (CCLA)**. These actions may entail CS initiatives joining forces with existing organisations, networks and initiatives, incl. FabLabs and LivingLabs, to implement, or even co-design such actions from scratch. As such, focusing on the concepts of CGD and CCLA serves to

capture in tangible ways the full breadth of data, local insights and knowledge, and (co-designed) actions for environmental protection that a holistic understanding of CS entails.

Academic explorations of CS and ECA include in a special issue on *Where Citizen Science meets the Law* (2023) by the journal *Citizen Science Theory and Practice* and a book on civic monitoring for environmental enforcement (Berti Suman, 2024). Wyeth (2023) provides examples of how US environmental agencies already work with citizen scientists in monitoring schemes as initial integration in ECA, highlighting the agencies’ roles, use of CGD and stakeholder engagement issues. However, a comprehensive exploration of the linkages between CS and the distinct ECA pillars is still missing.

In order to base the more4nature conceptualisation of CGD and CCLA contributions to ECA on practice-based knowledge, a task force of the more4nature consortium partners consolidated this during a small number of dedicated workshops in early 2024. This resulted in a visual concept of the contributions of CGD and CCLA to ECA (see Figure 31), focusing on a data path (CGD-based) as well an action path (via CCLA) from CS initiatives to the three ECA pillars.

Figure 31 Potential contributions of CGD as well as citizen & community-led actions in collaborative ECA, according to the more4nature task force

A structured summary of the insights captured by the task force is presented in

Table 1, indicating the actual and potential contributions of CGD and CCLA to the three ECA pillars (compliance promotion, compliance monitoring and compliance enforcement). It is noteworthy that for both, CGD and CCLA, abstaining from activities may be a necessary course of action, so that civilian actors are not subjected to personal danger. Also, it is important to safeguard the potential positive effects stemming from the availability of CGD, e.g. for species monitoring, against potential abuse or inadvertent use (e.g. directing poachers and illegal loggers to sites).

Table 1 Overview of (potential) contributions of CGD and CCLA to ECA

ECA pillars	(Potential) CGD contribution	(Potential) CCLA contribution with Fab/ LivingLabs and env. NGOs
Compliance promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use CGD to engage with media to generate attention about the topic/policy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Volunteer contributions (e.g. fencing) ▪ Take solution-driven practical action (e.g. clean up actions) ▪ Reward compliance of duty holders (e.g. prizes, hitlists of role models) ▪ Engage duty holders (e.g. industry, utilities, landowners, trade companies, individuals) to encourage compliance to targets ▪ Engage with media to generate attention about the topic/policy (celebrate/shame) ▪ Radical activist action to promote compliance by duty holders
Compliance monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Identify data gaps in official monitoring data/networks ▪ CGD collecting ▪ Citizen engagement to generate more (and better quality) data ▪ Contribute data for indicator calculation by responsible authority (combined CGD & official data) ▪ Early detection of infringement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Create additional detractors (e.g. citizen 'environmental neighbourhood watch' as "capable guardians")
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Drive for change to admit CGD for reporting ▪ Drive for change in targets and/or monitoring framework (new indicators, inclusion of CGD) 	
Compliance enforcement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fast track CGD to authorities during early detection of non-compliance ▪ Inform authorities via CGD for inspection, surveillance or investigation of alert ▪ Crime pattern analysis: NODES (generators, detractors, attractors) ▪ Pattern development and analysis, CGD evidence trail 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Highlight low probability of action or conviction, advertise acts that can be committed with impunity ▪ Engage authorities to enforce set targets ▪ Take legal action (or request authorities to do so) ▪ Radical activist action inhibits non-compliance by duty holders

The identified contributions of CGD and CCLA to ECA relate to the regulatory cycle for ECA as presented in Figure 32. Civilian actors engaging with authorities and policy makers to create or change policy/regulations at supra or national level is conceived as a cross-cutting contribution connected to all three ECA pillars, stemming from public participation in ECA via CGD and/or CCLA, and directly linked to both, evaluation and development of laws and implementation regulations. A concrete example of such requests for policy change is the call by (Berti Suman *et al.*, 2023) to go beyond the right to *obtain* environmental information (currently granted by the Aarhus Convention) by installing “*a right to contribute environmental information*” (p.3-4) which includes the obligation for responsible authorities to consider such data and information.

Many of the conceptualised contributions of CGD and CCLA to ECA elaborated in summary Figure 32 rely on facilitating factors, such as knowledge of relevant protocols (for data collection) or of procedures (for fast tracking CGD to relevant authorities for enforcement). Other barriers to the uptake of CGD (Fritz *et al.*, 2019) and CCLA in environmental compliance assurance include lack of capacity and common methodologies, lack of trust in the data, uncertainty of how CGD could or will be used, or data discovery and integration issues (e.g. Wehn and Almomani, 2019; Rubio-Iglesias *et al.*, 2020; Eicken *et al.*, 2021; Tengó *et al.*, 2021; Wyeth, 2023).

Figure 32 Conceptualised contributions of CGD and CCLA to the regulatory cycle of ECA (adapted from OECD 2004)

The strengthening these action resources of civil society actors (in close collaboration with institutional actors) is at the heart of the more4nature case activities. This requires taking stock of the status quo at the start of the case activities of key aspects such as the (online) visibility and accessibility of the existing CS initiative(s); the variables observed and data collected; protocols for data collection; standards, quality control, filtering and established vocabularies required and/or complied with; CGD licencing; API endpoint access to the CGD; the usefulness of the data for creating indicators for monitoring the situation; the capacity to detect anomalies and generate notifications; and the extent of current use of CGD in ECA (e.g. for alerting, monitoring or reporting). Overall, some aspects will be known by the more4nature case contacts *ex ante*, while others, especially many of the technical details, will have to be ascertained during the work with the case stakeholders. Strengthening these action resources also relies on a deeper understanding of the behavioural dynamics between these core actors (see section 2.7) and how to drive transformative change in their actions and interactions related to ECA (see section 2.8).

2.6.4 Compliance Theories: Academic research as Action Resource

As noted in section 2.6.2, ECA is based on the rationale that the level of compliance can be influenced. All ECA-related actions, both of the institutional and the civil society actors, are ultimately targeted towards duty-holders based on assumptions about their motives and reasons for acting. In other words, the underlying belief is that non-compliers can be transformed into compliers by interventions (see Figure 33). Most assumptions how interventions affect duty-holders are based in compliance theories, though actors may or may not be aware about the source of their beliefs, or attempt to base their ECA tools on scientific evidence. One example for conscious grounding of ECA practice is the “Table of 11” which underpins the ‘enforcement pyramid’ of Dutch authorities.

Figure 33 Foundational assumption of ECA: non-compliant duty-holders can be turned compliant adapted from (source: Nokes and Holloway, 2012)

For use in the more4nature, compliance theory and approaches are relevant for three purposes

- Understanding the intentions and operational logic of institutional actors and the local ECA tools and strategies;
- Investigate baseline compliance levels (which factors are currently targeted, where are potential gaps, weaknesses, etc); and
- To make design of CGD and CCLA focused, theory-guided and evidence-based, especially to reveal assumptions of civil society actors.

As academic research can be used to design or improve the effectiveness of action resources, it can be seen as an action resource for ECA actors itself.

Compliance theories originated in the research of criminal behaviour and as a theoretical underpinning for law enforcement in general (e.g. Becker, 1968). Compliance with environmental regulation includes a broad range of obligations, and failure to submit a report can be the extent of non-compliant behaviour. In the following sections, damaging and outright criminal offenses receive relatively more attention, reflecting the subject of leading environmental compliance research. However, the relatively lower attention to administrative compliance does not mean that ECA actions should pay less attention to actors who are non-compliant with procedures such as reporting because it is costly, a hassle, or do not see the reason, even if they operate within legal margins.

A vast body of knowledge from multiple disciplines proposes models and explanations for non-compliant and criminal behaviour, including psychology, economics, criminology, and legal research (Ramcilovic-Suominen and Epstein, 2012; Fine *et al.*, 2014; Arias, 2015; Oyanedel, Gelcich and Milner-Gulland, 2020). As one fundamental distinction, approaches and frameworks differentiate

between unconsciously or unintentionally non-compliant actors who are unaware of rules applicable to them, and conscious non-compliers (LEEC, 2004; Nokes and Holloway, 2012). The remainder of this section will focus on theories proposing factors affecting conscious non-compliance; actors unaware of rules will be discussed further in section 2.6.2 in relation to the tools of compliance promotion.

Fundamentally, non-compliance can be explained as the interaction of a motivated actor with a situation presenting an opportunity. Accordingly, compliance theories focus on identifying factors that influence the individual motivations of an actor when deciding to comply or not, as well as on factors that influence the actor’s perception of the context as opportunity for compliance or non-compliance in the moment of decision. Both perspectives have significant limitations, especially at the intersection of social and ecological systems, suggesting that compliance should be conceptualized with consideration of both motivational and contextual compliance factors (Figure 34) (Oyanedel, Gelcich and Milner-Gulland, 2020). For example, illegal harvesting of natural resources such as wood, fish, or wildlife products requires the presence of trees, water bodies or suitable habitats in the context. This means that a one-sided analysis focused on actor motivations alone is unlikely to satisfactorily explain non-compliance with logging, fishing or hunting regulations. At the same time, not every actor in a target-rich context commits environmental crimes. So, an analysis too narrowly focused on contextual opportunities will equally fail to sufficiently explain compliance levels.

Figure 34 Key compliance approaches and proposed factors affecting compliance levels own elaboration based on Oyanedel, Gelcich and Milner-Gulland (2020)

Actor-based approaches explain non-compliance with the underlying motivations of actors.

- Most influential are instrumental models drawing on economic utility calculation, such as the deterrence model or the compliance framework. With origins in the 1960s (Becker, 1968), they are both well established, and popular with enforcement agencies as they assign quantifiable value to deterrence actions (Sutinen and Andersen, 1985; LEEC, 2004). A contemporary example for use of the compliance framework is the OECD (OECD, 2009; Mazur, 2011).
- With regard to non-economic compliance factors, actor-based approaches widely suggest that the perceived legitimacy and acceptance of rules, authorities, and procedures affect motivations to comply (Sutinen and Kuperan, 1999; Raakjær Nielsen, 2003; Levi, Sacks and Tyler, 2009; Ramcilovic-Suominen and Epstein, 2012, 2015; Jong, 2013), as do shared norms (Fine *et al.*, 2014; Deffains and Fluet, 2019; Oyanedel, Gelcich and Milner-Gulland, 2020).
- The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) is not a dedicated compliance theory, but has been used to understand and predict non-compliance in the context of natural resource management (Shrestha *et al.*, 2012; Fairbrass *et al.*, 2016; Bergseth and Roscher, 2018).

Opportunity-based approaches assume that non-compliance is not distributed randomly across space and time and focus on the role that the immediate environment plays in the performance of non-compliant behaviours (Critchlow *et al.*, 2015; Petrossian, Marteache and Viollaz, 2015; Kurland and Pires, 2017; Kurland *et al.*, 2017). Evidence from different studies suggests that, in fact, non-compliant use of, and trade in, natural resources occurs at specific places, facilities, times and products. Prominent examples of opportunity-based models include the rational choice model, the routine activity model, and the crime pattern model.

- The rational choice approach to explaining compliance has certain overlaps with the instrumental model. However, instead of calculating cost in terms of probability of detection and sanction, it considers properties of the environmental crime itself that makes the offense more or less costly to perform, such as the level of skill or equipment required. The rational choice model is built on the evidence that societies, in general, are very inefficient at delivering economic sanctions, concluding that low probability of sanction makes them less relevant in cost-benefit calculations than the costs of offenses themselves (Cornish and Clarke, 1987; Celik and Sayan, 2008; Hands, 2014; Paternoster, 2019; Mateo-Tomás *et al.*, 2022).
- The routine activity model proposes that non-compliance occurs when (a) motivated actors, (b) suitable targets, and (c) the absence of capable guardians converge in time and space. This model takes user motivations towards non-compliance as a given and implies that offense rates are affected by changes to crime ‘targets’ or presence of ‘guardians’. Relevant to more4nature, it studies how spatial-temporal factors in the organization of daily life help to convert criminal inclination into action, and considers as ‘guardians’ not just authorities, but also civilian actors (Cohen and Felson, 1979; Lindley and Techera, 2018).
- The crime pattern model also identifies factors that generate, attract, or deter offenses (Kinney *et al.*, 2008). In contrast to the Routine activity model, the approach focuses less on patterns of human action, and more on environmental patterns. Specifically, they found that many most land-use types act as crime detractors, while specific geographical areas generate or attract offenders (Clarke, 1980; Brantingham and Brantingham, 1993)

The knowledge and insights generated by compliance theories reveal three specific opportunities for evidence-based collaborative ECA.

First, environmental offenses are inherently spatial in nature (e.g. there is no illegal logging in areas without trees), but spatial analysis of compliance data requires extensive data sets. Using crime pattern analysis and the routine activity model, CGD streams might be valuable to conduct pattern analysis, identify attractors, detractor or generator nodes. The theories also provides opportunities to clarify the role of CCLA in coherent conceptual ways, for example modelling activities as ‘guardian nodes’.

Second, compliance research suggests that influencing the motivations of duty-holders is a traditional weak spot of authorities. Actor-based theories highlight the difficulty of crafting interventions that change underlying normative beliefs (Cornish and Clarke, 1987; Oyanedel, Gelcich and Milner-Gulland, 2020). In contrast, civil society often have their strongest impact through awareness raising and social pressure, suggesting complementary potential.

Finally, compliance research offers useful methodological contributions for the more4nature Case Learning Journeys. As example, crime script analysis (Petrossian and Pezzella, 2018) bears similarities to established co-design tools like ‘user journeys’ applicable in the process. In terms of content, such tools serve to identify actions of duty-holders that form part of a pathway towards offending and which might prevent offenses if disrupted, but which are not targeted by institutional ECA actors because they are too numerous or not in themselves offenses.

2.7 Behavioural dynamics in ECA

In the original IAD framework, actor interactions were framed as social bargaining process in which actors exchanged resources, developed rules, or demanded action from other stakeholders (Polski and Ostrom, 1999; Ratner *et al.*, 2013). For the purpose of more4nature, that is too narrow. At the heart of the more4nature interventions lie the stakeholder interactions in the ECA action arena that are at play in each case. In order to understand these stakeholder interactions and the opportunities and barriers for changes in these dynamics, a key element of the more4nature conceptual framework draws on the research in the field of behavioural dynamics and policy. Behavioural approaches have already helped to understand the motivations of key stakeholders to participate in citizen science and citizen observatories (Gharesifard and Wehn, 2016; Wehn and Almomani, 2019). (Wehn and Almomani, 2019) used the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) to integrate the dispersed insights from >40 empirical studies into a consolidated model of incentives and barriers for participation in citizen science and citizen observatories.

Figure 35 Conceptual model (per CO stakeholders), based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (based on: Ajzen, 1991; elaboration Wehn, 2009; Ganzevoort *et al.*, 2017; Wehn and Almomani, 2019)

This provides a structural model of the generic belief clusters related to attitudes, social pressures and agency for participation. Applied to a specific case, it can generate detailed insights into the respective incentive systems of core CS stakeholders (e.g. Wehn, Imperiale and Crystal, 2024) and reveal their attitudes, norms, values, agency, and goals. Nevertheless, while the insights into the incentive systems of stakeholder types are useful and necessary, they are not sufficient for understanding the extent to which and how their respective incentive systems align or clash and what the fundamental reasons are for the dynamics of their interactions. The behavioural dynamics approach by Montalvo *et al.* (2021) (see Figure 36) has addressed these shortcomings by i) including emotion and relational models that are mediating interactions with other actors (in the case of more4nature: civil society or institutional actors) and ii) dividing the model into three moments for a dynamic decision-making process.

Figure 36 Citizens in relational behaviour (source: Montalvo, Schlindwein and Kantel, 2021)

This approach provides the means to grasp the interactions of the key ECA actors in ways that are observable, measurable, and falsifiable, and to generate key insights for the interventions at the more4nature case levels. The resulting model of behavioural dynamics in collaborative ECA (Figure 37) will guide the project work to help tackle the step from citizen science and citizen & community-led actions to actually contributing to ECA.

Figure 37 Preferences and behaviour mediated by interactions (GRETA project) (source: Montalvo et al. (2021), based on Montalvo (2007; 2021)

Specifically, this will enable more4nature to distinguish and model:

- a) the **influence** of attitudes, norms, values, agency, goals, and emotions on the behaviours of the core more4nature actor groups (civil society actors; institutional actors), e.g. data uptake of authorities, enhancements of CS initiatives, and citizen & community-led actions related to ECA;
- b) the **sources of influence** for the individual core actors' decisions and behaviours from the collective and vice versa; and
- c) the **structure and dynamics of the relation** between individual ECA actors and the collective that result in CGD uptake by authorities for compliance monitoring, reporting and enforcement, as well as CCLA in ECA.

This element of the more4nature conceptual framework will guide the project's work on how, in practice, public authorities and regulatory bodies could interact with CS initiatives. In doing so, the work will derive end-use considerations (behavioural and technical) to consider citizen-generated data for compliance assistance and enforcement, and evolve into a set of behavioural best practices and technical tools. This element will be further elaborated by T1.4 in WP1, forming the basis for the needs assessment tool as well as the inventory provided, generating case-specific as well as cross-case insights.

2.8 Transformative change in ECA via social learning

2.8.1 Transformative change

As noted in section 2.6.1, challenges with the current results of environmental regulation and ECA practice have been widely acknowledged. The European Commission (2022), in its communication on the last EIR notes specifically that compliance assurance efforts of environmental authorities and the national courts, the two actors with the primary responsibility for implementing EU law, have not been sufficient to improve compliance levels. As priority action for compliance assurance, the European Commission recommends to “Encourage and monitor public participation in enforcement”, for example through awareness-raising activities on the options for reporting environmental problems, and for filing complaints about environmental issues or infringements.

Especially in environmental monitoring and compliance monitoring, the potential value of citizen involvement is already recognized. As an example, monitoring of existing environmental policies such as the EU Habitats Directive, only around 20% of numerical estimates or trends originate from complete or robust surveys while more than 20% of the information reported by Member States is based on expert judgement, showing that the data and available knowledge is insufficient (Röschel et al., 2020). Reimagining and deepening the role of citizens and communities in ECA via Citizen Science, Citizen Generated Data and Citizen & Community-Led Actions, nevertheless, constitutes a transformative change. It requires visioning and experimenting with new roles and interactions to create possibilities for collaboration previously unimagined (Table 2). As such, it implies “*fundamentally different forms of thinking, actions, systems and structures*” (Waddel, 2016; cited in Fazey et al., 2018, p.56) that go hand in hand with high levels of uncertainty for the civil and institutional actors involved.

Table 2 Types of Change (Fazey et al., 2018), based on (Waddell, 2016, p. 15)

	Incremental	Reform	Transformation
Learning type	Single loop	Double loop	Triple loop
Core questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ How can we do more of the same? ▪ Are we doing things right? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ What are the rules and structures? ▪ What are the rewards? ▪ Who should do what? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ How do I make sense of this? ▪ What is our core purpose? ▪ How do we know what is best
Purpose	To improve performance	To understand and change the system and its parts	To innovate and create previously unimagined possibilities
Power and relationships	Confirms existing rules	Opens rules up to revision	Opens issues to the creation of new ways of thinking and action
Core dynamic	Replication	Reorganization	Transcendence
Archetypal actions	Copying, duplicating, mimicking	Changing policy, adjusting, adapting	Visioning, experimenting, inventing

2.8.2 Social Learning as core element of transformative change

Transformative change towards collaborative ECA therefore requires a comprehensive process that seeks to change existing systems and norms, and ultimately leads to changes in

- i) the *form and level of collaboration and trust* among core actors should change, including use of CS tools to facilitate communication or collaboration between groups;
- ii) the *level of compliance* in the case area,
- iii) which is intended to impact the environmental *state of the resource* in focus of a case over time (e.g. air quality in the zero pollution theme, pollinators in the biodiversity protection theme, or forest health in the deforestation prevention theme).

Among the scholarly deliberations of how transformative change can actually be achieved (Fazey et al., 2018; Wittmayer et al., 2024), social learning is considered a key process for any transformative change in environmental governance regimes (Pahl-Wostl, 2009; Garmestani and Benson, 2013; Westley, 2013; Imperiale and Vanclay, 2021; Järnberg, Vulturius and Ek, 2023) cited in (Wehn, Imperiale and Crystal, 2024). The increasing attention to social learning as a means for transformative change is based on the realisation that complex environmental situations, such as environmental protection, require, among other factors, collective learning and common understanding, and not just only individual learning, as well as knowledge co-creation and accumulation of wide experiences to generate a broader knowledge and evidence base from which decisions can be taken.

For social learning to occur, it must move beyond fostering cognitive and/or behavioural changes at the individual level and become situated at a broader social scale through wider social interactions and participatory processes. In common social contexts, social learning outcomes should therefore not only be observed at the individual level, but also at social-relational levels, in terms of changes (or improvements) of the social interactions among the actors involved in social learning processes.

In general, the social learning process therefore consists of changes at different levels - individual, collective and institutional levels - and entails the following (Reed et al., 2010):

- deliberate efforts triggered by specific social conditions and directed towards achieving specific outcomes
- changes in feelings, attitudes, actions, behaviours and social norms
- changes in understanding within individuals that can then become embedded within larger societal groups

More specifically, (Wehn *et al.*, 2018), after (Collins and Ison, 2009)) have argued that social learning consists of one or more of the following:

- The convergence of goals (expressed as purpose)
- The process of co-creation of knowledge which provides insights into the causes of a situation and the means of its possible transformation
- The changes in behaviours and actions resulting from new understandings
- An emergent property of the process to transform a situation.

Both definitions emphasize that social learning is intentional and aims to boost cooperation and learning among stakeholders. This process is meant to foster a better understanding of challenges and ways to address them, involving shifts in mental models, beliefs, perceptions, and practices among the key stakeholders involved (Figure 38).

Figure 38 Illustration of convergence of goals (source: Montalvo, Schindwein and Kantel, 2021)

In more4nature, social learning as a deliberate effort includes the following key intermediate outputs (based on Wehn, Imperiale and Crystal (2024):

- a common vision of the problem and of the desired outcomes to be achieved
- a social learning agenda:
 - specific aspects and activities to be undertaken to achieve the desired outcomes
 - specific changes at individual, relational, organizational and institutional levels that are needed to allow all involved ECA actors in a more4nature case to implement these activities and achieve the desired outcomes

In practice, path dependencies may imply, to a degree, that institutional actors may have a hard time transcending embedded patterns. Organizational path dependencies, or ‘embedded action patterns’ (Sydow, Schreyoegg and Holtmann, 2011) are a well-established phenomenon, described as ‘robust organizations’ in institutionalism (Keohane, 1989), as ‘de facto structural parameters’ in constructivist theory (Wendt, 1992), as ‘hegemonic discourses’ in research on epistemic communities (Warner, Wester and Bolding, 2008) or ‘routine patterns’ in institutional bargaining (Young, 1989). They occur because ‘a group of actors holding the same management paradigm will most likely reinforce their belief through their interaction’ (Pahl-Wostl *et al.*, 2010). In ECA practice, this is a relevant element of engagement with institutional actors.

Helpful for reflection on the situation of institutional stakeholders is (Sydow, Schreyoegg and Holtmann, 2011), who describe the evolution of an organizational path as emerging in a characteristic

three-phase process that narrows the range of available action options at critical junctions that might feature visibly in the narratives of partners (see Figure 39).

Figure 39 Constitution of an organizational path (source: Sydow, Schreyögg and Koch, 2009, p. 692)

Overcoming path dependencies in social learning may therefore require leveraging mechanisms of influence inside the institutional actors (authority, loyalty, efficiency, information & training).

2.8.3 Facilitating social learning for transformative change

The type of transformative change process envisioned by more4nature is sometimes referred to as social innovation (SI). Social innovations are ideas, activities or services that (a) meet social goals or needs, which (b) improve the quality or quantity of life, and (c) have the nature of a public good (Wehn and Evers, 2015). Collaborative ECA as envisioned by more4nature fulfils all three criteria. Other authors regard SI as a process, entailing the “*the invention, development and implementation of new ideas to solve social problems faced by individuals, groups or communities*” (Oeij et al., 2019, p. 244); or a ‘*self-conscious collective action that seeks to address the unsatisfied need for sustainable development*’ (Mehmood and Parra, 2013, p. 53e66); which may or may not rely on technological innovation. The process perspective is compatible with the more4nature focus on social learning and behavioural dynamics. Soma et al. (2018, p.363) note that SI processes involve “*changing behaviour of a group of actors joined in a network, leading to new and improved ways of collaborative action*” that can take place across a variety of institutions, markets and sectors. Moulaert et al. (2013) emphasise that social learning is a key component of any SI process. They suggest that the production and (open) sharing of knowledge in a non-profit driven manner is essential for impact. Metszösy (2019) outlined the various SI stages during which social learning takes place. Changes in interaction patterns as a characteristic of the process is highlighted by Neumeier (2012), who suggested that the impacts of SI are not always material, but can be reflected in changes in attitudes, behaviours and relationships. This view is shared by Simms (2006), who suggested that social innovation is a key determinant of human behaviour.

The SI body of knowledge is valuable for the purpose of more4nature, as a significant share of the literature specifically investigates social innovation as institutional-level change that can be stimulated and brought about in directed and facilitated multi-stakeholder processes, and provides evidence for aspects that influence the impact potential of outcomes. Authors have highlighted the complexity of this process, starting with its multi-phase nature. For example, Garud et al. (2012) identified three phases within the innovation process: invention, development and implementation, with each phase posing different challenges, with a variety of solutions. The SI process is generally

seen as collective in nature, with input needed from a variety of stakeholders (Sharra and Nyssens, 2010). The terminology of an innovation ‘journey’, rather than ‘process’, highlights the human, collective and non-linear quality (2019), who utilise the innovation (Van de Ven, 2017; Van de Ven, Angle, & Poole, 1989), involving complexities that require ‘deep’ scaling, re-framing cultural and institutional norms, in order to change relationships and behaviours (Moore, Riddell and Vocisano (2015).

A common finding is that all elements of a social innovation – the envisaged outcomes, as well as the social, technological and operational mechanisms - need to be negotiated and institutionalized by a community of relevant actors. The key implication is that the success and impact of a collaborative mechanism is inherently linked to a purpose that transcends the motivations and expectations of individual actors and reaches a collective, societal level. Considering the more4nature cases’ Learning Journeys from this perspective suggests as key elements for success of the process *the formation of a group of actors who are in a position to negotiate the relevant outcomes*, guided exchanges to arrive at a joint understanding of the challenges to be addressed, and mechanisms to institutionalize agreements of the resulting collaboration.

Since 2018, in the EU, concerted efforts are ongoing to improve implementation of environmental regulation and increase the coherence and effectiveness compliance assurance (see section 2.6.2). This was triggered by the State of the Environment Report 2015, which triggered the establishment of the regular Environmental Implementation Review (EIR), combined with the “better regulation” drive starting 2016 (European Commission, 2015, 2016). The results of the EIR 2018 created a focus on enhanced compliance assurance (European Commission, no date), leading to actions such as the collation of best practices by dedicated task forces (see section 2.6.2), as well as formation or increased support for professional networks of environmental regulators, enforcers, prosecutors and judges. This means that institutional actors, at least in more4nature cases in EU member states, are already involved in processes of change and learning, and are not starting on a blank page. Collaborating with civil society actors including CS is part of the recommendations within the formal change process, so organic entry points for more4nature can be established. However, it is important to realise that civil society partners will attempt to embark on a train already in motion, and recent organizational developments in institutional counterparts will have implications for action options available.

2.9 Summary of the more4nature conceptual framework

The more4nature conceptual framework provides a coherent frame for guiding and analysing the diverse empirical experience of the cases and enables the development of generalized understanding and recommendations from their activities. It consists of

- iii. the more4nature concept of collaborative Environmental Compliance Assurance and
- iv. the conceptual framework of transformative change towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance through social learning and socio-technical experimentation.

2.9.1 Collaborative Environmental Compliance Assurance

Legally, ECA is defined as “the range of interventions used by public authorities to ensure compliance by duty-holders with environmental rules that apply to economic and other activities that directly affect the environment through emissions, discharges, or land- and water-related impacts.” (European Commission, 2017); accordingly, environmental ECA aims to encourage, assist and compel duty holders to improve implementation of environmental rules on the ground. *In most formal ECA processes, citizen involvement is an ambition, not an entitlement.* The more4nature concept of collaborative Environmental Compliance Assurance (illustrated in Figure 40) captures the shared understanding of how CS can contribute, in different ways, to the three ECA pillars (compliance promotion, compliance monitoring and compliance enforcement) via

- CGD - data generated by diverse forms of CS initiatives
- CCLA - actions and interventions, taken or initiated by individual citizens, civil society organizations or communities.

Figure 40 more4nature concept of collaborative Environmental Compliance Assurance (source: more4nature consortium)

Both CGD and CCLA provide opportunities for civilian actors to contribute effectively to improving the implementation of environmental rules on the ground, not all of which require participation in formal ECA processes. In collaborative environmental compliance assurance, citizens and communities work in partnership with relevant authorities in promoting, monitoring and acting to protect the environment.

2.9.2 Conceptual framework of transformative change towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance

The more4nature conceptual framework of transformative change towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance through social learning and socio-technical experimentation is illustrated in Figure 41. This is the result of careful combination of concepts and insights from environmental governance and compliance theory and approaches, behavioural science, the science of citizen science, sustainability science and innovation studies.

We use the Institutional Analysis and Development (IAD) as the underlying framework for generalized analysis of the real-life settings of the more4nature cases. This adapted version of the IAD serves to facilitate the analysis of processes that create or change institutional arrangements in ECA (towards collaborative ECA) based on individual and collective choices, including a review of actors, norms, institutional settings, incentive structures, rules, and more. Specifically, the adapted IAD framework for the more4nature project consists of four elements:

1. The **core actor groups** in more4nature are *institutional and civil society stakeholders* directly interacting in collaborative ECA.
2. The **case situation** is the ‘action arena’ in which the two core actor groups (institutional and civil society actors) interact with respect to ECA. This is characterised
 - (1) by the ‘*action resources*’ that give actors their agency.
 - (2) by the *patterns of interaction among the actors*.
 - (3) by the *rules-in-use* governing their actions and interactions.
3. The **case context** - exogenous variables that shape the interaction patterns or action resources of actors in the action arena, namely the socio-technical context, the biophysical conditions of the resources (Z/B/D), the attributes of the community and environmental policy.
4. **Outcomes or changes** resulting from the interactions and institutional arrangements of the actors in the action arena (levels of collaboration & trust, compliance levels, and status of the resource).

Reimagining and deepening the role of citizens and communities in *collaborative* ECA via Citizen Science, Citizen Generated Data and Citizen & Community-Led Actions constitutes a **transformative change**. This requires visioning and experimenting with new roles and interactions to create possibilities for collaboration previously unimagined. Transformative **social learning** as intended by more4nature will not occur by coincidence. Rather, it will be initiated, stimulated and facilitated via **Learning Journeys** to create spaces in which conditions are conducive to social learning, inviting the right configuration of stakeholders into the space, and assist with the co-creation of knowledge socio-technical experimentation.

This comprehensive process seeks to change existing systems and norms, and ultimately will lead to changes in

- iv) the *form and level of collaboration and trust* among core actors should change, including use of CS tools to facilitate communication or collaboration between groups;
- v) the *level of compliance* in the case area,
- vi) which is intended to impact the environmental *state of the resource* in focus of a case over time (e.g. air quality in the zero pollution theme, pollinators in the biodiversity protection theme, or forest health in the deforestation prevention theme). In most cases, the last is likely to happen beyond the timeline of the more4nature project.

Key elements for success of the social learning process are the formation of a group of actors who are in a position to negotiate the relevant outcomes, guided exchanges to arrive at a joint understanding of the challenges to be addressed, and mechanisms to institutionalize agreements of the resulting collaboration. The model of *behavioural dynamics in collaborative ECA* will guide the project work to help analyse **evolving interaction patterns** among these core actors and tackle the step from citizen science and citizen & community-led actions to actually contributing to ECA. In sum, contributions to the IAD from other theoretical and evidence-informed foundations have helped to transform it from a tool for the analysis of self-organised processes, to a tool for the guidance of a facilitated learning and change process. The operationalisation of more4nature conceptual framework in the methodology for the case-level activities is presented in chapter 3.

Transformative Change through Social Learning & Socio-Technical Experimentation

Figure 41 more4nature conceptual framework for transformative change towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance (source: the authors)

3 Methodology more4nature Double Loop Action Research

3.1 Purpose of the more4nature action research methodology

The more4nature pursues its central research question through Action Research with two sets of 20 cases each, creating individual Learning Journeys for 40 participating cases (Figure 42).

Figure 42 more4nature ‘double loop’ action research (source: more4nature DoA)

The more4nature conceptual framework provides a coherent frame for guiding and analysing the diverse empirical experience of the cases and enables the development of generalized understanding and recommendations from their activities. In this section, the conceptual frame is operationalized as a methodological approach for double loop action research. It outlines how the project will guide and mentor cases through two cycles of Action Research suitable to stimulating transformative change towards collaborative ECA, in line with the overall project objectives (section 1.1). The operationalization builds on established approaches validated in a number of earlier projects, adapted with the conceptual elements described in chapter 2.

The following sections will

- introduce the more4nature methodology at project (3.2) and case level (o) and present its main components and;
- outline the principles for guiding the process (3.4) and the stipulations for stakeholder groups to be involved in the cases (3.5);
- present the stages of the more4nature methodology (3.6);
- outline the implementation procedure and tools for each case (o).

3.2 more4nature Action Research at project level

At project level, the more4nature methodology consists of detailed instructions for consistent and overall coherent elements of the action research activities driven at case level first by T3.2 in the Pioneer Cases and then by T3.3 in the Follower Cases. The cases are supported by WP1 with conceptually grounded guidance for empowering citizens and fostering transformative change; and by WP2 with tools and principles enabling integration of CGD in collaborative ECA. The methodology for stimulating, guiding and tracking social learning towards collaborative ECA in all more4nature

case is complemented by an approach for peer learning, co-evaluation and synthesis (T3.6 and T3.7) to ensure that resulting insights can cross-fertilize activities between cases, and feed into the production of generic guidelines and recommendations. (Figure 43).

Figure 43 Overall more4nature Action Research methodology (source: more4nature DoA)

At the project level, the methodology provides procedures to ensure effective progress in the cases, coordinates research activities and interactions between the cases and project tasks and work packages, and ensures that all case activities reflect and adhere to the ethical principles of the more4nature project as stipulated by deliverable D6.1.

3.3 Methodology for the more4nature change process at case level

The two sequential “loops” of Action Research in the Pioneer and Follower cases (Figure 42), aim to

- Explore the applicability and validity of the more4nature socio-technical knowledge, tools and methods in transformative change towards collaborative ECA;
- Foster learning and knowledge co-creation among citizens, communities, regulators and enforcement agencies, as well as among citizen science practitioners on new forms of collaboration for effective environmental compliance assurance;
- Support the co-design of the tools and citizen actions for environmental protection via synergies between CS initiatives and LivingsLabs for green and digital transformations;
- Promote recognition by policy makers and authorities of the value of CGD and CCLA in collaborative ECA.

A guided and interactive Learning Journey for the participating cases forms the core of the more4nature action research activities. The Learning Journey builds directly on the more4nature conceptual frame, which

- Provides the basis for guidance of cases in stimulating interactive processes of knowledge co-production and learning (2.8);
- Supports identification and engagement of relevant stakeholders (2.3) in their real-life context (2.2, 2.4 and 2.5) and with their practice-based knowledge as frame of reference (2.6); and
- Proposes scientific concepts and approaches useful to enhance understanding the cases and foster the emergence of solutions outside and beyond the current state of practice (2.6.4).

The Learning Journey is structured into five phases (see section 3.6), with each stage designed to prepare and facilitate stakeholder decision-making on all relevant aspects of the evolving local solution. The project team provides socio-technical learning impulses in each phase to stimulate social learning towards cooperative ECA, but stakeholders will remain in charge of all decisions and results. Stakeholder ownership of the process is crucial to trigger transformative change, as has been demonstrated in multiple projects implementing socio-technical change processes for environmental governance challenges, such as Ground Truth 2.0 (Wehn and Pfeiffer, 2019), MICS (Wehn, 2021), MAR2PROTECT (Wehn, Somerwill and Bilbao, 2023), and C2B2 (Wehn, Imperiale and Crystal, 2024).

Figure 44 The more4nature Learning Journey adapts tested approaches to the specific challenges of ECA (source: GT20.eu)

While the effectiveness of the action research methodology has been demonstrated and validated in the above-mentioned projects, the more4nature project presents a new methodological challenge with the need to reflect the legal foundations and institutionalized practices of ECA in all stages and interactions. Overall, the more4nature methodology comprises five elements:

6. Overarching **guiding principles**.
7. Stipulations for case **stakeholders** to be engaged
8. **Key stages** with generic list of activities and envisaged outcomes per stage
9. **Compendium** as one-stop-shop for instructions, worksheets and guidelines (online workspace)
10. **Guidance system: dedicated teams** with more4nature partners per thematic area (Z/B/D) and WP1 & WP2 mentors

3.4 Guiding principles for more4nature case implementation

The diversity of the more4nature cases, with differences in topic, scale, culture, and activities requires a methodological guidance with build in flexibility and room for local adaptation. The primary method for achieving this flexibility is principle-based guidance. Principle-based guidance means that the framework does not specify decision-points and choices to be made, but rather elaborates for the case contact (as process manager and facilitator)

- How to review interactions between case stakeholders to determine if action or intervention is needed to preserve the learning environment;
- How to choose stimuli to give and how to give them, based on the fit with the stakeholder dynamics.
- How to review stakeholder outputs from ethical perspectives and identify possible blind spots that stakeholders need to be made aware of.

The difference between principles-based guidance and ethical guidance bears similarities to the difference between being “effective” and being “efficient” when managing a process. Principle-based facilitation serves to keep a process moving and directed towards achieving an outcome. As the proposed principles draw on extensive empirical knowledge, decisions that align with the principles are most likely to avoid problems that can bring the collaborative process to a halt without a result accepted by all participants. This means, principle-based guidance is similar to ‘doing things right’. However, the principles used to make a result possible or accepted do not guarantee that the result is a ‘good’ result from an ethical point of view.

Ethical guidance refers to reviewing both interactions and interim and final outcomes of all stages of a process, and comparing results with a set of normative benchmarks. Which normative benchmarks are applied, is not a matter of empirical effectiveness, but a matter of choice and commitment. More4nature has committed to two specific sets of normative benchmarks. The first is the overall ethical framework applied to its research process and activities, as outlined in deliverable D6.1. The second are the ethical frameworks applied to all the governance and management of data (collection) conducted in connection with the project, specifically the FAIR and CARE principles mainstreamed in activities under guidance by Tasks T1.3 and T2.

The two ethical frameworks mentioned, however, apply only to activities under the control of the project. As the Case Learning Journey stimulates behaviour change by stakeholders, a final challenge for the project derives from the potential of unintended consequences of research outcomes. Based on the nature of the more4nature Case Learning Journeys and collaborative ECA, guidance of the cases will, therefore, follow three sets of principles:

- **Principles for social learning** – how to create spaces that enable social learning and foster innovative thinking
- **Principles for Transformative Research** – how to guide partners to ensure compliance with the project’s research ethics

- **Principles for building ethics into collaborative ECA** – how to ensure case stakeholders consider ethical implications of civil society engagement in monitoring and enforcement of law

While sharing the general characteristics of other social learning and social innovation processes, the compliance focus of the more4nature project creates a number of distinct and specific characteristics. These differences pose specific ethical and practical challenges and have to be considered in the guidance of the case teams. Three characteristics, in particular, affect the methodology at a principle and ethical level: (1) a pre-existing normative frame, (2) pre-determined stakeholders, and (3) the role of non-compliers. The first two affect the learning environment, the third creates ethical implications for the guidance of transformative research and the review of process results.

3.4.1 Enabling social learning

As highlighted in section 2.8, transformative social learning as intended by the more4nature project will not occur by coincidence. It can and should be initiated, stimulated and facilitated, which means the creation of spaces in which conditions are conducive to social learning, inviting the right configuration of stakeholders into the space, and assist with the co-creation of knowledge.

The more4nature cases aim to foster increased collaboration in ECA among civil society and institutional actors through social learning with case-related stakeholder based on experimentation and socio-technical impulses. This underlying logic suggests to **adopt the key principles of LivingLabs**, a mechanism developed to support innovation by offering a ‘neutral arena’ where different stakeholders would be able to meet and co-develop innovative solutions (Ståhlbröst, 2012). The five guiding principles are:

- Create **value** for stakeholders by understanding their needs and motivations
- Enable stakeholders to **influence** decisions they are affected by
- Aim for long-term economic, social and environmental **sustainability**
- Involve multiple perspectives and collaborate widely for **openness**
- Carry out activities in a **real-life context**

Following the joint preparations by the thematic teams of all sessions with their respective case stakeholders, **facilitators will have a particularly important role** in creating the conditions for social learning in these interactions with stakeholders. Factors suggested in the literature for fostering social learning (see Table 3) pay particular attention to the content dimension of social learning (i.e. scoping the problem(s) and identifying desired outcomes), to the context dimension of social learning (i.e. existing organisational conditions, individual attitudes and the governance system), and to the process dimension of social learning (i.e. iterative, recursive and inclusive process).

Table 3 Summary of enabling factors for social learning in the more4nature cases (source: adapted to more4nature from (Wehn, Imperiale and Crystal, 2024) and (Wehn et al., 2018))

Enabling factors for social learning	Description
Content dimension	The case activities should be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Applied to ECA issues in real-life contexts and directed towards environmental protection and sustainability; ▪ System-oriented and grounded in system thinking; ▪ Based on local knowledge, needs and desires; ▪ Informed by relevant disciplinary science and insights from the respective thematic fields (zero pollution, biodiversity protection, deforestation prevention)
Context dimension	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ensure the technical and social competences to carry out case activities; ▪ Ensure tolerance of ambiguity and diversity of opinions; ▪ Enable flexibility and open-mindedness; ▪ Enhance the capacity of all involved actors for critical self-reflection; ▪ Ensure reliability and consistency of all case activities
Process dimension	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Facilitate co-ownership of the case activities and outcomes.

Enabling factors for social learning	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ensure inclusiveness, especially the inclusion of the most vulnerable people and sectors, through a structured/targeted approach ▪ Ensure respectfulness towards each other’s feelings and perspectives <p><i>Convergence of goals:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Realise that the extent to which convergence of goals can be achieved is highly case-dependent and locally defined ▪ Convergence does not mean there is always complete agreement, but a recognition of the systemic relationships between different stakeholders’ goals, which can then lead to more concerted forms of action. ▪ The ability to formulate and agree on a definition of the purpose of current and future ECA indicates convergence of goals at system level <p><i>Co-creation of knowledge:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Realise the re-enforcement between i) trust and willingness to cooperate, on the one hand, and ii) knowledge co-production and mutual learning, on the other ▪ Making boundary choices about the relevance of ECA issues can be difficult ▪ Collaborative process and tasks can be challenging in terms of revealing assumptions about the ECA situation, this requires careful promotion of dialogue and integration of different perspectives. ▪ Aim for a structured dialogue on the purpose of ECA and identification of core themes for ECA challenges ▪ Co-creating and using system diagrams can reveal the complexity of ECA and the realization that no individual or organization can manage this complexity in isolation. ▪ Ensure transparency and accountability in scenario analysis, planning activities, and achieving desired outcomes; <p><i>Changes in behaviour and actions:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Changes in behaviours and actions may take time to develop and become ‘acceptable’ to individuals and organizations, require time and perseverance ▪ Not all changes in understanding and practices can be realized by participants, ▪ Evidence of changes is difficult to collect with short-term interventions. <p><i>Emergent property of the process to transform a situation:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Aim for the incorporation of the co-created knowledge into decision-making; ▪ there are no guarantees of social learning or any other collaborative element (e.g. convergence of goals). ▪ Social learning is neither a magic ingredient nor an assumed outcome. ▪ Enhancing trust and collaboration requires time and effort but even in the short term, the advantages of such collaboration can be noticeable. This multi-scale and multi-sector collaboration can only be achieved with a well-defined social learning process ▪ Demonstrated commitment of all stakeholders leads to trust ▪ Ultimately, the potential for changing the role of citizens (in ECA) is highly dependent on the room that citizens are granted by authorities – but also on that claimed by citizen

3.4.2 Principles for transformative research

Research Ethics are a crucial aspect of more4nature, as the project aims to stimulate transformative change in the real-world environment of citizens and professionals (see more4nature deliverable D6.1). Guidance of cases has to ensure (=promote, monitor and enforce) that activities are compliant with the ethical rules of the project. For this purpose, guidance will be based on the 10 principles for action-oriented research proposed by Fazey et al. (2018), summarized in Figure 45.

Figure 45 Ten essentials for action-oriented research (source: Fazey et al., 2018)

Two characteristics of the more4nature project, furthermore, affect how these principles have to be applied in the Pioneer Cases.

First, a compliance-related initiative starts with a specific rule, law, or regulation giving the discussion a **pre-existing normative frame** and vision regarding an intended environmental outcome. This alters the nature of initial engagements. While the co-design of governance-related initiatives might begin with an open discussion of goals and principles, the more4nature Learning Journeys involve the interpretation of goals and application of rules negotiated by others. With the exception of cases that specifically aim to change European or international environmental policy, social learning processes will focus on actions that aim to achieve **a situation that, by law, should already exist**.

On the one hand, this legal frame creates a significant starting point for a collaborative process. On the other hand, participants have to be aware of and respect implications of this foundation for the role, boundary conditions and behavioural imperatives of other stakeholders. For example, a legal frame is not just binding for a specific sub-set of stakeholders (enforcement agencies, prosecutors, judges), but non-negotiable. High levels of sensitivity are required for a constructive learning process, for example recognizing situations in which private convictions or opinions of enforcers conflict with official positions they are duty-bound to uphold, and not invited to question while acting in official capacity.

Secondly, a compliance-related initiative involves pre-determined sets of institutional stakeholders as required core stakeholders. Initiatives such as citizen observatories aiming to improve natural resource management enjoy a certain degree of freedom with regard to policy-makers or decision-makers that may be targeted or ‘recruited’ as members or collaboration partners. Co-design of governance-related initiatives might change their stakeholder configuration over time based on engagement levels, observed group dynamics and resulting impact potentials. **ECA, by definition, involves specific actors with specific mandates.** The governance level of each case (local, national), and the focus of the CS initiative or community-led action in the case, will determine a number of institutional actors without whose participation ‘collaborative’ ECA is not possible.

This influences the nature of stakeholder engagement. **Specifically, more4nature cases have to engage mandated stakeholders regardless of their level of response.** This includes separate but continuous engagement of authorities who refuse to participate in joint events. The more4nature methodology is designed with this contingency in mind. In line with the concept of stakeholder dialogue and action outlined in section X, activities of each stage can be implemented either jointly, or separately, by civil society and institutional participants. In each stage, advances in social learning will invite and support a decision to move from separate activities within shared objectives to a collaborative modus operandi. However, the more4nature methodology does not require agreement for joint activities to succeed.

3.4.3 Principles for building ethics into collaborative ECA

A final, major challenge in the guidance of the Pioneer cases, is the need to review both interactions and interim and final outcomes of all stages of the Learning Journey, and comparing results with a set of normative benchmarks. As collaborative ECA envisions civilian involvement in activities linked to enforcement, i.e. actions that might involve coercive actions taken by state actors, the ethical implications require diligent consideration (Irvine *et al.*, 2016). For data to lead to action, it needs qualified interpretation, and the presence of big data sets can even hide ignorance of participating actors about legal, technical or cultural nuances of the situation. When the aim of an action is to “influence collective behaviour through the organs of the state or a [...] public authority able to command a non-voluntary obligation of obedience on the part of those affected by its decisions” (Bellamy, 2010, p. vii) then the person acting is no longer just a private individual, but a political actors responsible for public rules and regulations, and has to accept resulting responsibilities.

This is particularly relevant in the relationship between cases and duty-holders of the targeted regulation. The **action arena** of a compliance-focused initiative is not just shaped, but **created by the presence** of a specific range of stakeholders, namely that of **‘non compliers’**. Non-compliance can take many forms, both deliberate and unknowing, and non-compliant actors can originate from institutional, individual, or private sector backgrounds (see sections 2.6.2 and 2.6.4). Crucially, from a principle-based perspective, deliberate non-compliers risk sanctions due to their behaviour and, therefore, have something to lose. This introduces additional risks and ethical concerns to the process, which have to be reflected in the guidance. Non-compliance by institutional actors has to be considered from a public ethics perspective, i.e. the conduct of public officials in the execution of their office, with issues ranging from conflicts of interest to outright corruption.

Non-compliance by individuals and private sector duty holders ranges from negligence and minor infractions, to offenses with significant monetary stakes, to environmental crime committed by individuals or even organized offenders (UNEP/Interpol, 2016; Ciara and Zachary, 2017; CIEL, 2019; European Commission, 2021). Depending on the context, civil society actors taking action on environmental issues may be exposed to prosecution, threats, or even physical violence, necessitating risk assessments and precautionary measures in the design of tools. Citizen alerts might trigger enforcement actions with potentially significant risks and repercussions both for deployed enforcement agents and targeted duty holders. And as citizen & community-led actions are not subject to the rules of due process, the protection of civil rights (including of offender’s rights) has to be carefully considered in the design of citizen & community-led actions. Again, this involves issues of public ethics.

3.5 Case stakeholders

3.5.1 Stakeholder engagement in the Learning Journey

Discussion of the legal foundations of ECA (section 2.5), the nature of the Pioneer Case journey as social learning or social innovation process (section 2.8), and the ethical aspects of collaborative ECA (section 3.4), all imply a central role for the selection and configuration of stakeholders to be engaged. The social innovation literature, in particular, clarifies that in each stage of the innovation process, input from different groups of stakeholders is required. In the initial stages, essential collaboration partners of ‘collaborative’ ECA need to be involved to negotiate and agree a shared agenda. Expert advisors might be necessary to clarify options and limitations. In later stages of the process, other stakeholders are required, for example policy makers or stakeholders capable of reaching wider or specific audiences.

A stakeholder is usually defined as someone having an interest in a particular situation, even if this interest is not recognized or acknowledged by others. Collins, Blackmore, Morris, & Watson (2007) note that this does not sufficiently convey what stakeholders do, as opposed to who they are. They propose to focus on the dynamics of “stake holding”, in which stakeholders actively construct, promote and defend their stake over time, exerting influence both through contributions to and deliberately abstaining from participatory processes. While understanding of the case Learning Journey as social innovation process implies that the configuration of engaged stakeholders needs to change over time, understanding of stakeholding as an act highlights that involved actors share and reshape their stakes as part of the social learning process.

The Learning Journeys in the more4nature cases involve the two core actor categories of institutional and civil society stakeholders (see section 2.3), but may also engage additional groups as necessary to support the shared vision. Overall, four categories of stakeholders are expected to be engaged in all more4nature cases, namely i) civil society, ii) institutional actors and legislators at the governance level relevant to the specific case, iii) experts, and iv) the private sector.

3.5.2 Civil Society stakeholders

The primary objective of more4nature is to explore the transformative potential of increased citizen involvement in ECA through CS on the one hand, and community-led action on the other. Conceptually, any interested citizen or community could be engaged for the purpose. However, reflecting the objectives and action research approach of the more4nature project, cases will not assist in the formation of new initiatives, but initially focus on stakeholders with pre-existing practical knowledge. With regard to civil society actors, this means the engagement of

- **Existing CS initiatives** focused on biodiversity, deforestation, or pollution reduction/prevention, with an interest in expanding their activities into compliance assurance, especially monitoring and/or enforcement.
- **Existing LivingLabs and FabLabs** with whom citizen & community-led actions for biodiversity protection, pollution reduction/prevention (advocacy) or deforestation prevention will be co-designed to strengthen ECA.

In later stages of the Learning Journey cases might identify additional civil society stakeholders in the enabling environment, for example to engage them as relevant partners for the implementation of collaborative ECA strategies developed by the core stakeholders.

3.5.3 Institutional stakeholders

Authorities with a formal role in ECA form an essential group of required core stakeholders necessary to make the vision of more collaborate ECA a reality. Primary actors, with strong recognition in the European setup, are environment agencies, inspectorates, police officers, prosecutors, and judges. As outlined in section 2.5, and as will be discussed in more detail in the stage descriptions below, a key task for the methodology is to support identification and engagement of stakeholders most relevant to the level and nature of each case.

Apart from authorities, a second group of institutional stakeholders are **legislative bodies at all levels**, from local councils to national parliaments. For one, such bodies are charged with the oversight of authorities and enforcement agencies, and have legal rights to question and influence how formal laws are translated into agency-internal policies, strategies, and priorities. Furthermore, legislative stakeholders are responsible for the adoption and implementation of existing European Directives at subsidiary levels, and for initiating reviews and changes to legislation based on evaluation of compliance levels, environmental outcomes and ECA practice. In contrast to enforcement agencies, elected stakeholders in legislative functions are entitled to question existing legislation on normative grounds, which makes them essential agents of change in a systemic transformation towards collaborative ECA.

3.5.4 Experts

International environmental policy and, in particular, European environmental regulation, in its design, implementation, monitoring and enforcement, is a fundamentally expert-driven system. Therefore, designing and evolving civil society involvement in ECA necessarily requires the involvement of experts qualified to guide the cases and help them match formal and scientific requirements and benchmarks. In particular, this includes

- **Researchers, academic and other thematic experts** on issues of biodiversity, pollution and deforestation, both with scientific expertise, and with knowledge how the state of academic research is reflected in current technical regulations of the field (for example design of environmental monitoring systems).
- **Legal experts** with extensive knowledge on international environmental policy and/or European environmental ‘acquis’⁸ and its implementation practice in member states. Legal experts are crucial to guide the review and interpretation of authoritative texts, to assist with the engagement of ECA practitioners in the legal system (prosecutors, judges), and to guide citizen & community-led actions involving legal actions or actions with legal implications.

3.5.5 Private sector

Careful assessment and engagement of private sector stakeholders in the cases reflects the fact that business entities are the primary group of ‘duty-holders’ under European environmental regulation, obliged to fulfil environmental obligations concerning their activities. Therefore, it is difficult to work towards improved environmental compliance levels without active collaboration by the affected private sector.

Environmental civil society initiatives tend to focus their private sector engagement first on offenders in their area of interest, i.e. on the targets of citizen & community-led actions. Such ‘negative’ engagement might be complemented with positive engagement of businesses from the same sector. Companies compliant with all environmental regulations often face higher cost, and thus competitive disadvantages, compared to non-compliant companies, which can make them allies both for formal and civil-society ECA. However, the motivations and objectives for engagement of private business actors who are subject to current or planned regulation has to be carefully considered (Morgenstern and Pizer, 2007).

However, too narrow a focus on duty holders as potential partners overlooks a number of private sector actors that can powerfully shape the enabling environment of a case. In particular, companies with a large workforce or physical presence in the case area, companies reliant on natural resources, or companies strongly affected by perceptions and attitudes of their staff and the surrounding community should be identified and assessed as potential collaboration partners in later stages of the Learning Journey.

⁸The European Union (EU) acquis is the collection of common rights and obligations that constitute the body of EU law, and is incorporated into the legal systems of EU Member States. (Definition by EUR-Lex.europa.eu.)

3.6 Stages of the more4nature case methodology

The more4nature case methodology follows a phased approach with five **key stages** for setting up and implementing the partnerships for collaborative ECA. Each stage includes a generic list of activities and envisaged outcomes; based on content, process and context dimensions that enable transformative change to occur among all involved actors and across governance levels. The more4nature methodology for transformative change within its Pioneer Cases consists of the five stages Prepare, Engage, Explore, Consolidate, and Evaluate & Sustain. Several of these stages consist of carefully designed interaction moments with relevant stakeholders to work towards collaborative ECA. Iterations of distinct stages and stakeholder interactions may be necessary on a case-by-case basis to ensure stage-specific objectives are met.

Figure 46 Stages and expected outputs/outcomes of the more4nature Learning Journey in the cases

The 5 stages consist of generic activity clusters designed to achieve specific milestones along the Case Learning Journey.

summarizes the purpose, key activities, as well as planned inputs and outputs per stage. The following sections will describe the five stages in more detail, in particular highlighting the connections to and implications of the conceptual framework for stage activities, and for guidance of the case contacts in implementing the stage activities. Where possible, the stage descriptions will outline how case activities and guidance might be affected by the thematic area and level of case, as well as by the ECA pillar targeted and path for civil society engagement chosen (CGD or CCLA).

Each stage description will be operationalized in the Case Compendium (see Part II). In order to effectively guide the more4nature cases, the methodology has to be translated into clear advice regarding

- Which stakeholders to engage
- How to apply the guiding principles to activities facilitated in the stage
- Which tools and inputs made available to complete activities
- How the thematic team and mentors will be involved
- How the activities draw on the conceptual frame, or how understanding of case context, case situation, or interaction patterns can help to effectively steer activities.

Table 4 Summary Stages of the more4nature Case Learning Journey

Stage	Purpose	Activities	Envisioned Outcomes
PREPARE	Initial Screening and scoping to prepare engagement with case stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rapid screening of context & case opportunities/challenges • Develop a team vision of collaborative ECA for the case • Initial stakeholder analysis to identify potential Learning Journey participants • Set up of stakeholder management tools & procedures • Tailor methods to comments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Summary of contextual information per case • Team vision for collaborative ECA of the case • Initial set of relevant stakeholders identified & invited • Sound set up of stakeholder management tools & procedures
ENGAGE	Start dialogue with the case stakeholders and launch the Learning Journeys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organise dialogue launch workshop(s) • Agree on principles for collaboration • Develop a (common) vision of collaborative ECA for the case • Collect requirements for collaborative ECA (needs analysis) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 2 interaction moments with case stakeholders completed • Principles for Learning Journey in the cases agreed • (Common) vision of collaborative ECA in the case produced • Initial, agreed Social Learning Agenda with identified transformative changes that are needed at individual, social/organizational and institutional levels to enable collaborative ECA in the case • Detailed needs assessment completed (socio-technical requirements) • Additional stakeholders identified & invited
EXPLORE	Explore and test potential roles and tools of CDG and CCLA in collaborative ECA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iteratively experiment with more4nature socio-technical tools • Co-create CCLAs related to case, with LivingLabs and FabLabs • Include CGD in methods for compliance indicators based on policy requirements and existing CGD, if applicable • Foster horizontal interactions among stakeholders at same governance level & across cases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Socio-relational: improvements in the behavioural dynamics among case case actor groups • Technical tools and methods tested in the case and new requirements identified • Preliminary understanding of proposed changes in governance arrangements setting (e.g. norms & organisational practices, regulatory frameworks, protocols & procedures) • CGD-based indicators & indicator methods tested by the case, if applicable • Case participants joined the CS CoP and the Institutional CoP, respectively • Strengthened capacity of case stakeholders to use selected tools & methods • FAIR & CARE principles implemented by cases

Stage	Purpose	Activities	Envisioned Outcomes
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthen the capacity of case stakeholders to use tools & methods, if needed 	
CONSOLIDATE	<p>Consolidate individual and organisational changes initiated in Learning Journeys and begin embedding tested practices for collaborative ECA</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish a social learning agenda for collaborative ECA in the case Build momentum and acceptance for effective practices in collaborative ECA; stabilize and /or formalize associated rules, roles and responsibilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisational improvements: raised awareness and reflection of collaborative ECA in the organisations of case actors Changes in norms, organisational procedures, regulatory frameworks and protocols Indicator methodologies and alerting systems presented to policymakers and accepted Integration of the case data in the GDDS node for CS Updated, agreed Social Learning Agenda with identified transformative changes that are needed at individual, social/organizational and institutional levels to enable collaborative ECA in the case
CO-EVALUATE & SUSTAIN	<p>Co-evaluate results of the Pioneer Cases & strengthen capacity to sustain changes towards collaborative ECA</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-evaluation of results Strengthen the capacity of case stakeholders for continued collaborative ECA after the end of the facilitated Learning Journey 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ownership; mutual learning & basis for further collaboration Strengthened capacity of institutional actors to include CGD and CCLA Collaborative ECA institutionalised (as much as possible) ECA indicator and alerting systems sustained over time

3.6.1 Stage 1 – PREPARE

STAGE 1 – PREPARE	
Initial Screening and scoping to prepare engagement with case stakeholders	
Key activities & activity clusters	Envisioned outputs & outcomes per case
Rapid screening of context & case opportunities/challenges	Summary of contextual information per case
Develop a team vision of collaborative ECA for the case	Team vision for collaborative ECA of the case
Initial stakeholder analysis to identify potential Learning Journey participants	Initial set of relevant stakeholders identified & invited
Set up of stakeholder management tools & procedures	Sound set up of stakeholder management tools & procedures
Tailor methods to comments	
Interactions with more4nature WPs	
Inputs from WP1 to case	Outputs from case to WP1
Policy analysis (case relevant) (T1.1) Actor agendas/resources Template for national policy analysis (T1.1) Policy/legislation monitoring (T1.1/T4.5)	Incremental input on national policy context (T1.1)
Inputs from WP2 to case	Outputs from case to WP2
Demonstration of existing tools for data cataloguing, accessing CGD and alerting apps.	Definition of the current status of the Pioneer Cases.
Learning Dialogue & Reflection fostered across tasks and cases	
Mentoring session(s) (per thematic Z/B/D cluster) with case contacts to prepare start of case Learning Journeys	

The more4nature cases start in a situation characterized by strong power and information asymmetries between the case stakeholders involved, while confronting each case actor with a challenge outside their current expertise. Therefore, it is important to be mindful of the following:

- **Civil society actors** in the more4nature Pioneer Cases have extensive experience in their field of environmental governance, but will typically not analyse issues from the specific legal and institutionalized perspective of formal ECA.
- **Institutional actors** engage in the field based on formal mandates, and have access to internal information and policies, strategies and ECA practices as action resources. They are likely to consider citizen engagement in terms of citizens using tip lines or other channels offered to them, and might be less familiar with the full potential of CS and CCLA.
- **Case contacts** share a high motivation to empower citizens in ECA, but the new role as stimulator of a guided social learning process might differ from past engagement with the stakeholders involved.

Citizen involvement in most formal ECA is an ambition, not an entitlement. In extreme cases, it is possible that an institutional ECA actor refuses to join the process altogether, or drops out because

they perceive a conflict with their mandate or priorities. Therefore, diligent preparation is crucial to prevent starting the case Learning Journey on the figurative ‘wrong foot’, and accidentally undermine successful incubation.

The purpose of the PREPARE stage is to clarify the starting point of the Learning Journey based on a more comprehensive *understanding* of the situation, and to put into place the tools needed for successful initial engagement of case stakeholders.

Main Activities: Pioneer Case contacts enter the PREPARE stage with specific ideas and motivations regarding collaborative ECA, for example reflected in the results of the Case Impact Journey exercise completed in M2. The guided rapid assessment of the case context, challenges and opportunities invites the cases to take a step back from the experience-based planning, and test their understanding of situational and context aspects relevant to successfully initiating a transformative change process towards collaborative ECA. The results of the rapid assessment will then be used to review the ideas reflected in the Case Impact Journey template, checking if there is a need for adjustment to correct mistaken assumptions or misperceptions, in recognition of new priorities or previously unknown opportunities, or due to increased understanding of the legality or feasibility of original plans. Discussion will result in the development of a preliminary vision for collaborative ECA in the case. The team vision serves both to guide stakeholder identification, and to craft messaging for their engagement.

A second group of activities involves practical preparation of the Case Learning Journey, such as setting up the workspace including assembly of background and contact information, starting and customizing collaborative documents, and a review of local practicalities that affect planning of events.

3.6.2 Stage 2 – ENGAGE

STAGE 2 – ENGAGE	
Start dialogue with the case stakeholders and launch the Learning Journeys	
Key activities & activity clusters	Envisioned outputs & outcomes per case
Organise dialogue launch workshop(s)	At least 2 interaction moments with case stakeholders completed
Agree on principles for collaboration	Principles for Learning Journey in the cases agreed
Develop a (common) vision of collaborative ECA for the case	<i>(Common) vision of collaborative ECA in the case produced</i>
Establish an initial social learning agenda for collaborative ECA in the case	Initial, agreed <i>Social Learning Agenda</i> with identified transformative changes that are needed at individual, social/organizational and institutional levels to enable collaborative ECA in the case
Derive requirements for collaborative ECA (needs analysis)	Detailed needs assessment completed (socio-technical requirements)
	Additional stakeholders identified & invited
Interactions with more4nature WPs	
Inputs from WP1 to case	Outputs from case to WP1
Needs assessment tool (T1.4) for identifying key actors' incentives and barriers (completed with/by case stakeholders)	Detailed social & socio-technical requirements (for T1.3 and T1.4)
FAIR & CARE principles (T1.3)	
Comprehensive map of ECA indicators for which CS is already contributing data or has potential to do so in the future (T1.2, D1.2).	
Cross-case examples from policy context (T1.1)	
Inputs from WP2 to case	Outputs from case to WP2
Data catalogues and harmonization tools (T2.1)	Detailed technical & socio-technical requirements (reached agreement on what is feasible and within project roadmap) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What data is collected • What level of quality is required • How does it need to be processed and presented to each audience
Sharing and analysing data according to agreed data management principles FAIR & CARE and ethical requirements (technical aspects and standardization) (T2.4)	Current standards of CGD for sharing, validation, harmonization and processing, including current indicator creation and alerting: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of existing data – data catalogue – databases and infrastructure (CGD but also other sources to improve it (e.g. Copernicus data)) • Methods and tools for CGD collection, storage and analysis of the CI Initiatives involved in this case

STAGE 2 – ENGAGE (cont.)	
Inputs from WP3 to case	
Showcasing from more4nature partners experienced with collaborative ECA	
Learning dialogue & reflection fostered across tasks and cases	
Meetings with case contacts and other more4nature project team members within thematic area (Z/B/D) (T3.2.X)	

The purpose of the ENGAGE stage is to successfully initiate, with the case stakeholders, the *Learning Journey towards increased collaboration in ECA*, offering a ‘neutral arena’ and creating conditions conducive to transformative social learning among actors that are in a position to negotiate collaborative ECA.

Main Activities: the more4nature team will be convening case-specific sessions to invite case stakeholders (civil society and institutional actors) into the ‘neutral arena’ and to gain their commitment for the Learning Journey facilitated by more4nature, by reaching agreement on the principles for collaboration. These ‘interaction moments’ may take place in joint sessions or in bilateral meetings (e.g. separately with civil society actors and institutional actors, respectively), depending on the case situation ascertained during the PREPARE stage.

The sessions will be designed to provide guided exchanges to arrive at a joint understanding of the ECA challenges to be addressed. Facilitation will require careful promotion of dialogue and integration of different perspectives. The aim of these sessions is to gain insights into the dynamics of the current ECA situation in the case, incl. current practices and stakeholder assumptions about the ECA situation in the case; involvement in related, already ongoing processes of change and learning; the technical set up such as current standards of CGD for sharing, validation, harmonization and processing; the extent of current incorporation of CGD and CCLA into ECA; as well as the stakeholders’ ideas and motivations regarding collaborative ECA. The discussions among the stakeholders, facilitated by the more4nature team, are intended to generate a joint definition (or at least joint delineation) of problems with current ECA, a (common) vision for collaborative ECA in the case and an initial social learning agenda that identifies the specific changes for progressing from the current situation to the envisaged collaborative ECA in the case. The extent to which this will be a truly ‘common’ vision will differ from case to case, depending on the initial dynamics among the case stakeholders.

The more4nature cluster teams will analyse the stakeholder vision of collaborative ECA for the case, along with the results of the needs assessment to i) generate detailed technical & socio-technical requirements for collaborative ECA, taking into account what is feasible and within the more4nature project roadmap and ii) identify additional stakeholders that should be invited to subsequent workshops with the case stakeholders.

3.6.3 Stage 3 - EXPLORE

STAGE 3 – EXPLORE	
Explore and test potential roles and tools of CDG and CCLA in collaborative ECA	
Key activities & activity clusters	Envisioned outputs & outcomes per case
Iteratively experiment with more4nature socio-technical tools	<i>Socio-relational</i> : improvements in the behavioural dynamics among case stakeholder groups
	Technical tools and methods tested in the case and new requirements identified
	FAIR & CARE principles implemented by cases
Co-create CCLAs related to case, with LivingLabs and FabLabs	Preliminary understanding of proposed changes in governance arrangements (e.g. norms & organisational practices, regulatory frameworks, protocols & procedures)
Include CGD in methods for compliance indicators based on policy requirements and existing CGD, if applicable	CGD based indicators & indicator methods tested by the case, if applicable
Strengthen the capacity of case stakeholders to use tools & methods, if needed	Strengthened capacity of case stakeholders to use selected tools & methods
Interactions with more4nature WPs	
Inputs from WP1 to case	Outputs from case to WP1
Initial repository with capacity building tools & methods to address social & socio-technical needs (guidance for categorised needs) (T1.4)	Feedback on initial (proposal of) set of socio-technical tools
Methodology for co-designing (local) CCLAs in CS Initiatives and LivingLabs (T1.5)	Co-designed CCLAs (for T1.5)
Initial set of proposed Indicators for the case (T1.2)	Feedback on initial set of proposed indicators likely for the case (for T1.2)

STAGE 3 – EXPLORE (cont.)	
Inputs from WP2 to case	Outputs from case to WP2
Iterative development and adaptation of:	Are the tools "fit-for-purpose" at various levels? Feedback on tools re.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical level: performance feedback, ease of use • Adoptability • Acceptance by final target groups • Examples • Comparison to the selected indicators • Using data to evaluate trends based on indicators
Tools for data collection, validation, and processing (T2.1, T2.3, T2.5, T2.7).	
Tools for trusting the data and data quality (T2.2, T2.5)	
Infringement Alerting system (use of existing alert systems, e.g. related to deforestation such as GLAD alerts or NASA FIRMS active fire data)	
How data is it going to be used (e.g. indicators and beyond) and by whom	
Defined and selected indicators (together with WP1) based on the generated data in WP3	
Learning Dialogue & Reflection fostered across tasks and cases	
Meetings with M4N team members within thematic area (Z/B/D) (T3.2.X)	
Participation of CS Initiatives and institutional actors from the case in the respective CoPs (CS CoP; thematic CoPs; institutional CoP) (T3.6)	
Activities with LivingLabs and FabLabs (T3.5)	

The purpose of the EXPLORE stage is to facilitate the iterative experimentation with and by the case stakeholders with the more4nature socio-technical tools and approaches, feeding the cumulatively generated insights back into the project for continuous improvements of the tools and enhancement of the capacity building repository.

Main Activities: The social & socio-technical tools and roles identified by the more4nature partners for addressing the identified requirements will be tested and used during hands on experimentation and socio-technical impulses with the case stakeholders in order to assess whether they are "fit-for-purpose" at various levels. The facilitation of the sessions in this stage has to focus on creating an atmosphere of open-mindedness, willingness to share knowledge and learn (incl. from failure), and foster critical self-reflection. The use of specific tools and approaches may also be reliant on additional technical or legal experts who have to be onboarded and integrated in these sessions. relevant existing LivingLabs and FabLabs for the co-design of case-specific suitable CCLAs have to be identified and engaged. Based on the deeper understanding of the case context, situation, ambition and behavioural dynamics among the case stakeholders, required changes in governance arrangements (e.g. norms & organisational practices, regulatory frameworks, protocols & procedures) will be analysed.

Additional activities related to strengthening (horizontal) social interactions among stakeholders at the same governance level and across cases and to ramping up learning dialogues and reflection beyond the thematic clusters. Case stakeholders will be connected across cases in relevant Communities of Practice, while carefully considering their availability to avoid ‘engagement fatigue’.

3.6.4 Stage 4 – CONSOLIDATE

STAGE 4 – CONSOLIDATE	
Consolidate individual and organisational changes initiated in Learning Journeys and begin embedding tested practices for collaborative ECA	
Key activities & activity clusters	Envisioned outputs & outcomes per case
Build momentum and acceptance for effective practices in collaborative ECA; stabilize and /or formalize associated rules, roles and responsibilities	<i>Organisational improvements:</i> raised awareness and reflection of collaborative ECA in the organisations of case stakeholders
	Changes in norms, organisational procedures, regulatory frameworks and protocols
	Indicator methodologies and alerting systems presented to policymakers and accepted
	Integration of the case data in the GDDS node for CS
Review and revise the social learning agenda for collaborative ECA in the case	Updated, agreed <i>Social Learning Agenda</i> with further transformative changes that are needed at individual, social/organizational and institutional levels to enable collaborative ECA in the case
Interactions with more4nature WPs	
Inputs from WP1 to case	
Indicate/link to opportunities in National/EU fora for reviewing the law/policy. If yes, link with relevant CS experts to get involved (T1.1, T4.5, T3.5)	Feedback on CCLA methodology effectiveness & impact
Inputs from WP2 to case	Outputs from case to WP2
From alpha to beta (or perhaps production)	Integrated official and CGD used for modelling or official reports
Making data run in common data sharing infrastructure (e.g. GDDS node for CS)	
Tools for visualization and for data analysis	
Inputs from WP4 to case	
Tested tools and methods from WP1 and WP2 (available via the Needs & Solutions Hub on Online Knowledge Platform)	
Learning Dialogue & Reflection fostered across tasks and cases	
Meetings with mre4nature team members within thematic area (Z/B/D) (T3.2.X) Case participants active in the CoPs (CS CoP; thematic CoPs; institutional CoP) (T3.6) Activities with LivingLabs and FabLabs (T3.5)	

The purpose of the CONSOLIDATE stage is to embed the tested practices for collaborative ECA in organisational and institutional protocols & procedures, and regulatory frameworks.

Main Activities: Ideally, by this stage, case stakeholders will have witnessed (some level of) convergence of goals and purpose that transcends the motivations and expectations of individual actors and reaches a collective, societal level. Boosting cooperation and learning among case stakeholders remains important but needs to progress to the consolidation and institutionalisation of tested practices for collaborative ECA to ensure that collaborations, practices and procedures are maintained beyond the involvement of the participating individuals, e.g. withstanding staff turnover.

Not all changes in behaviours and actions re. collaborative ECA resulting from new understandings, mental models, beliefs, perceptions and practices can be realized by the case stakeholders, or by them alone. Case stakeholders will require supporting with building momentum and acceptance for effective practices in collaborative ECA and how to stabilize and /or formalize associated rules, roles and responsibilities. Organisational path dependencies can narrow the range of available action options within their organisations at critical junctions. These might feature visibly in the narratives of respective (institutional) stakeholders in the case sessions, if not revealed earlier from the behavioural dynamics analysis. Overcoming path dependencies will require carefully exploration of options, incl. leveraging mechanisms of influence inside the administration.

Ultimately, the potential for changing the role of citizens in ECA is highly dependent on the room that citizens are granted by authorities – but also on that claimed by citizen. Such changes in behaviours and actions may take time to develop and become ‘acceptable’ to individuals and organizations, requiring perseverance, incl. beyond the more4nature lifetime. A key activity in this stage is therefore to facilitate the review and revisions of the social learning agenda by the case stakeholders to articulate their continued commitment and to serve as a roadmap going forward.

3.6.5 Stage 5 – EVALUATE & SUSTAIN

STAGE 5 – EVALUATE & SUSTAIN	
Co-evaluate results of the Pioneer Cases & strengthen capacity to sustain changes towards collaborative ECA	
Key activities & activity clusters	Envisioned outputs & outcomes per case
Co-evaluation of results	Ownership; mutual learning & basis for further collaboration
Strengthen the capacity of case stakeholders for continued collaborative ECA after the end of the facilitated Learning Journey	Strengthened capacity of institutional actors to include CGD and CCLA in ECA
	Collaborative ECA institutionalised (as much as possible)
	ECA indicator and alerting systems sustained over time
Interactions with more4nature WPs	
	Outputs from case to WP1
	Content for methods & tools refinement (T1.4 and T1.5)
Inputs from WP2 to case	Outputs from case to WP2
Operationalised indicator methods and alerting systems	Content for Dashboards and story maps (T2.8)
	Outputs from case to WP3
	Lessons learned from change processes towards collaborative ECA from case; from thematic team; from CS initiatives CoP and institutional CoP; from LivingLabs and FabLabs interactions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insights for reflections on first cycle & refinement (T3.3) • Insights for scientific analysis (T3.8)
Learning Dialogue & Reflection fostered across tasks and cases	
Lessons learned collected from cases, thematic teams, CS CoP, thematic CoPs, institutional CoP, and LivingLabs and FabLabs for refinement of methodology and scientific analysis	

The purpose of the EVALUATE & SUSTAIN stage is to take stock of the results achieved via joint evaluation and reflection with the case stakeholders and to ensure that capacities are in place for sustaining the changes made already towards collaborative ECA.

Main Activities: Inherently, evidence of changes is difficult to collect with short-term interventions. A relevant and appropriate evaluation, undertaken jointly with the case stakeholders and consistently in all cases, will generate case-specific as well as generic insights for the refinement of the more4nature methodology and its implementation in the Follower cases.

Another key activity in this stage is the implementation of various capacity strengthening activities with the case stakeholders (and across cases and CoPs) to ensure that the continuation of collaborative ECA after the end of the facilitated Learning Journey with the more4nature team.

3.7 Implementation of the more4nature change process in the Pioneer cases

Implementation of the more4nature action research methodology in the Pioneer cases involves the following elements:

1. **Case contacts**
2. **Case compendium** as primary tool for case guidance, workspace, and documentation of case insights
3. **Mentoring of the cases in thematic teams (Z/B/D)** by the more4nature experts in a collaborative process
4. **Interactions between cases** to enable peer learning, co-evaluation and reflection of the Pioneer Case experiences in preparation of the second loop of action research with Follower Cases.

3.7.1 Case contact

Case contacts carry the primary responsibility for implementing the more4nature Action Research methodology in the Pioneer Cases. Case contacts are staff members of more4nature consortium partners and as such part of the project team with access to confidential and methodical aspects of the Learning Journey. Using the case compendium (section 3.7.2) as working tools, they will act as interface between the project in participating CS initiatives and ECA actors.

The specific responsibilities of the more4nature Case Contacts is to:

1. engage relevant actors - Civil society (Community-led initiatives and CS initiatives), Institutional actors at the governance level relevant to the specific case (ECA authorities, enforcement agencies, legislators), experts (scientific and legal), and the private sector;
2. stimulate social learning among all actors involved in the more4nature cases, within the organizations to which they belong and at the institutional setting in which they operate; and, thus,
3. bring about transformative change towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance in the respective thematic areas of more4nature in the cases (zero pollution, biodiversity protection, deforestation prevention).

The role of the Case Contact the social learning process of the case stakeholders is summarized in Figure 47.

Figure 47 Case contacts stimulating social learning in the facilitated learning journey (adapted from: Figueroa et al., 2002)

Case contacts will be mentored by the more4nature thematic teams (see section 3.7.3) to enable them as facilitators of the Case Learning Journeys. Research shows that effective network management affects the outcomes of governance networks (Klijn, Steijn and Edelenbos, 2010), and related skills need to be carefully considered. Given the nature of the more4nature Learning Journey as process of Transformational Change (see section 2.8), case contacts should be considered as change agents (Irvine et al., 2016). Change agents initiate and introduce changes within the system they work in (Atkisson, 2011). Successfully acting as change agent requires not just technical skills, but also intrinsic motivation, relational skills, openness to engage in reflexive learning methods, as well as awareness for normative dimensions involved in shaping institutional frameworks (Felder and Brent, 2004; Brundiers, Wiek and Redman, 2010; Myers, Staats and Gino, 2014).

Relational skills: Stakeholder engagement is a cornerstone of sustainable development, and requires collaborative planning and decision-making, building trust, maintaining relationships and valuing the contributions of diverse actors. Transformative change starts with securing commitment from leaders, buy-in from staff, and support from relevant external groups. Translated into competency needs for change agents, stakeholder engagement requires combinations of interpersonal and communication skills, process (management) competencies, open-mindedness and a willingness to learn and adapt (Kranz and Mostert, 2010; Atkisson, 2011; Lansu et al., 2013; Wesselink et al., 2015; Irvine et al., 2016).

Normative and ethical aspects: The facilitation of task involving normative and ethical dimensions present specific challenges. Skills for the management of three aspects are of particular relevance:

- 1) Building a **shared understanding of collaborative ECA**. Stakeholders sometimes perceive initial sharing of their own knowledge and sense-making as lengthy and cumbersome. But since human understanding is shaped by culture and personal experience, even terms carrying a formal definition may have different interpretations, and identical ideas are expressed in different terms. Time invested in collaborative workshops is, therefore, rarely wasted. Jointly developing an agreed vision builds trust, reveals hidden values and creates pre-

conditions for successful collaboration and programme implementation (Pfeiffer *et al.*, no date; Pfeiffer and Leentvaar, 2013).

- 2) Dealing with **'messy' workplace realities**: Workshop exercises in project planning phases rarely anticipate that actors might refuse to listen to prepared presentations, react outraged or insulted at carefully thought-through solutions, fail to care about topics other parties are passionate about, or attempt to instrumentalize or manipulate the process for personal gain. Real-world decision-making can be biased by power and personal affiliations, and dominated by greed, self-interest, or intransigent positions rooted in fear or ideology. Mentoring change agents, therefore, has to include tools for dealing with agendas and emotions. A particular challenge will be the ethical dimensions of transformative change and the potential ethical implications of the more4nature results. This is discussed in more detail in more4nature deliverable 6.1 and section 3.4.
- 3) **Dealing with norms and personal values**: It is increasingly recognized that personal background and education influences how professionals envision and judge personal conduct in their chosen profession (Gantt and Madison, 2015). Case contacts bring their own identities, ambitions and expectations to the process, which can create specific challenges. Staff involved in new or specialized degree programmes will often share related values, but suggesting a norm-driven agenda for existing practices might face outright rejection (Grindstedt 2015). Experts with technical backgrounds often assume that information leads to knowledge which leads to behavioural changes and struggle to accommodate value-based arguments of local communities, which can cause conflict in expert-led planning environments (Halbe *et al.* 2015). Behaviour-based approaches to policy making ((Vandenbergh, Carrico and Bressman, 2011; Cammack, 2014; Banerjee and Galizzi, 2024)) are based on awareness for mental models and value systems, but the understanding is still limited and can easily turn into manipulation (Sunstein, 2015; Schmidt and Engelen, 2020). Change is ultimately facilitated by inspiring people to care about a subject, which cannot be "taught" or trained into stakeholders (Pfeiffer *et al.*, no date; Brundiers, Wiek and Redman, 2010; Myers, Staats and Gino, 2014).

Accordingly, the mentoring of the Case contacts forms an integral part of the methodology, and will be embedded in the guidance for all activities of the Pioneer Case Learning Journeys.

3.7.2 Case Compendia as primary implementation tools

A 'compendium' is a **structured workbook** containing instructions, worksheets and guidelines that accompanies the more4nature cases in throughout their Learning Journey. The generic more4nature case compendium presented in Part 2 of this report is a template that will be used to set up a dedicated, confidential online workspace for the more4nature partners to work on case-specific details. The compendium clarifies the purpose of each stage, and provides guidance for the implementation of key activities as well as forms and templates to document activities taking place in each case. Checklists serve to monitor progress in the cases and signal readiness to transition from one stage to the next.

The instructions and templates in the compendium originate from multiple more4nature work packages, and these work packages will use the compendia to share case-specific relevant information with cases. Collating all interactions into one coherent compendium per case serves to reduce the number of documents and requests each Pioneer Case has to handle at any given time, and to prevent redundancies. The standardized documentation of activities in all cases turns the case compendia into a tool for structured data collection at the same time. It ensures **consistent implementation across the Pioneer Cases** and is a basis for comparison, generating inputs for the overarching Action Research goals of the project.

Overall, the case compendium:

- (1) guides the more4nature case contacts in the set up and implementation of the Learning Journey for collaborative ECA in their case;

- (2) ensures that the principles guiding the case journeys are observed and remain embedded in activities and decision-making
- (3) orient the case activities in each stage towards achieving transformative change at the individual, social relational/organizational and institutional levels.

Dissemination status: project internal (**confidential**).

The process of working with the compendium is as follows:

1. WP1 and WP2 task leads prepare guidance related to each stage that informs the activities in all more4nature case studies. These instructions are the same for all cases and these are collated in the generic compendium template. Each case study uses their own copy of the compendium as a workspace (i.e. a Notebook on the more4nature shared drive).
2. The case teams use the respective compendium for each case in their thematic area to record and report all results of their Learning Journey set-up and implementation activities, jointly filling in the documents over time. This ensures all information is easily accessible for all tasks in more4nature, without the need for much coordination.
3. The progressive completion of each case compendium [i.e. completion of tables in the main text and the respective compendium activities, as requested] feeds into and is undertaken during the regular thematic area team teleconferences and discussions (see section 3.7.3). These meetings will therefore also serve as a mechanism to ‘enforce’ use of the more4nature compendium for each case.

3.7.3 Thematic Teams

Dedicated teams of more4nature partners are formed to set up and implement the Learning Journey in each case, one team per thematic area (zero pollution, biodiversity protection, deforestation prevention). **Each thematic team consists of the participating case contacts, social science experts from WP1 and technology experts from WP2, as well as IHE team members supporting implementation of the methodology.** The thematic leads convene these meetings and provide thematic issue-related expertise/interest (Z/B/D), while the mentoring on specific socio-technical aspects is done by WP1 and WP2 experts, respectively.

Figure 48 Illustration of Action Research case clustering, following a common methodology at their own pace (source: CitiObs)

The thematic team meetings will build on the successful experience with guiding clusters of cases in the CitiObs project. During the more4nature sessions of the thematic teams, one or two more4nature cases can be discussed in detail, showcasing to all others how specific activities per stage are implemented, providing the opportunity to mentor and address case-specific as well as general questions and concerns. With the cases taking turns during these weekly/bi-weekly sessions, sufficient depth of mentoring and guidance can be provided while avoiding fatigue with having all case contacts report on (mostly) the same aspects each time.

Table 5 Thematic Clustering of more4nature Pioneer Cases

Level	Title	Country	Partner
Biodiversity Protection			
Thematic Lead: Nordisk Fond for Miljø og Udvikling (NORD)			
National	Monitoring and achieving global biodiversity targets	Denmark	NORD
National	Reversing the decline of pollinators	Netherlands	NIOO
National	Reversing the decline of pollinators	Portugal	FC.ID
National	Free-flowing rivers for freshwater (and wetland) biodiversity	Norway	NIVA
Local	Reversing the decline of pollinators	Oeiras, Portugal	FC.ID
Local	Free-flowing rivers for freshwater (and wetland) biodiversity	Rogaland River Basin District, Norway	NIVA
Local	Monitoring and achieving global biodiversity targets	Thy National Park, Denmark	NORD
Deforestation Prevention			
Thematic Lead: Kobenhavns Universitet (UCHP)			
National	Halting illegal deforestation	Denmark	UCHP
Local	Reducing forest loss from illegal activities and fires	Bolivia	Forests of the world
Local	Halting illegal deforestation	Five provinces in Cambodia	UCPH
Local	Halting illegal deforestation	Jutland and Falster, Denmark	UCPH
Zero Pollution			
Thematic Lead: Irish Coastal Environment Group (CW)			
National	Clean and healthy surface water	Ireland	Coastwatch (CW)
National	Preventing plastics in the ocean	Ireland	Coastwatch (CW)
National	Clean air for all	Netherlands	RIVM
National	Preventing plastics in the ocean	Norway	NIVA
National	Clean air for all	Poland	Krakow Smog Alert (KSA)
National	Clean and healthy surface water	Sierra Leone	Earthwatch (EW)
Local	Clean air for all	Dunmore East stream flowing into EU Bathing Water, Ireland	Coastwatch
Local	Clean and healthy surface water	Marzenego River, Italy	Earthwatch
Local	Clean air for all	Oslo, Bergen & Kristiansand, Norway	NILU

3.7.4 Cross-case learning

The main research question that more4nature addresses is how the transition towards collaborative environmental compliance as processes of change can be realized for zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention. more4nature proposes a socio-technical approach to deal with the prevailing social and technical challenges that limit the improved integration of Citizen Science initiatives in policy and decision making in general and in environmental compliance assurance in particular. This will address both, i) how to bring about the necessary social changes, strengthened capacity, collaboration and partnerships between citizens, CS INITIATIVES, experts and

authorities, as well as ii) the technical advances and developments to increase the quality, usefulness of and trust in data and generate knowledge from diverse sources, incl. by means of data governance mechanisms.

There is no blue-print (yet) of how to transition towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance. The methodology for the Action Research with the cases (20+20) is designed to provide demand-driven guidance, tools and capacity building to trigger changes towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance in real-life settings. **A key element will be to feature success cases** (e.g. specific Coastwatch campaigns in Ireland and other parts of Europe, RIVM uptake of CGD in NL, citizens monitoring of forests in Denmark, community patrols to monitor deforestation in Cambodia) during these co-design sessions. We will also involve the stakeholders across the cases in the finalisation of the more4nature dashboards, interfaces, tools and approaches and ensure their ease-of-use via the more4nature Online Knowledge Platform. The consistent implementation of the more4nature case methodology across the Pioneer Cases provides the basis for comparison in order to derive scientifically sound insights, lessons learned and recommendations, as well as a draft blue print for the Follower cases on how to transition towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance.

Peer-to-peer learning among and between Pioneer Cases (T3.2) and Follower Cases (T3.4) will be facilitated in a number of targeted ways. Based on experience from the previous WeObserve H2020 project, existing 'best practice' methods in knowledge management and exchange, including workshops, twinning and Communities of Practice (CoP) will be applied. The task will initially establish two overarching CoPs by M9: 1) citizens and CS INITIATIVES across all cases, and 2) local/regional authorities, national agencies and policy makers across all cases; these 2 CoPs will be led by NORD and organize at least 3 online meetings per full year per CoP. Subsequent to and building on stakeholder interactions in the cases, we will also establish three additional CoPs with CS INITIATIVES, local/regional authorities, national agencies and policymakers in all Pioneer and Follower Cases within each theme (Z/B/D). These 3 CoPs will be led by the respective theme leaders and will organize at least 3 online meetings per full year. Twinning will be organized initially between relevant local and national cases, subsequently within themes (Z/B/D) among Pioneer and Follower Cases. Existing CoPs and Working Groups (e.g. the ECSA WGs, WeObserve CoPs, the Citizen Science & Open Science CoP) and the LivingLabs and FabLabs involved with the themes will be invited to participate.

3.8 Summary

This chapter has provided detailed information about the more4nature methodology for the change process in ECA at case level and its implementation. This methodology will be implemented through two cycles of Action Research suitable to stimulating transformative change towards collaborative ECA. The double loop action research involving two large sets of cases (20 Pioneer Cases and 20 Follower Cases) requires careful coordination to ensure consistent and coherent application as well a timely completion of the five stages of the methodology by the cases. These activities are being strengthened and reinforced by continuous learning within and across the cases via carefully crafted and planned learning mechanisms (see schedule in Figure 49). This schedule of activities has been discussed with the more4nature partners and was finalised based on their suggestions.

Figure 49 Implementation of the more4nature methodology in the Pioneers & Follower cases

4 Conclusions and next Steps

This report has outlined the rationale and scientific foundation for the more4nature conceptual framework and the corresponding methodology for the more4nature Double Loop Action Research (Part 1), along with the comprehensive guide for stage 1 of the case methodology in the form of a compendium for the Pioneer cases (Part 2). It integrates state of the art insights on establishing and implementing effective social learning processes among key stakeholders in the cases to foster transformative change towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance. For the thematic teams in more4nature, the compendium included in this report (Part 2), along with ongoing coaching from experts in WP1 and WP2, will serve as a crucial tool for ensuring the successful and consistent implementation of the Learning Journeys in the more4nature Pioneer Cases.

This report has introduced the initial prototype version of the more4nature compendium. The final version, containing complete instructions for all stages of the methodology, will be developed during the first cycle of the more4nature Double Loop Action Research. After being reviewed and refined, it will be implemented in the second stage of the more4nature Double Loop Action Research with the Follower Cases.

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Part II

Prototype Compendium

for the first loop of Action

Research with the

Pioneer Cases

Presentation of the Prototype Compendium in this Deliverable

The more4nature Case Compendia are realized as a shared workspace in the online platform. The online workspace provides a number of tools that support the work of case contacts, but for which exact replication in a deliverable document it not useful. The presentation of the compendium is adjusted to the purpose of this deliverable as follows:

Compendium Navigation

All content is grouped into sections containing pages displayed similar to a website, with a **visual navigation menu**. Therefore, compendium content does not have chapter numbering. To make the prototype compendium readable as a deliverable, the following sections contain the text content of online compendium pages, combined with screenshots that show the navigation as it will be visible to case contacts (see example below).

The online format of the compendium does not include “landing pages” for a section. Therefore, the logic behind the Compendium navigation structure is not narrated in the Compendium itself. To assist the reader, “**section summaries**” have been included in this deliverable, clarifying the rationale of the section and outlining the content pages included.

Resource materials

Background information and resources can be included in the text and made accessible with hyperlinks. Therefore, definitions and explanations can be kept short in the text, and simplifies cross-references. The compendium predominantly uses **resource links** for three different types of references.

1. Links to pages in a more4nature methodology online reference. The online reference replicates Part I of this deliverable. Any element of the conceptual frame or methodology mentioned in the instructions, such as “case context”, is linked to the respective section in the online reference.

The screenshot shows a Microsoft Word document titled "Preview Pioneer Compendium". The document content includes a table of contents with sections like "About the Pioneer Co...", "Case Information", "Case Management", "Stage 1 PREPARE", "Stage 2 ENGAGE", "Stage 3 EXPLORE", "Stage 4 CONSOLIDATE", and "Stage 5 CO-EVALUATE...". The main text area is titled "What is the Pioneer Compendium" and contains introductory text about the compendium's purpose and a note about its use in case studies.

↑ links in the compendium lead to an online reference version of D3.1 ↓

The screenshot shows a Microsoft Word document titled "D3.1 Methodology - Preview". The document content includes a table of contents with sections like "1 Introduction", "2 Conceptual Framework", and "3 Methodology". The main text area is titled "2.1 Approach to Framework Development" and contains a section titled "2 more4nature conceptual framework" with a sub-section "2.1 Approach to framework development" and a list of four functions.

2. Links to other section of the Case Compendium. Information about the evolving case is collected by the case and provided to the case in line with the activities in the Learning Journey. Some data collection is spread over several activities, such as the stakeholder analysis, which is refined in several steps. The online format of the compendium makes it possible to present instructions and activities chronologically, while compiling resulting information into organically evolving resources accessible in multiple ways.
3. Links to other more4nature deliverables relevant to preparing activities or deepening the understanding of observations made in the Learning Journey.

Coding of data collection and other tools

While the deliverable format is not suitable to replicate the hyperlink navigation, the following section will indicate resources made accessible via link from each page.

The online compendium can be edited by case contacts, and instructions may include requests to insert text or fill tables. However, the platform does not allow collaborative work on documents, and it is not designed as a data collection tool. Therefore, the majority of content and data collection is not realized in the online compendium itself. Rather, the compendium integrates **links to a range of complementary tools**, including collaborative documents, templates, or online surveys. The following section will employ icons to indicate which tools are used in the online compendium for data collection, The data collection tools themselves are illustrated with screenshots, or included as Annex where suitable.

Page descriptions are coded as follows:

- **Information** – the page contains narrative and explanatory text. All narrative text of the compendium is replicated in this deliverable in full.
- !** **Instructions** – the page contains instructions for action by the Case Contact.
- **Direct entry** – the page includes fields for direct data entry by the Case Contact into the Compendium, such as a table.
- **Data collection** – the page includes a link to an online form for collection of research data into a database, using tools such as the Kobo toolbox, ODK or Google Forms.
- **Collaborative document** – the page contains a link to a collaborative document. Collaborative documents are files with a coherent format for all cases, designed by more4nature tasks. Copies of the file are stored in the case folders of each individual case in the online platform, and are typically filled by case teams in collaborative activities.
- **Templates** – the page contains a link to a template. A template is a document provided by a project task for the purpose of collecting data outside the online tools linked to the compendium. Templates are files that are downloaded from a central repository, filled in 'offline', and subsequently scanned or digitized and uploaded into specific folder in the online workspace.

Summary Section 1 (Deliverable only, not online)

About the Pioneer Compendium

Preview Pioneer Compendium ▾	
About the Pioneer Co...	What is the Pioneer Compendium?
Case Information	How to use the Compendium
Case Management	Your role as Case Contact
Stage 1 PREPARE	
Stage 2 ENGAGE	
Stage 3 EXPLORE	
Stage 4 CONSOLIDATE	
Stage 5 CO-EVALUATE...	

Purpose of the Section

The section is a ‘quick start’ user manual for case contacts and other users accessing the compendium. It ensures users not familiar with the methodology receive a short briefing and are guided to background resources, including the online reference version of deliverable D3.1. Furthermore, it includes practical guidance, such as an overview of icons used in the compendium to denote different types of assignments. Finally, a “your role as case contact” summarizes parts of the methodology that will translate into actions by the case contact, to make the implications and personal influence of the case contact more clear and accessible.

Pages in the Section

- What is the more4nature Pioneer Case Compendium
- How to use the compendium
- Your role as Case Contact

What is the more4nature Pioneer Case Compendium

The screenshot shows a Microsoft Word document with the following content:

Table of Contents:

About the Pioneer Co...	What is the Pioneer Com...
Case Information	How to use the Compen...
Case Management	Your role as Case Contact
Stage 1 PREPARE	
Stage 2 ENGAGE	
Stage 3 EXPLORE	
Stage 4 CONSOLIDATE	
Stage 5 CO-EVALUATE...	

Document Title: What is the Pioneer Compendium?
 Sunday, June 23, 2024 5:31 PM

Text:

The more4nature case compendium is an internal, confidential workbook containing instructions, worksheets and inputs that will guide your case through the more4nature learning journey. It is a key part of the [more4nature methodology](#).

The compendium is a one-stop shop through which

- You can find all information needed to facilitate the learning journey of your case, and
- document all case activities and submit information to the project

It contains

- Guidance for the stage and activities in each stage
- Links to forms, templates or collaborative documents to report case activities
- Summary checklist on progress to confirm when a stage is completed
- Inputs from other more4nature work packages
- Background information about the conceptual frame and method (D3.1)

The compendium is structured according to the stages of the more4nature Learning Journey (see Figure below). Each stage consists of a number of activities that need to be completed before advancing to the next stage. The compendium will clarify the purpose of each stage in the process, provide guidance for the implementation of key activities, and share forms and templates to document activities taking place in each case. Iterations of activities may be necessary to ensure that stage-specific objectives are met. Checklists will assist in monitoring your progress and signal readiness to transition from one stage to the next.

Diagram: Stages of the more4nature Learning Journey

The diagram shows a vertical axis labeled 'EXPERIENCE' increasing upwards. The stages are:

- STAGE 2: ENGAGE** (case stakeholders for the learning journey): 2 Interaction moments & added stakeholders; Agreed vision ECA and principles for Learning; Detailed needs assessment completed.
- STAGE 3: EXPLORE** (roles of CDG and CCLA in collaborative ECA): Improvements in dynamics core actors; Tools, methods & CDG based indicators tested; Strengthened capacity of stakeholders; FAIR & CARE principles implemented.
- STAGE 4: CONSOLIDATE** (changes (social, institutional, technical)): Agreed Social Learning Agenda; Changes in norms, procedures, regulation; Indicators and alerting systems accepted; Case data in the GDDS node for CS.
- STAGE 5: CO-EVALUATE & SUSTAIN** (co-evaluate results & strengthen capacity to sustain changes): Increased institutional capacity; ECA institutionalised & systems sustained.

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Next to the description of the detailed activities per stage, the information provided in this compendium includes the tips how to apply the principles to each stage, and guidance on aspects that are likely to influence the successful achievement of stage objectives.

Please note that the case compendium is also a key tool to collect comparable insights from across all Pioneer and Follower Cases, which allows the more4nature project as a whole to learn from the case experiences. It ensures consistent implementation across the Pioneer Cases and presents the basis for comparison. Not every tool or proposed activity will feel equally useful for your specific case, but all will contribute to the collective effort of creating an active role for citizen science and community-led action in environmental compliance assurance.

How to use the compendium

Preview Pioneer Compendium ▾

- About the Pioneer Co... What is the Pioneer Com...
- Case Information How to use the Compen...
- Case Management Your role as Case Contact
- Stage 1 PREPARE
- Stage 2 ENGAGE
- Stage 3 EXPLORE
- Stage 4 CONSOLIDATE
- Stage 5 CO-EVALUATE...

Add section Add page

How to use the Compendium

Tuesday, June 25, 2024 4:05 PM

The process of working with the compendium is as follows:

1. WP1 and WP2 task leads prepare guidance that inform the activities in all more4nature case studies. These instructions are the same for all cases and these are collated in the generic compendium template. Each case study uses their own copy of the compendium (in their folder) as a workspace.
2. The case teams use the respective compendium for each case in their thematic area to record and report all results of their Learning Journey set-up and implementation activities, jointly filling in the documents over time. This ensures all information is easily accessible for all tasks in more4nature, without the need for much coordination.
3. The progressive completion of each case compendium [i.e. completion of tables in the main text and the respective compendium activities, as requested] feeds into and is undertaken during the regular thematic area team teleconferences and discussions. Layout elements and specific icons are used across all pages to indicate to the case contact what need to be done. The following elements are used.

Instructions

! Instructions are formatted in italics and tagged with an exclamation symbol.

Worksheets

Worksheets ask case contacts to enter information directly into the compendium. In worksheets, instructions are followed by placeholders or formatted spaces (e.g. tables) to fill in:

- Example 1: Placeholder to replace with an image

- Example 2: Table to fill in

Forms for Data Collection

Research Data is collected using appropriate online survey tools, such as Kobo Toolbox, Google Forms or ODK. Requests to submit data via survey tool are indicated with the form symbol

The process of working with the compendium is as follows:

1. WP1 and WP2 task leads prepare guidance that inform the activities in all more4nature case studies. These instructions are the same for all cases and these are collated in the generic compendium template. Each case study uses their own copy of the compendium (in their folder) as a workspace.
2. The case teams use the respective compendium for each case in their thematic area to record and report all results of their Learning Journey set-up and implementation activities, jointly filling in the documents over time. This ensures all information is easily accessible for all tasks in more4nature, without the need for much coordination.
3. The progressive completion of each case compendium [i.e. completion of tables in the main text and the respective compendium activities, as requested] feeds into and is undertaken during the regular thematic area team teleconferences and discussions.

Layout elements and specific icons are used across all pages to indicate to the case contact what need to be done. The following elements are used.

Instructions

! Instructions are formatted in italics and tagged with an exclamation symbol.

Worksheets

Worksheets ask case contacts to enter information directly into the compendium. In worksheets, instructions are followed by placeholders or formatted spaces (e.g. tables) to fill in:

- Example 1: Placeholder to replace with an image or file

- Example 2: Table to fill in

Forms for Data Collection

Research Data is collected using appropriate online survey tools, such as Kobo Toolbox, Google Forms or ODK. Requests to submit data via survey tool are indicated with the form symbol combined with a weblink or QR code (for KOBO mobile app) from the compendium.

Collaborative Documents

Collaborative documents are pre-formatted text documents, excel sheets, or presentations that are customized to your case and stored in the ‘supporting documents’ folder of your case in the online platform. Documents are ‘collaborative’ as they are typically edited by multiple members of the case team, either as aggregation of separate contributions, or simultaneously during workshops or online sessions. Requests to add information to a collaborative document are indicated with the indicated collaboration icon, combined with an internal link to the respective file in the case folder. **Always access a collaborative document through a link and edit the file online. DO NOT DOWNLOAD, COPY, MOVE, or substantially change the format or structure of a collaborative document**, as they need to remain accessible by teams and tasks, and their format needs to remain coherent across cases.

Templates

A template is a document provided by a project task for the purpose of collecting data outside the online tools linked to the compendium. Templates are files that are downloaded from a central repository, filled in ‘offline’, and are subsequently scanned or digitized and uploaded into specific folder in the online workspace. Templates are indicated with the indicated icon combined with a download link and instructions regarding upload of completed templates into a specific location in the ‘Compendium Supporting Docs’ folder.

Background information and resources

Throughout the compendium, you will find links to background materials and resources useful to complete activities and provide guidance to your case. Specifically, the compendium contains

1. Links to pages in an **online reference version of D3.1 Conceptual Frame and Methodology**. Any element of the conceptual frame or methodology mentioned in instructions in the compendium, such as “case context”, is linked to the respective section in the online reference in case you wish to refresh your memory of the meaning of different terms and their use in more4nature.
2. **Links to other section of the Case Compendium**. Information about the evolving case is collected by the case and provided to the case in line with the activities in the Learning Journey. Some data collection is spread over several activities, such as the stakeholder analysis, which is refined in several steps. The online format of the compendium makes it possible to present instructions and activities chronologically, while compiling resulting information into organically evolving resources accessible in multiple ways.

3. **Links to other more4nature deliverables** relevant to preparing activities or deepening the understanding of observations made in the Learning Journey.

Your role as Case Contact

Case contacts carry the primary responsibility for implementing the more4nature Action Research methodology in the Pioneer Cases. Case contacts are staff members of more4nature consortium partners and as such part of the project team with access to confidential and methodical aspects of the Learning Journey. Using the case compendium as working tool, you will act as interface between the project in participating CS initiatives and ECA actors.

The specific responsibilities of the more4nature Case Contacts is to:

4. **engage relevant actors** - Civil society (Community-led initiatives and CS initiatives), Institutional actors at the governance level relevant to the specific case (ECA authorities, enforcement agencies, legislators), experts (scientific and legal), and the private sector;
5. **stimulate social learning** among all actors involved in the more4nature cases, within the organizations to which they belong and at the institutional setting in which they operate; and, thus,
6. **bring about transformative change** towards collaborative environmental compliance assurance in the respective thematic areas of more4nature in the cases (zero pollution, biodiversity protection, deforestation prevention).

The role of the Case Contact the social learning process of the case stakeholders is summarized in the figure below.

Case contacts will be mentored by the more4nature thematic teams to enable them as facilitators of the Case Learning Journeys. Research shows that effective network management affects the outcomes of governance networks (Klijn, Steijn and Edelenbos, 2010), and related skills need to be carefully considered. Given the nature of the more4nature Learning Journey as process of Transformational Change, case contacts should be

considered as change agents (Irvine *et al.*, 2016). Change agents initiate and introduce changes within the system they work in (Atkisson, 2011). Successfully acting as change agent requires not just technical skills, but also intrinsic motivation, relational skills, openness to engage in reflexive learning methods, as well as awareness for normative dimensions involved in shaping institutional frameworks (Felder and Brent, 2004; Brundiers, Wiek and Redman, 2010; Myers, Staats and Gino, 2014).

Relational skills: Stakeholder engagement is a cornerstone of sustainable development, and requires collaborative planning and decision-making, building trust, maintaining relationships and valuing the contributions of diverse actors. Transformative change starts with securing commitment from leaders, buy-in from staff, and support from relevant external groups. Translated into competency needs for change agents, stakeholder engagement requires combinations of interpersonal and communication skills, process (management) competencies, open-mindedness and a willingness to learn and adapt (Kranz and Mostert, 2010; Atkisson, 2011; Lansu *et al.*, 2013; Wesselink *et al.*, 2015; Irvine *et al.*, 2016).

Normative and ethical aspects: The facilitation of task involving normative and ethical dimensions present specific challenges. Skills for the management of three aspects are of particular relevance:

- 4) **Building a shared understanding** of collaborative ECA. Stakeholders sometimes perceive initial sharing of their own knowledge and sense-making as lengthy and cumbersome. But since human understanding is shaped by culture and personal experience, even terms carrying a formal definition may have different interpretations, and identical ideas are expressed in different terms. Time invested in collaborative workshops is, therefore, rarely wasted. Jointly developing an agreed vision builds trust, reveals hidden values and creates pre-conditions for successful collaboration and programme implementation (Pfeiffer *et al.*, no date; Pfeiffer and Leentvaar, 2013).
- 5) **Dealing with ‘messy’ workplace realities**: Workshop exercises in project planning phases rarely anticipate that actors might refuse to listen to prepared presentations, react outraged or insulted at carefully thought-through solutions, fail to care about topic other parties are passionate about, or attempt to instrumentalize or manipulate the process for personal gain. Real-world decision-making is can be biased by power and personal affiliations, and dominated by greed, self-interest, or intransigent positions rooted in fear or ideology. Mentoring change agents, therefore, has to include tools for dealing with agendas and emotions. A particular challenge will be the ethical dimensions of transformative change and the potential ethical implications of the more4nature results.
- 6) **Personal values**: It is increasingly recognized that personal background and education influences how professionals envision and judge personal conduct in their chosen profession (Gantt and Madison, 2015). Case contacts bring their own identities, ambitions and expectations to the process, which can create specific challenges. Individuals with technical backgrounds often assume that information leads to knowledge which leads to behavioural changes. But change is ultimately facilitated by inspiring people to care about a subject, which cannot be “taught” (Pfeiffer *et al.*, no date; Brundiers, Wiek and Redman, 2010; Myers, Staats and Gino, 2014)

Accordingly, the mentoring of the Case contacts forms an integral part of the methodology, and will be embedded in the guidance for all activities of the Pioneer Case Learning Journeys.

Summary Section 2 (Deliverable only, not online)

Case Information

Preview Pioneer Compendium ▾	
About the Pioneer Co...	Case Summary
Case Information	Impact Journey
Case Management	Inputs from WP1
Stage 1 PREPARE	Policy analysis (case re...
Stage 2 ENGAGE	Actor agendas
Stage 3 EXPLORE	Inputs from WP2
Stage 4 CONSOLIDATE	Inputs from WP3
Stage 5 CO-EVALUATE...	Inputs from WP4
	Case Progress Reports

Purpose of the Section

This section compiles (updated) background information about the case to ensure summary information used across the project is always up-to-date. In many projects, detailed case information is collected and presented at the proposal stage, while information resulting from case progress is fragmented and distributed across files such as presentations to consortium meetings or annual reports. Similarly, Work Packages will provide inputs to specific case activities, but knowledge or perfect recall of activities is required to locate or re-use such inputs later. The compendium 'Case Information' provides a structured access to information about the case.

It includes one summary page based on the case information submitted at the proposal stage, which will be updated by case contacts, so it always reflects decisions made by the case stakeholders along the case journey. All other pages of the section will be filled cumulatively, for example recording results of exercises from consortium meetings, information produced by work packages for the cases, or extracting case-related paragraphs from annual reporting.

Pages in the Section

- Case Background
- Impact Journey
- Input from WP1
- Input from WP2
- Input from WP3
- Input from WP4
- Case Progress Reports

Case Summary

Preview Pioneer Compendium ▾
Sunday, June 23, 2024 9:44 AM

About the Pioneer Co...	Case Summary	<p>! This page serves to ensure that consistent, up-to-date information about your case is used across the project. In many projects, background information about cases is presented at the proposal stage, while information resulting from case progress is spread across presentations and annual reports. This summary page serves to update summary information from the proposal stage with decisions made by the case stakeholders along the case journey.</p> <p>Case Title Monitoring and achieving global biodiversity targets, Denmark <i>[replace generic title if/once case evolves into initiative locally named by partners]</i></p> <div style="text-align: center; margin: 10px 0;"> </div> <p>! <i>[provide (an) illustrative image(s) you suggest to use in publications featuring the case. Update as needed on discretion of case.]</i></p> <p>Case Summary ! <i>This table contains case information as presented in the project DoA. Please update as and when changes occur.</i></p> <p>External Resources ! <i>add selected links to relevant existing websites/resources from the case partner that can be used by new team members for easy orientation about the case (optional)</i></p>
Case Information	Impact Journey	
Case Management	WP1 Inputs	
Stage 1 PREPARE	Case-related opportunit...	
Stage 2 ENGAGE	T1.1 Policy analysis (case...	
Stage 3 EXPLORE	T1.2 ECA Indicators	
Stage 4 CONSOLIDATE	T1.4 Actor agendas/Res...	
Stage 5 CO-EVALUATE...	WP2 Inputs	
	WP3 Input: Showcases fro...	
	WP4 Input: Tested Tools a...	
	Case Progress Reports	

This page serves to ensure that consistent, up-to-date information about your case is used across the project. In many projects, background information about cases is presented at the proposal stage, while information resulting from case progress is spread across presentations and annual reports. This summary page serves to update summary information from the proposal stage with decisions made by the case stakeholders along the case journey.

Case Title

Monitoring and achieving global biodiversity targets, Denmark

! *[replace generic title if/once case evolves into initiative locally named by partners]*

! *[provide (an) illustrative image(s) you suggest to use in publications featuring the case. Update as needed on discretion of case.]*

Case Summary

This table contains case information as presented in the project [DoA](#). Please update as and when changes occur.

Example:

Case Code	B10-DK(N)
Theme	Biodiversity Protection
Level	National
Goal	Monitoring and achieving global biodiversity targets
Country	Denmark
Location	<i>[only for local cases]</i>
Lead Partner	NORD
Policy Context	Kunming-Montreal Global biodiversity framework (GBF). The European Green Deal, The Biodiversity Strategy 2030, The Farm to Fork Strategy, and SDG 14 & 15. The proposed new Danish Biodiversity Law
Authority	Nature and Biodiversity Division, Danish Ministry of Environment
Compliance need	All 195 parties to the CBD are required to track progress towards the goals and targets, using an agreed monitoring framework. Governments are encouraged to augment what they report by using CGD. Provisional estimates suggest 45% of the 291 proposed indicators can involve CGD.
Ongoing CS	Combination of existing initiatives including Arter.dk, Bugbase, DOFbasen, InsektObs
SH involved	10,000 citizen scientists across Denmark (local communities, people interested in nature)
CGD collected	Data available from the existing CSIs in Denmark. 20 datasets. GBF indicator examples: Change in the quality of coastal water ecosystems over time, Red List Index, and services provided by ecosystems

External Resources

add selected links to relevant existing websites/resources from the case partner that can be used by new team members for easy orientation about the case (optional)

Impact Journey

Preview Pioneer Compendium

- About the Pioneer Co... Case Summary
- Case Information Impact Journey
- Case Management WP1 Inputs
- Stage 1 PREPARE Case-related opportunit...
- Stage 2 ENGAGE T1.1 Policy analysis (case...
- Stage 3 EXPLORE T1.2 ECA Indicators
- Stage 4 CONSOLIDATE T1.4 Actor agendas/Res...
- Stage 5 CO-EVALUATE... WP2 Inputs
- WP3 Input: Showcases fro...
- WP4 Input: Tested Tools a...
- Case Progress Reports

Impact Journey

Sunday, July 28, 2024 12:23 PM

! *The impact journey exercise conducted during the [KoM meeting Delft 30 Jan -1 Feb 24](#) collected key information about the case situation at the start of the learning journey. Please transfer the results of your exercise into this page for easy reference.*

- ☞ If you completed the exercise, the digitized results are saved in your case folder in the shared workspace ([\\Documents\General\09 WP3 Case studies\T3.2 First Cycle\\[your theme\]\\[case code\]](#)) in a dedicated subfolder ... \3 Compendium Supporting files\Impact Journey*
- ☞ If you have not participated in the exercise, please use the [M4N impact journey template.pptx](#) to complete the worksheet below*

1) Starting state of the case regarding the role of CGD and CCLA

Compliance promotion	Compliance monitoring	Follow-up and enforcement

2) Starting state of relations between the key stakeholders

How do they relate & interact?	What are current levels & sources of (mis)trust?

The impact journey exercise conducted during the [KoM meeting Delft 30 Jan -1 Feb 24](#) collected key information about the case situation at the start of the Learning Journey. Please transfer the results of your exercise into this page for easy reference.

If you completed the exercise, the digitized results are saved in your case folder in the shared workspace ([\\Documents\General\09 WP3 Case studies\T3.2 First Cycle\\[your theme\]\\[case code\]](#)) in a dedicated subfolder ... \3 Compendium Supporting files\Impact Journey

If you have not participated in the exercise, please use the [M4N impact journey template.pptx](#) to complete the worksheet below

1) Starting state of the case regarding the role of CGD and CCLA

Compliance promotion	Compliance monitoring	Follow-up and enforcement

2) Starting state of relations between the key stakeholders

How do they relate & interact?	What are current levels & sources of (mis)trust?

3) Short term impacts the case hopes to achieve

In practice, collaborative environmental compliance assurance will mean:

For Compliance Monitoring (if applicable)
For Compliance Enforcement (if applicable)
For Compliance Promotion (if applicable)
For partnership & trust between the key institutional and civil society stakeholders

4) Long-term impacts the case hopes to achieve

Examples per applicable impact domain

Environmental impacts (if applicable)
Societal Impacts (if applicable)
Governance Impacts (if applicable)
Economic Impacts (if applicable)
Science & technology Impacts (if applicable)

Inputs from Work Packages

Pioneer Case Compendium ▾	
About the Pioneer Co...	Case Summary
Case Information	Impact Journey
Case Management	WP1 Inputs
Stage 1 PREPARE	Case-related opportun...
Stage 2 ENGAGE	T1.1 Policy analysis (ca...
Stage 3 EXPLORE	T1.2 ECA Indicators
Stage 4 CONSOLIDATE	T1.4 Actor agendas/Re...
Stage 5 CO-EVALUATE...	WP2 Inputs
	WP3 Input: Showcases fr...
	WP4 Input: Tested Tools ...
	Case Progress Reports

WP1 Inputs

Sunday, June 23, 2024 5:45 PM

■ This page indicates all inputs that will be provided by Work Package 1 tasks to your case, over the entire course of the learning journey. It serves to have a summary view and clarify what to expect, as well as to make inputs easy to locate and easy to access. However, it is not necessary for cases to monitor this page. Instructions for case activities during each stage will clearly indicate inputs that are available, and provide guidance how each input can assist with the completion of specific activity.

As new inputs are completed by the WP tasks

- Items marked with the link icon will be replaced with a link to an input document
- Case specific content will be copied directly into the linked subpage of your compendium

Stage 1

- Policy analysis (case relevant) (T1.1)
- Analysis of actor agendas/resources (T1.4)
- Template for national policy analysis (T1.1)
- Policy/legislation monitoring (T1.1/T4.5)

Stage 2

- Needs assessment tool (T1.4) for identifying key actors' incentives and barriers (to be completed by case stakeholders as part of Stage 2 activities)
- Comprehensive map of ECA indicators for which CS is already contributing data or has potential to do so in the future (T1.2, D1.2).
- FAIR & CARE principles (T1.3)
- Cross-case examples from policy context (T1.1)

This page indicates all inputs that will be provided by Work Package 1 tasks to your case, over the entire course of the Learning Journey. It serves to have a summary view and clarify what to expect, as well as to make inputs easy to locate and easy to access. However, it is not necessary for cases to monitor this page. Instructions for case activities during each stage will clearly indicate inputs that are available, and provide guidance how each input can assist with the completion of specific activity. Items marked with the link icon will be replaced with a link to an input document. Case specific content will be copied directly into the linked subpage of your compendium

Stage 1

- Policy analysis (case relevant) (T1.1)
- Analysis of actor agendas/resources (T1.4)
- Template for national policy analysis (T1.1)
- Policy/legislation monitoring (T1.1/T4.5)

Stage 2

- Needs assessment tool (T1.4) for identifying key actors' incentives and barriers (to be completed by case stakeholders as part of Stage 2 activities)
- Comprehensive map of ECA indicators for which CS is already contributing data or has potential to do so in the future (T1.2, D1.2).
- FAIR & CARE principles (T1.3)
- Cross-case examples from policy context (T1.1)

Stage 3

- Initial repository with capacity building tools & methods to address social & socio-technical needs (guidance for categorised needs) (T1.4)
- Methodology for co-designing (local) CCLAs in CS Initiatives and LivingLabs (T1.5)
- Initial set of proposed Indicators for the case (T1.2)

Stage 4

- Link to opportunities in National/EU fora for reviewing the law/policy relevant to the case. Including links to relevant CS experts to get involved (T1.1, T4.5, T3.5).

Case Progress Reports

This page serves to compile case inputs to 6-monthly internal reporting for easy reference and summary tracking of case progress. Use this page to draft your reporting input or copy the reporting input below once it has been prepared.

M6 Case Progress report
[please copy initial progress report here]

M12 Case Progress report

M18 Case Progress report

M24 Case Progress report

M30 Case Progress report

M36 Case Progress report

M42 Case Progress report

M48 Case Final report

Summary Section 3 (Deliverable only, not online)

Case Management

Preview Pioneer Compendium ▾	
About the Pioneer Co...	Case Contact Details
Case Information	Case File Management
Case Management	Stakeholder Management
Stage 1 PREPARE	Logbook Case meetings
Stage 2 ENGAGE	
Stage 3 EXPLORE	
Stage 4 CONSOLIDATE	
Stage 5 CO-EVALUATE...	

Purpose of the Section

Purpose of the Section is to create a central access point for all compendium elements that are used over the duration of the entire Learning Journey, or that reflect organizational or practical aspects or organizing the cases. It also serves to track staff changes.

Pages in the Section

- Case Contact Details
- Case File Management
- Stakeholder Management
- Logbook Case meetings

Case Contact Details

! ✎ 🖨

Home Insert Draw View Help Tell me what you want to do

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Preview Pioneer Compendium

- About the Pioneer Co... Case Contact Details
- Case Information Case File Management
- Case Management Stakeholder Managem...
- Stage 1 PREPARE Logbook Case meetings
- Stage 2 ENGAGE
- Stage 3 EXPLORE
- Stage 4 CONSOLIDATE
- Stage 5 CO-EVALUATE...

Case Contact Details

Sunday, June 23, 2024 9:44 AM

! Maintaining the Compendium is the **primary responsibility of the Case Contacts**. Please ensure this page includes up to date details of the current contact, and tracks any handover to a new contact. The information in this table will be used by the thematic team, but also to correctly attribute contributions or co-authorship in publications using case data.

Current Case Contact

First Name	Last Name	Organization
Email	Phone	Other contact
Start date	End date	Link to minutes of handover meeting
01-01-2024		

Past Contacts
(copy table of outgoing contact below this header upon handover)

M4N Team details of case thematic cluster
Role and function of [Thematic teams](#) in the methodology

Link to cumulative call notes of the thematic cluster bi-weekly online sessions:
[M4N Zero Pollution Coordination Call Notes.docx](#)

! Maintaining the Compendium is the primary responsibility of the Case Contacts. Please ensure this page includes up to date details of the current contact, and tracks any handover to a new contact. The information in this table will be used by the thematic team, but also to correctly attribute contributions or co-authorship in publications using case data.

Current Case Contact

First Name	Last Name	Organization
Email	Phone	Other contact
Start date	End date	Link to minutes of handover meeting
01-01-2024		

Past Contacts

! (copy table of outgoing contact below this header upon handover)

M4N Team details of case thematic cluster (Page customized to the thematic team of each case)

🔗 Role and function of [Thematic teams](#) in the more4nature methodology

Link to cumulative call notes of the thematic cluster bi-weekly online sessions:

[M4N Zero Pollution Coordination Call Notes.docx](#)

Role	Name
Thematic lead	Karin Dubsky, Coastwatch
WP1 Mentors	
T1.1 Policy context	Eléonore Maitre-Ekern, NIVA
T1.2 CGD & Indicators	Sasha Woods, Earthwatch
T1.3 FAIR&CARE	Sven Teurlincx, NIOO
T1.4 Incentives & barriers	Uta Wehn, IHE Delft
T1.5 Co-design of CCLA	Óscar González, IAAC
WP 2 Mentors	TBD
T3.1 Method mentors	Uta Wehn, IHE Delft Ellen Pfeiffer, IHE Delft

Link to cumulative call notes of the thematic cluster bi-weekly online sessions:

[M4N WP3 Biodiversity theme meeting notes.docx](#)

Role	Name
Thematic lead	Gitte Kragh, NORDECO
WP1 Mentors	
T1.1 Policy context	Eléonore Maitre-Ekern, NIVA
T1.2 CGD & Indicators	Sasha Woods, Earthwatch
T1.3 FAIR&CARE	Sven Teurlincx, NIOO
T1.4 Incentives & barriers	Uta Wehn, IHE Delft
T1.5 Co-design of CCLA	Óscar González, IAAC
WP 2 Mentors	TBD
T3.1 Method mentors	Uta Wehn, IHE Delft Ellen Pfeiffer, IHE Delft

Link to cumulative call notes of the thematic cluster bi-weekly online sessions:

[M4N WP3 Deforestation theme meeting notes.docx](#)

Role	Name
Thematic lead	Ida Theilade, Uni of Copenhagen

WP1 Mentors	
T1.1 Policy context	Eléonore Maitre-Ekern, NIVA
T1.2 CGD & Indicators	Sasha Woods, Earthwatch
T1.3 FAIR&CARE	Sven Teurlincx, NIOO
T1.4 Incentives & barriers	Uta Wehn, IHE Delft
T1.5 Co-design of CCLA	Óscar González, IAAC
WP 2 Mentors	TBD
T3.1 Method mentors	Uta Wehn, IHE Delft Ellen Pfeiffer, IHE Delft

Case File Management

! Please visit your [case folder](#) familiarize yourself with the file structure. Set up internal folders you need for your case and store files needed for collaborative work accordingly.

A standard set of five subfolders have been created in each Pioneer Case folder. Please preserve this structure and use it as indicated. This is important to keep data of all 20 cases accessible and manageable for the M4N work packages.

- **Red folders** are part of the methodology, and will be used by M4N tasks aggregating research data. Please use red folders only if and as instructed.
- **Yellow folders** can be structured and used at the **discretion of the cases**. (If your team already held meetings, minutes are filed under “Case Management”). Importantly, all M4N tasks will ignore the contents of the ‘internal workspace’. It can be used freely for incomplete drafts, working documents and anything else that is not ready for discussion. More information about the Case file management is included in the Compendium.
- **Green folders** are for storing case or communication materials that are approved for public distribution by the case contact, for example fact sheets that might be attached to emails for outreach or networking. Do not save confidential or otherwise restricted materials in the folder.

1 Case Management (use as applicable to case)

Location for all **organizational notes and files**. Content and formats as needed by case (Template available for meeting minutes.) Contents might be accessed for clarification by research teams. In particular

- Minutes of team meetings or other meetings ([template available](#))

- Activity planning
- Any other organizational documents

2 Documentation Learning Journey Events (use as guided)

Location for documentation of formal stakeholder events or workshops that form part of the case Learning Journey. Content will be used for project research purposes, and should only contain files linked to that purpose.

Cases will **create one subfolder per event within this folder**. Each event subfolder should be clearly named with the stage number, date and event name (e.g. "S2_12-11-2024_Launch meeting"). A subfolder for an individual event should contain:

- Invitation letters/formal correspondence & attendance lists
- presentations
- materials/handouts shared with stakeholders
- results of exercises not captured by the compendium itself (e.g. notes, digitized/photographed flipcharts, scanned worksheets)
- photographs of the event itself

3 Compendium supporting files (use as guided)

Location for collaborative documents and upload of filled templates that form part of the official methodology. Content will be used for project research purposes, and should only contain **files produced in response to activities in the case compendium**.

4 Communication Materials (ready for distribution only)

Location for case specific materials produced with or for WP4. Content should only contain materials that have been approved by the case lead for use and/or external distribution by more4nature.

5 Case workspace (internal files & drafts, use "as you see fit")

Location for all other case drafts, files and documents. Structure and content is at the discretion of the case. **All files will be considered case internal and not be used by the project for research purposes.**

Stakeholder Management for the case

Over the course of the next few months, you will identify, contact and interact with a wide range of stakeholders for your Pioneer Case. To keep track of the preparations and interactions, and to communicate the activities within the more4nature project for planning and research purposes, it is essential to collect stakeholder information in the following master list.

Logbook Learning Journey Events

Preview Pioneer Compendium ▾

- About the Pioneer Co... Case Contact Details
- Case Information Case File Management
- Case Management Stakeholder Management
- Stage 1 PREPARE Logbook Case meetings
- Stage 2 ENGAGE
- Stage 3 EXPLORE
- Stage 4 CONSOLIDATE
- Stage 5 CO-EVALUATE...

Logbook Case meetings

Tuesday, June 25, 2024 4:37 PM

■ The Case Meeting Logbook tracks the implementation of the method in the case, and captures the experience of the case with the activities. This generates important information about the context and effectiveness of each stakeholder workshop, as well as insights & lessons learned that will then feed into subsequent events. The Case Meeting Logbook is a key tool in making insights comparable across all Pioneer and Follower Cases, which allows the more4nature project as a whole to learn from the case experiences.

Overview Case Meetings

Entry #	Stage	Date	Title of event	Location
1				
2				
3				
...				

! *A logbook entry consists of four tasks that need to be completed for each stakeholder event*

1. **Enter** the date, title and location of the event in the summary table above
2. **Create a subfolder for the event** in the folder "2 Documentation Learning Journey Events" in your case folder in the online workspace. Name the subfolder clearly with the stage number, date and title of the event matching the entry in the table below (e.g. "S2_12-11-2024_Launch meeting"). In the event subfolder, save all files and documents produced for or during the event. In particular:
 - invitation letters/formal correspondence & attendance lists
 - presentations
 - materials/handouts shared with stakeholders
 - results of exercises not captured by the compendium itself (e.g. notes, digitized/photographed flipcharts, scanned worksheets)
 - photographs of the event itself

The Case Meeting Logbook tracks the implementation of the method in the case, and captures the experience of the case with the activities. This generates important information about the context and effectiveness of each stakeholder workshop, as well as insights & lessons learned that will then feed into subsequent events. The Case Meeting Logbook is a key tool in making insights comparable across all Pioneer and Follower Cases, which allows the more4nature project as a whole to learn from the case experiences.

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Entry #	Stage	Date	Title of event	Location
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 - invitation letters/formal correspondence & attendance lists
 - presentations
 - materials/handouts shared with stakeholders
 - results of exercises not captured by the compendium itself (e.g. notes, digitized/photographed flipcharts, scanned worksheets)

- *photographs of the event itself*

3. *During the event, please capture the experience of all participating case stakeholders with the **form 'Participant Evaluation'** (1 submission per participant).*

(link will be activated shortly)

4. *Please complete the form **Case Reflection** with the M4N team during a joint debriefing session (ca. 45-60 min.) that immediately follows the implementation of events.*

(link will be activated shortly)

Section Summary (Deliverable only, not online)

Stage 1 PREPARE

Preview Pioneer Compendium ▾	
About the Pioneer Co...	About Stage 1 - PREPARE
Case Information	Action 1: Rapid Screening
Case Management	Action 2: Team Vision
Stage 1 PREPARE	Activity 3: Stakeholder Analysis
Stage 2 ENGAGE	Activity 4: Setup Tools & Procedures
Stage 3 EXPLORE	Action 5: Tailor methods to comments
Stage 4 CONSOLIDATE	
Stage 5 CO-EVALUATE...	

Purpose of the Section

The five “stage” sections compile guidance and worksheets for the activities of the stages.

Pages in the Section

- About stage 1 – PREPARE
- Action 1.1 Rapid Screening
- Action 1.2 Team Vision
- Action 1.3 Stakeholder Analysis
- Action 1.4 Tailor methods to comments

About stage 1 – PREPARE

Summary

STAGE 1 – PREPARE	
Initial Screening and scoping to prepare engagement with core stakeholders	
Key activities & activity clusters	Envisioned outputs & outcomes per case
Rapid screening of context & case opportunities/challenges	Summary of contextual information per case
Develop a team vision of collaborative ECA for the case	Team vision for collaborative ECA of the case
Initial stakeholder analysis to identify potential Learning Journey participants	Initial set of relevant stakeholders identified & invited
Set up of stakeholder management tools & procedures	Sound set up of stakeholder management tools & procedures
Tailor methods to comments	
Interactions with more4nature WPs	
Inputs from WP1 to case	Outputs from case to WP1
Demonstration of existing tools for data cataloguing, accessing CGD and alerting apps.	Incremental input on national policy context (T1.1)
Inputs from WP2 to case	Outputs from case to WP2
Demonstration of existing tools for data cataloguing, accessing CGD and alerting apps.	Definition of the current status of the Pioneer Cases based on WP3 inputs.
Learning Dialogue & Reflection fostered across tasks and cases	
Mentoring session case contacts to prepare start of case learning journeys	

Purpose of the stage

The more4nature cases start in a situation characterized by strong power and information asymmetries between the case stakeholders involved, while confronting each case stakeholder actor with a challenge outside their current expertise.

Purpose of the stage is to create awareness for the

- **Civil society actors** in the more4nature Pioneer Cases have extensive experience in their field of environmental governance, but will typically not analyse issues from the specific legal and institutionalized perspective of Formal ECA.
- **Institutional actors** engage in the field based on formal mandates, and have access to internal information and policies, strategies and ECA practices as action resources. They are likely to consider citizen engagement in terms of citizen using tip lines or other channels offered to them, and might be less with the full potential of CS and CCLA.
- **Case contacts** share a high motivation to empower citizens in ECA, but the new role as stimulator of a guided social learning process might differ from past engagement with the stakeholders involved.

Citizen involvement in formal ECA is an ambition, not an entitlement. Institutional ECA actors might refuse to join the process, or drop out if they perceive a conflict with their mandate or priorities. Therefore, diligent preparation is crucial to prevent starting the case Learning Journey on the figurative 'wrong foot', and accidentally undermine successful incubation.

The purpose of the PREPARE stage is to clarify the starting point of the Learning Journey based on a more comprehensive understanding of the situation, and put into place the tools needed for successful initial engagement of case stakeholders

Objectives

- **Case Workspace** set up and **Thematic Team** mentoring process initiated
- **Rapid Assessment** of the case context, challenges and opportunities completed
- **Preliminary a team vision** of collaborative ECA developed to guide initial stakeholder identification and engagement planning
- Stakeholders **management tools** set up and an initial **stakeholder analysis** conducted
- **Methods** tailored to the needs of the context and local stakeholders

Stage Activities

Pioneer Cases enter the PREPARE stage with specific ideas and motivations regarding collaborative ECA, for example reflected in the results of the Case Impact Journey exercise completed in M2. The guided rapid assessment of the case context, challenges and opportunities invites the cases to take a step back from the experience-based planning, and test their understanding of situational and context aspects relevant to successfully initiating a transformative change process towards collaborative ECA. The results of the rapid assessment will then be used to review the ideas reflected in the Case Impact Journey template, checking if there is a need for adjustment to correct mistaken assumptions or misperceptions, in recognition of new priorities or previously unknown opportunities, or due to increased understanding of the legality or feasibility of original plans. Discussion will result in the development of a preliminary vision for collaborative ECA in the case. The team vision serves both to guide stakeholder identification, and to craft messaging for their engagement.

A second group of activities involves practical preparation of the Case Learning Journey, such as setting up the workspace including assembly of background and contact information, starting and customizing collaborative documents, and a review of local practicalities that affect planning of events.

Completion Checklist

- Completed the [rapid screening](#) and created summary context information on the case context and opportunities/challenges for collaborative ECA in the case
- Developed an [initial team vision](#) of collaborative ECA for the case
- Completed the [initial stakeholder analysis](#) and identified potential Learning Journey participants
- Solid [stakeholder management tools and procedures set up](#).
- Information on Initial participants [captured](#) and stakeholders invited
- All [methods tailored](#) to the needs of the case

